

Big Data to Enable Global Disruption of the Grapevine-powered Industries

D9.3 - Dissemination and Awareness Report

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ACRONYMS LIST

BDG	BigDataGrapes
DoA	Description of Actions
IT	Information technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
GFSI	Global Food Safety Initiative
DaaS	Data as a Service
EU	European Union
FP7	Framework Programme 7
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PaaS	Platform as a Service
MQL	Marketing Qualified Lead
SQL	Sales Qualified Lead
IoT	Internet of Things
API	Application Programming Interface

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

BigDataGrapes aims to help European companies in the wine and natural cosmetics industries become more competitive in the international markets. It specifically tries to help companies across the grapevine-powered value chain ride the big data wave, supporting business decisions with real time and cross-stream analysis of very large, diverse and multimodal data sources. The project involves the following types of commercial partners of the European grapevine-powered industries:

- Wine producers, bottlers and distributors that are managing large vineyards and are taking critical decisions that may affect (a) product lines, such as which grape varieties to combine and plant at which location and under which treatment in order to produce a new wine; or (b) production years, such as how to efficiently monitor and predict where careful vineyard management interventions should take place.
- Producers and packagers of food and wine products using grape by-products as ingredients (such as raisins, must, vinegar and grape juice) and that are continuously monitoring the quality of their product and assessing its vulnerability to risk.
- Natural cosmetic companies that have product lines based on grapes and wine that are continuously testing the quality of the grape extracts that they are using as ingredients and the corresponding suppliers.

BigDataGrapes also aims to improve the competitive positioning of companies in the European IT sector that are serving companies and organisations with software applications:

- Software companies developing farm management and precision agriculture systems for companies in the agriculture sector.
- Software companies developing food risk assessment monitoring and prediction systems for companies in the food sector.
- Software companies developing quality control and compliance software for companies in the beauty and cosmetics sector.

Furthermore, BigDataGrapes aspires to establish a framework facilitating the transparent documentation, exploitation and publication of research assets (datasets, software components results and publications), in order to enable their reuse and repurposing from the wider research community. Thus, the vision of BigDataGrapes project is to develop and demonstrate powerful data processing technologies that could initially serve all European companies active in two key industries powered by grapevines: the wine industry and the natural cosmetics one and it could be evolved to a BigDataGrapes entity demonstrator that will be positioned as the European grapevine-powered thematic entity.

WP9 concentrates on the dissemination of the project and its results among the identified target groups by using online and offline dissemination channels and activities. More specifically, WP9 focuses on (a) creating awareness and engaging further the scientific communities that are related to each one of the projects' pilots: Table and Wine Grapes Pilot (AUA), Wine Making Pilot (INRA), Farm Management Pilot (ABACO & GEOCLEDIAN), Natural Cosmetics Pilot (Symbeeosis) and Food Protection Pilot (Agroknow) (b) creating general awareness about BigDataGrapes and the types of innovative services that scientists may use, in other scientific communities and networks (Task 9.2). Moreover, linking BigDataGrapes with international initiatives and networks that are

working on open, big and interoperable data for agriculture and nutrition towards contributing to the corresponding standardisation work falls within the scope of WP9 under Task 9.3. Additionally, alignment of the work held in BigDataGrapes with the development and deployment of roadmap, to help positioning BigDataGrapes in the global Data as a Service (DaaS) and Platform as a Service (PaaS) ecosystems, as well as establish a legal entity for its future management and operation is part of Task 9.4.

Adapting our Dissemination Plan to Covid-19

We faced major challenges during the last year of the BigDataGrapes project, due to Covid-19. The new operational reality caused by the Covid-19 pandemic, presented unique dissemination challenges. Tailored dissemination plan was the key to a timely and strategic response to this quickly changing environment. The consortium plan was to reduce the travel and in-person meetings (most of the times traveling was also restricted by the national and EU laws) by turning to online events and digital media (e.g., webinars, short videos, and more) **to raise awareness, foster capacity building and knowledge sharing, adopting digital-centre dissemination actions.** Digital marketing is cost-effective, quickly implemented, easily measured, and it allows for great exposure.

Our conclusion in WP9 (see D9.2) is that the proposed innovations need an updated state of the art strategy in order to position competitively in the global market. After consulting with experts in the field, we are convinced that this revised strategy needs to be based on the principals of inbound and digital marketing to maximize the competitiveness of companies that choose to use the BigDataGrapes data from (Big) Data Platform. Agroknow, as the WP leader suggested and implemented a revised version of this deliverable that incorporated the revised dissemination and exploitation strategy. This is the final version of the deliverable aiming at reporting the final dissemination activities, taking into account all recommendations during the lifespan of the project.

WP9 has created an online infrastructure (including project website and social media channels) and a set of print dissemination materials to promote the project (as presented in Annex B). By the end of the project, the project website has been visited by 4.252 people (unique visitors) and the social media channels count 550 followers (Twitter, LinkedIn, SlideShare and YouTube), 3.105 views (SlideShare) and 510 views (YouTube). Also, the project partners prepared 15 online press publications and communicated the project objectives and vision via online dissemination media (see section 6.1). These numbers were achieved as soon as additional tangible results were available during the second period of the project (M19-M36).

Finally, our consortium organized 6 workshops in well-known and relevant conferences (for more details see section 4.1.1), 6 webinars demonstrating the project's outcomes to the scientific communities (for more details see section 4.2) and 10 open days in the partners premises, inviting stakeholders interested to discover the BigDataGrapes results (for more details see section 4.3). Moreover, we attended in 18 events in order to disseminate our results from which: (i) 6 were training events of young scientists (e.g., summer schools); (ii) 8 events targeted to special interest groups in specialised forums, standardisation groups, global networks; (iii) 4 events at AgriTech commercial exhibitions and trade fairs (for more details see section 4.4). In total, more than 545.100 stakeholders have been reached, 47 scientific papers (journal papers and conference papers) were submitted for publication or published (see Section 6.2) and 3 extra papers (i.e., two white papers and one discussion paper) have been created in order to outreach policy & decision makers and inform them about project activities, outcomes, successes and societal impact we develop (see section 6.4).

This deliverable describes online and offline dissemination channels, as well as activities, which were conducted until the end of the project. Moreover, it provides an outlook of the dissemination activities that were implemented in order to increase project's engagement with SMEs. The collaboration of BigDataGrapes project with other EU and international projects by providing tools and services is also demonstrated. Finally, Key Performance Indicators are described and applied to measure the effectiveness of dissemination.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 OUR EXPECTED IMPACT

Data analysis facilitates the optimization of processes and decisions, innovation, and the prediction of future events. This global trend holds enormous potential in various fields and is of high relevance and significance for the European companies active in the grapevine-powered industries. BigDataGrapes aims to achieve impact in two areas of paramount importance for the EU.

First, to illustrate how European companies operating in the agriculture, food and beauty sectors may generate value by data assets. This will be achieved by introducing them to software and IT architecture solutions that are capable of processing, analysing and visualising extremely big and heterogeneous data within real life business applications. This is linked to the primary goal of BigDataGrapes to develop and demonstrate powerful data processing tools and methods that are produced by EU technology partners, rigorously tested in data challenges that representatives of the grapevine-powered industries face while competing in the global market.

Second, to increase the competitiveness of the European IT companies that serve organisations in the agriculture, food and beauty sectors. This will be achieved by engaging them deeper into data economy challenges of these particular sectors and helping them work on methods, standards and processes that will enable free, interoperable and secure data flows. This is linked to the second goal of BigDataGrapes to demonstrate how data value chains may be created in the grapevine-powered industries via deploying a proof-of-concept data marketplace for sharing and accessing large and heterogeneous grapevine-related data assets from both corporate and public organisations.

1.2 OUR HIGH-LEVEL IMPACT INDICATORS

The table below illustrates all the **Key performance indicators** that BigDataGrapes partners were expected to implement to contribute to the anticipated impacts set out in the Work Programme of the call along with their targeted and achieved goals.

Work Programme aim	BigDataGrapes contribution	Key performance indicators
Powerful (Big) Data processing tools and methods that demonstrate their applicability in real-world settings	Will produce a software stack of components for distributed data and process mining, predictive analytics and visualisation trained using sector-specific data.	1) # of tested and prove components for processing, analytics and visualisation (target: >4 VS achieved: 8)
	Will produce a software stack of components for complex event processing proven to perform better over extremely large numbers of high-volume streams of noisy and incomplete data.	2) # of tested and proven components for complex event processing (target: >3 VS achieved: 3)
	Will deploy software demonstrators for decision support over extremely large	3) # of deployed software demonstrators in real life business scenarios (target: >5 VS achieved: 9)

	numbers of high volume streams of noisy and incomplete data in real life settings	4) # of typical users recruited as testers in all software demonstrators (target: >40 VS achieved: 46)
Including the data experimentation/integration (ICT-14) and Large Scale Pilot (ICT-15) projects	Will liaise with the 35MEuros “IoF 2020: Internet of Food and Farm” large scale IoT pilot that has a designated, large-scale, cross-Europe trial on Big Wine Optimisation.	5) # of use cases to be validated with projects having similar pilot trials (target:>3 VS achieved: 4)
	Will liaise with the 16MEuros “DataBio: Data- Driven Bioeconomy” large scale lighthouse pilot that will build an industrial-scale big data platform that will be tested in an agricultural pilot.	6) # of large scale data sets shared with other projects (target: >15 VS achieved: 16)
	Will liaise with ICT-14 projects for data integration working on relevant topics to share data assets and software services (such as EWShopp working on integrating customer-related data & analytics and SLIPO for DOI integration).	7) # of software stack components shared with other projects (target: >5 VS achieved: 18)
	Will liaise with ICT-14 projects for data experimentation to share business challenges and reference data that will invite and engage more EU startups that will support grapevine related industry players (such as Data Pitch).	8) # of joint events with relevant projects (target: >8 VS achieved: 8)
Demonstrated, significant increase of speed of data throughput and access, as measured against relevant, industry-validated benchmarks	Will generate gold standard and industry-specific data sets that can be used to train and benchmark technical performance on reference data relevant to the grapevine-powered industries	9) # of reference data sets specific to the grape vine powered industries (target: >10 VS achieved:31)
	Will perform experimental testing that will measure and illustrate improvements on technical performance parameters such as speed, scalability and robustness against relevant industry-validated benchmarks.	10) # of testing experiments measuring technical performance over industry validated benchmarks (target: >10 VS achieved:10)
	Will perform experimental testing that will compare the developed software stack against competing approaches from outside Europe (i.e. North America and China).	11) # of testing experiments measuring technical performance against non- European data processing (target: >5 VS achieved: 5)
Substantial increase in the definition and update of standards fostering data sharing, exchange and interoperability	Will contribute to the mapping, expansion and improvement of sector-specific standards for data sharing, exchange and interoperability within the registry of Agroportal and the VEST registry.	12) # of grapevine-related data standards registered (target: >10 VS achieved: 12)

	Will evolve the W3C Community Group on Agriculture and pursue the creation of W3C Interest & Working Groups on sector-specific data standards.	13) # of contributions to W3C groups on relevant data standards (target:>2 VS achieved: 2)
	Will contribute to the Agrisemantics initiative & contribute to the publication & linking of grapevine-related ontologies as SKOS.	14) # of grapevine-related ontologies published as SKOS (target:>10 VS achieved: 12)
	Will contribute to the GODAN Data Ecosystem WG & participate to the Technology & Interoperability sub-group to disseminate relevant standards for data sharing.	15) # of Data Ecosystem WG events devoted to data sharing, exchange & interoperability (target:>5 VS achieved: 5)

Table 1: BigDataGrapes KPIs

1.3 OUR WAY TO MAXIMIZE IMPACT

BigDataGrapes includes in its workplan a dedicated dissemination and exploitation plan (D9.2 | Dissemination & Exploitation Plan) that was initially developed at the beginning of the project and updated in order to depict all the changes in the internal and external environment (i.e., Covid-19 outbreak) of the project. Thus, our plan was particularly focused on the way in which the project work and outcomes will be communicated to its key targeted stakeholders:

- a) Targeted beneficiaries/users: beneficiary industries working on the variety of agricultural, food and beauty sectors.
- b) Technology providers: private and public organisations of various sizes (from large IT and agri-food industry players to young dynamic AgriTech and IT startups) that develop technology solutions of relevance to the agriculture, food and beauty markets and their value chains.
- c) Data providers and initiatives: various types of public and private institutions that are collecting, managing, using and publishing agriculture and food data. Includes a wide range of institutions (and people working in these institutions), from agricultural research institutes and ministries of agriculture, to food agencies and authorities.

The sections following present and analyse the qualitative and quantitative results of all the dissemination and exploitation activities we carried out during the whole lifespan of the project.

2 DISSEMINATION OF PROJECT RESULTS

2.1 OUR DISSEMINATION AIMS

Our approach to dissemination will be layered, starting from the partner organisations themselves, moving out to the whole consortium, to the directly connected networks, and then other relevant stakeholders. As soon as we have defined an initial version of the core concept, its unique value proposition, and the key messages to be used/tested, we will start working on this dissemination approach. This is particularly important in BigDataGrapes because the consortium includes three industrial partners that belong to larger groups of companies (**ONTOTEXT/SIRMA AI**, **ABACO** and **SYMBEEOISIS**) and four major research stakeholders (**CNR**, **INRA**, **AUA** and **KULEUVEN**) that have several departments, labs and teams – these should be informed about the project and get involved in it. Furthermore, since the consortium includes partners that participate in several strategic networks, as the dissemination activities move to the outer layer more and more relevant stakeholders will be engaged. The table that follows briefly outlines the aims, methods and stakeholders of each level.

2.2 OUR DISSEMINATION KPIS

This section describes Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which were used to measure the efficiency of the project dissemination activities in order to keep overview of the current status and to define (corrective) activities for the project periods. The evaluation was conducted from the first year of the project until the third and last one. The KPIs are based on those defined in Deliverable “D9.2 – Dissemination and Exploitation Plan” and they are further analysed with planned values for each year of the project.

The following KPIs (presented also in Table 2) measured the project **branding and the communication material**:

K1.1 - Project Website Unique Visitors: The reach of the project website was measured based on the unique visitor number. The KPI was measured through Google Analytics which was connected with our website. Through the big volume of blog posts we published we overcame the expected target and we accounted 1.752 extra unique visitors. More details for the K1.1 are presented in the Section 3.1.

K1.2 – Project Audience (Social Media Followers and Likes): This KPI provided the number of the anticipated project audience through our social media pages (Twitter, SlideShare, YouTube, LinkedIn). Several posts of high-quality content were uploaded during the lifetime of the BigDataGrapes project, engaged **50 additional followers** in comparison with the final target of 500 followers. All our actions are described in Section 3.2.

K1.3 - Dissemination Materials: It measured the number of different dissemination materials that were created for, mainly, offline promotion activities of the project aiming to expand the BigDataGrapes results and pull a “critical-mass” of stakeholders. More information about the dissemination material can be found on the Section 6.3.

K1.4 Videos of BigDataGrapes project: This KPI measured the number of project videos that were prepared during the project lifespan. In particular, we uploaded **14 videos** (10 extra that the initial target) with different contents, magnetizing the interest and increasing the interaction with our key-groups. All the videos, with a short-description can be found on the Section 3.2.2.

No	KPI	Target Source		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Sum
K1.1	Project Website Unique Visitors	Own Target	Annual Target	500	1.000	2.500	Sum: 2.500
			Achieved Value	461	1.509	4.252	Sum: 4.252
K1.2	Project Audience (Social Media Followers and Likes)	Own Target	Annual Target	100	200	500	Sum: 500
			Achieved Value	138	193	550	Sum: 550
K1.3	Dissemination Materials	DoA	Annual Target	2	2	5	Sum: 5
			Achieved Value	2	2	5	Sum: 5
K1.4	Videos of BigDataGrapes project	Own Target	Annual Target	-	1	4	Sum: 4
			Achieved Value	-	1	14	Sum: 14

Table 2: Branding & Communication Material, Channels KPIs (cumulative values)

The following KPIs (presented also in Table 3) measure the **project campaigns**:

K2.1 – Digital campaigns: This KPI measured the number of online campaigns targeting H2020 project coordinators & data managers. During the project’s lifetime we achieved to complete 11 newsletter campaigns (8 extra that the initial target) where all of them came in the last year of the project. Moreover, we orchestrate digital campaigns through LinkedIn. Details are given in the Section 3.2.5.

K2.2 - Outreach to general press and media: This KPI measured the number of press releases on project stories & outcomes, as well as interviews with project members and all our relevant Medium articles. The number was set at 15 in the beginning of the project and we covered all of them, were most of the volume came during the last year. The material used to outreach to general press and media have been described in Section 6.1.

K2.3 - Outreach to social media (LinkedIn & Twitter): This KPI was not in the DoA but we added it in order to keep up with the new digital strategy we proposed and implement in our dissemination plan (D9.2). It was added as a replacement of the Open data challenges & awards which we foreseen as unachievable. The KPI represents the number of posts published at LinkedIn and Twitter, in order to promote and raise awareness for the project’s results. While for the first and the second project period, this indicator equaled to 47 and 97 respectively, in the third year we got 62 posts, achieving a total of **159 posts and exceeding our target by 39**. Both of the content and the posts are described with more details in the Sections 3.2.1 and 3.2.4 and in Annex C.

No	KPI	Target		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Sum
K2.1	Digital campaigns	DoA	Annual Target	-	1	3	Sum: 3
			Achieved Value	-	-	11	Sum: 11
K2.2	Outreach to general press and media	DoA	Annual Target	5	10	15	Sum: 15

			Achieved Value	1	3	15	Sum: 15
K2.3	Outreach to social media (LinkedIn & Twitter)	Own Target	Annual Target	40	80	120	Sum: 120
			Achieved Value	47	97	159	Sum: 159

Table 3: Campaign KPIs (cumulative values)

The following KPIs (presented also in Table 4) measure the project **science and technology outreach**:

K3.1 - Editing of special topic volumes & journal issues: This KPI measured the number of edited volumes or journal special issues. We didn't manage to achieve this KPI, because none possibilities arise in editing a special topic volume. However, the Science & Technology Outreach goal was achieved through all the other KPIs presented as follows (e.g., we published a great number of scientific papers in journals and conferences).

K3.2 - Publication of scientific papers in journals or conferences: This KPI measured the number of scientific publications related to the project to conference proceedings, journals and book chapters. Our goal was to reach at least 30 publications, but we finally manage overcome this number and publish 47 scientific papers (17 extra that the initial target). Further, a more analytic description is described in Section 6.2.

K3.3 - Organisation of special sessions or workshops in scientific conferences: This KPI measured the number of special sessions organized in workshops or conferences. During the project's lifetime we organized 6 workshops (2 extra than the initial target). More information is presented in Section 4.1.1.

K3.4 - Promotion of targeted news items for scientists and experts through specialised channels: This KPI measured the number of news items and blog posts published at the project website. For the first, the second and the third project year, this indicator equalled to 45 and we publish 67 news items (12 extra that the initial target). More information is presented in the Section 3.3.

K3.5 - Participation to training events of young scientists (e.g., summer schools, summer institutes): This KPI measured the number of lecture & hands-on workshops related with the project and it was achieved totally by the end of the last year. More details for the participation of our consortium members in training events of young scientists can be found on the Section 4.4.

K3.6 - Organisation of webinars for scientists: This KPI measured the organization of webinars towards presenting the project outcomes to external stakeholders interested to the project technologies and pilots. We achieved this KPI by organizing 6 workshops. More information is presented in the Section 4.2.

K3.7 - Open days at partner premises: This KPI measured the number of open days organized at partners' premises regarding the project. This indicator equaled to 10, a number that was achieved gradually during the three years of the project and it includes the events organized and described in Section 4.3.

K3.8 - Special interest groups in specialised forums, standardisation groups, global networks: This KPI measured the number of working groups or special interest groups that the project participated. In particular, we represent BigDataGrapes to 8 events (4 extra than the initial target) such as Workshops, Conferences and Meetings with different type of audience to be attended (e.g., research and industry key-groups, policy makers, etc.). All the material from these events can be found on the Section 4.4.

K3.9 - Preparation of articles in general science communication & publication outlets: This KPI measured the number of articles published at journals and conferences. We completed the K3.9 by crafting 4 articles of high-content (1 extra than the initial target). The titles, the type of the articles and a short description of their content can be found on the Section 6.1.

No	KPI	Target	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Sum	
K3.1	Editing of special topic volumes & journal issues	DoA	Annual Target	-	-	1	Sum: 1
			Achieved Value	-	-	0	Sum: 0
K3.2	Publication of scientific papers in journals or conferences	DoA	Annual Target	-	10	30	Sum: 30
			Achieved Value	9	22	47	Sum: 47
K3.3	Organisation of special sessions or workshops in scientific conferences	DoA	Annual Target	1	2	4	Sum: 4
			Achieved Value	1	5	6	Sum: 6
K3.4	Promotion of targeted news items for scientists and experts through specialised channels	DoA	Annual Target	15	30	45	Sum: 45
			Achieved Value	11	34	67	Sum: 67
K3.5	Participation to training events of young scientists (e.g., summer schools, summer institutes)	DoA	Annual Target	-	3	6	Sum: 6
			Achieved Value	1	4	6	Sum: 6
K3.6	Organisation of webinars for scientists	DoA	Annual Target	2	4	6	Sum: 6
			Achieved Value	-	1	6	Sum: 6
K3.7	Open days at partner premises	DoA	Annual Target	-	5	10	Sum: 10
			Achieved Value	0	0	10	Sum: 10
K3.8	Special interest groups in specialised forums, standardisation groups, global networks	DoA	Annual Target	-	2	4	Sum: 4
			Achieved Value	2	5	8	Sum: 8
K3.9	Preparation of articles in general science communication & publication outlets	DoA	Annual Target	1	2	3	Sum: 3
			Achieved Value	0	2	4	Sum: 4

Table 4: Science & Technology Outreach KPIs (cumulative values)

The following KPIs (presented also in Table 5) measure the project business outreach:

K4.1 - Organise national opened hackathons & meetups: This KPI measured the number of hackathons or meetups that the project organized. Due to the unprecedented difficulties faced by the world community with the Covid19 outbreak, we were not able to organize open hackathons or meetups for companies. However, we perform a series of training meetups with 29 companies and 1 workshop in order to fulfil this indicator and maximize the business outreach.

K4.2 – BigDataGrapes early-stage incubation of innovative start-ups: This KPI measured the number of incubation activities for innovative start-ups building on the project infrastructure. In total, our project offered its expertise in 5 start-ups (3 extra that the initial target) which were: 1) isMOOD, 2) CremeGlobal, 3) ProvisionAnalytics, 4) Mesh Intelligence and 5) Britescan. More information about this action is provided in the Section 5.1.

K4.3 – BigDataGrapes representation at AgTech commercial exhibitions and trade fairs: This KPI measured the number of commercial exhibitions and trade fairs that the BigDataGrapes’ partners participated. Our project partners participated in the following 4 commercial exhibitions and trade fairs: Global forum for Innovations in Agriculture, Seeds & Chips, TuttoWine (part of TuttoFood) and Agritechnica. Section 4.4 provides further information about these trade fairs and exhibitions where BigDataGrapes had the chance to present its results in front of approximately 545.000 participants.

No	KPI	Target		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Sum
K4.1	Organise national opened hackathons & meetups	Own Target	Annual Target	-	1	2	Sum: 2
			Achieved Value	-	-	30	Sum: 30
K4.2	BigDataGrapes early-stage incubation of innovative startups	DoA	Annual Target	-	-	2	Sum: 2
			Achieved Value	-	-	5	Sum: 5
K4.3	BigDataGrapes representation at AgTech commercial exhibitions and trade fairs	DoA	Annual Target	1	2	3	Sum: 3
			Achieved Value	1	4	4	Sum: 4

Table 5: Business outreach KPIs (cumulative values)

The following KPIs (presented also in Table 6) measure the project **business outreach**:

K5.1 - Outreach of policy & decision makers informing about project activities, outcomes, successes, societal impact: This KPI measured the actions needed in order to inform policy & decision makers about the project’s activities, outcomes, successes, societal impact. In total, two (2) industry white papers and one (1) discussion paper have been published to guide decision makers about the project’s outcomes. More information for the white and discussion papers are presented in the Section 6.4.

K5.2 - Organize coordination meetings of H2020 big data and IoT project coordinators: This KPI measured the number of H2020 project coordinators’ information days to be organized by the project. Eight (8) coordination

meetings of H2020 organized by our consortium (5 extra that the initial target) and more specifically with the SFARM, Aginfra+, TheFSM, IOF2020, Ochrvine Control, Diversify, SmartCow and CYBELE projects. The partners that participated in these meetings were respectively the AUA for the first and last one and Agroknow for the rest of them. All of the information and details for these meetings are described in Sections 7.1 – 7.4.

No	KPI	Target		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Sum
K5.1	Outreach of policy & decision makers informing about project activities, outcomes, successes, societal impact	DoA	Annual Target	0	0	3	Sum: 3
			Achieved Value	-	-	3	Sum: 3
K5.4	Organise coordination meetings of H2020 big data and IoT project coordinators	DoA	Annual Target	1	2	3	Sum: 3
			Achieved Value	-	3	8	Sum: 8

Table 6: Policy Outreach KPIs (cumulative values)

Regardless the bottlenecks which BigDataGrapes faced during the three-year presence, and especially due to the Covid-19 outbreak, we finally succeeded to overcome most of them and keep-up with the indicators that were originally set. As actions speak louder than words, we continued to bring the expected results to the European stakeholders, showing that our project is extra responsible and agile to its commitments.

3 DIGITAL DISSEMINATION CHANNELS

To unleash our influence and engage those who matter along the path of supporting the European companies in two key industries powered by grapevines (the wine industry and the natural cosmetics one), we applied a dynamic approach to dissemination and growth-hacking. This section provides the list of the project's online dissemination channels that are used to promote its main outcomes and to attract the targeted stakeholders to actively participate in its activities.

The main online dissemination mean was the **project website** that presented all the project information and the progress until the end of the project. Additionally, the project **social media** such as LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube and SlideShare were the core online channels for informing the target groups about the project outcomes and the dissemination activities, like the presence in key events (workshops and conferences) and the organization of project's workshops. For the dissemination of these activities some **digital marketing campaigns** had also been implemented and several blog posts had been published in the **project's news blog**.

Adapting our Dissemination Plan to COVID-19

We faced major challenges during the last year of the BigDataGrapes project, due to COVID-19. The new operational reality caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, presented unique dissemination challenges. Tailored dissemination plan was the key to a timely and strategic response to this quickly changing environment. The consortium plan was to reduce the travel and in-person meetings (most of the times traveling was also restricted by the national and EU laws) by turning to online events and digital media (e.g., webinars, short videos, and more) **to raise awareness, foster capacity building and knowledge sharing, adopting digital-centre dissemination actions**. Digital marketing is cost-effective, quickly implemented, easily measured, and it allows for great exposure.

3.1 PROJECT WEBSITE

BigDataGrapes website (<http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/>) was the main-core online dissemination channel used to promote the project, to apply our growth hacking activities and to increase the stakeholders' awareness of the project activities. It provided general information about the project vision and objectives, research activities and important results, workshops and other project events. Furthermore, the project website established connection to offline dissemination activities promoting them and providing print materials, scientific papers and official deliverables for download. Contact information of consortium partners could also be found on the website. Below there is a figure that presents the main page of the BigDataGrapes website.

Figure 1: The BigDataGrapes Website

A strong web presence was critical for achieving the desired impact of the BigDataGrapes project and for increasing the brand’s awareness through the dissemination activities dedicated to the outcomes of the project and specifically targeting the intended stakeholders and target groups. To this end, the first step for ensuring this strong presence was the setup of BigDataGrapes dedicated spaces in Social media and content sharing platforms. Based on the consortium’s collective experience, the most impactful digital channels have been targeted (for details see Section 3.2).

Project website and project news blog (<http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/news>) were launched in January 2018 (M1). The main purpose of this blog was to inform the stakeholders about the latest news (e.g., pilots, new developments, project materials, announcements about organized and up-coming events, impressions from past events, etc). Notes on scientific outcomes of the project, implementation results, as well as particularities of technical realizations could also be published on the blog.

In order to measure the dissemination rate of the website and to collect general information about the users, the project website has been connected to Google Analytics since the 18th of July 2018 (M7). From M1 until M36, the website was visited, based on the Figure 2 which represents the number of visitors who accessed the

website for the period between 01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020, by **4,252 unique users**, with an average session duration of **2 minutes and 37 seconds**. The country with the most traffic to our website, based on the Figure 3 which represents the traffic per country in the website for the period between 01.01.2018 to 31.12.2020, was Greece (12.93%), **United States** (11.02%), **Italy** (10.48%), **France** (8.03%), **China** (4.55%), **Spain** (4.39%), **Germany** (4.20%), **India** (3.85%), **United Kingdom** (3.11%) and **Belgium** (2.87%), and other countries. 12% of visitors are new, and 88% are returning visitors.

Figure 2: Visits of the BigDataGrapes website [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

Country	Users	% Users
1. Greece	554	12.93%
2. United States	472	11.02%
3. Italy	449	10.48%
4. France	344	8.03%
5. China	195	4.55%
6. Spain	188	4.39%
7. Germany	180	4.20%
8. India	165	3.85%
9. United Kingdom	133	3.11%
10. Belgium	123	2.87%

Figure 3: The BigDataGrapes website traffic per country [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

Following the line chart of the Figure 2, we can see that on 2019 the most prominent peaks on the chart were appeared on 22 January during the days of the first BigDataGrapes Kick-off Meeting and on 28th of May, one day before the BigDataGrapes project Webinar on Field Monitoring, as well as during other dissemination and policy activities between the 5-13 of April, namely (a) Webinar on Field Monitoring with Geocledian's

Ag|knowledge API & Tools on 29th of May 2019 (b) Workshop on “Big Data for the Grapevine Industries” on 8th of April 2019.

On the Figure 4, we can also see the traffic sources that are represented as follows: 45.32% **organic search** (coming directly from Google search), 44.59% **direct traffic**, 7.4% **social traffic** (through social media) and 5.79% **referral** (redirection from other websites).

	Acquisition			Behavior		
	Users ↓	New Users ↓	Sessions ↓	Bounce Rate ↓	Pages / Session ↓	Avg. Session Duration ↓
	4,247	4,252	6,006	60.94%	2.63	00:02:37
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						

Figure 4: Traffic sources of the users [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

Most of the users’ land on the **homepage** (33.90%), whereas other frequent landing pages are the pages related to **news** (7.24%), **partners** (6.44%), **about the project** (6.25), **events** (5.79%) project **deliverables** (4.40%), **wine making pilot** (2.86), **contact us** (2.12), **farm management pilot** (1.96) and **table and wine grapes pilot** (1.75).

Page Title	Pageviews	% Pageviews
1. Welcome BigDataGrapes	5,372	33.90%
2. News BigDataGrapes	1,147	7.24%
3. Partners BigDataGrapes	1,020	6.44%
4. About the Project BigDataGrapes	991	6.25%
5. Events BigDataGrapes	918	5.79%
6. Deliverables BigDataGrapes	697	4.40%
7. Wine Making Pilot BigDataGrapes	454	2.86%
8. Contact us BigDataGrapes	336	2.12%
9. Farm Management Pilot BigDataGrapes	310	1.96%
10. Table and Wine Grapes Pilot BigDataGrapes	278	1.75%

Figure 5: Users’ land on the BigDataGrapes website

Finally, following the Figure 6 and the line chart, we can have an overview of the whole website traffic during the lifespan of the project. In total the pageviews were **15.788**, from which 11.607 were unique pageviews, with the average time on page to be **1 minute and 35 seconds**.

Figure 6: BigDataGrapes website pageviews and unique pageviews [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

KPI	KPI	Target	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Remaining Values
1.1	Project Website Unique Visitors	Annual Target	500	1000	2500	1752
		Achieved Value	461	2308	4252	

Table 7: BigDataGrapes website KPI

3.2 SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS

Through social media, BigDataGrapes sought to foster regular and timely conversations with the key stakeholders, generate through leadership and engagement, and unlock the hidden streams of our project leads. In order to support communication between the project (represented by particular consortium members) and external stakeholders from the targeted project communities, BigDataGrapes provided pages to four (4) main social media platforms, namely:

- BigDataGrapes Twitter - (<https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes>)
- BigDataGrapes YouTube - (<https://bit.ly/2x3ijLL>)
- BigDataGrapes SlideShare - (<https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes>)
- BigDataGrapes LinkedIn - (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13574473/>)

The content uploaded in the abovementioned platforms, was reliable, respective and high-quality. Our main target was to be distributed in an easy-to understand format and generate take-away messages on the activities, the generated knowledge and best practices of the usage of big data. Moreover, we collaborate with other projects and influencers achieving even higher dissemination of the key-messages that BigDataGrapes brings to the market.

Nr.	Social Media	Followers	Lead Partner
1	LinkedIn	173	Agroknow
2	Twitter	348	Agroknow
3	SlideShare	9	Agroknow
4	YouTube	20	Agroknow

Table 8: BigDataGrapes Social media KPI [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

3.2.1 TWITTER

The BigDataGrapes Twitter account (<https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes>) created in November 2017. Twitter was extremely useful to inform and engage our targeted audiences and their respective communities, as it was easy for followers to be engaged with the BigDataGrapes project, either by following, mentioning, retweeting or connecting with our tweets.

Our main focus was to build a community, in which our information about the latest updates on new events, discussions, news and series of videos would continue to be provided via Twitter. For this reason, we connected to “high influencers” in the research and business topics of the BigDataGrapes project, in order to create a high-value network for dissemination.

Below, we provide the statistics of our Twitter account (e.g., Tweets, Followers, Likes, etc.) which came through Twitter Statistics source.

Figure 7: The BigDataGrapes Twitter

BigDataGrapes' Twitter in numbers (Source: Twitter Statistics)	Reporting Period 01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020
Tweets	135
Followers	348
Likes	721
Retweets	239
Retweeted Tweets	100/135
Tweets impressions	276.500

Table 9: BigDataGrapes Twitter statistics [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

Analysing the above-mentioned data, we can extract some useful conclusions about our presence in Twitter. **74%** of our tweets are being retweeted and the total amount of **retweets** were **239** by a number of **348 engaged followers**. Our tweets, retweets and digital-network gave to our project a reach of **276.500 views**, indicating the relevance of the BigDataGrapes project aim. All the project's activity on Twitter is presented in detail, in Annex C.

3.2.2 YOUTUBE

YouTube channel was highly regarded as a very effective dissemination channel for video content. The BigDataGrapes YouTube account (<https://bit.ly/2x3ijLL>) was created in January 2019. At our YouTube channel, stakeholders had the chance to view recordings of the project webinars, a series of informative and education videos and other project promotional videos. Until the end of the project, in the YouTube channel **14 videos** were uploaded. The videos outlined the aims, objectives and challenges of the BigDataGrapes project to our targeted audience. All videos produced and published in the YouTube channel are divided in 3 different categories which are mentioned in the Annex C.

A series of videos explaining food safety predictions

BigDataGrapes through a short video series, eight (8) in total, aimed to end the existing struggle of applying predictive analytics in the food supply sector, especially in terms of food safety challenges. Through these series, our project aimed to fulfil its primary promise: to help European companies in the vine, wine, natural cosmetics and other related food sectors to use, exploit and benefit from big data tools, by supporting business decisions, while providing decision-making processes and support, resulting from the real-time and transversal analysis of relevant and heterogeneous data sources.

Giannis Stoitsis, CTO and partner at Agroknow (Coordinator partner of the BigDataGrapes project), was the main speaker in all of them and in every video, he focused on the following challenges:

- How to choose the right problem when talking about predictions?
- Which data subsets should be used for the specific problem?
- How can the appropriate algorithm be found and parameterized?
- How can it be measured if a prediction algorithm is working properly?
- Which questions need to be answered, when assessing operations?

Finally, two case studies were presented in the last episode, regarding the chocolate and the dairy industry.

Webinars videos

Three (3) of the webinars, which were organised by the project partners, have been uploaded in our channel on YouTube. In the first video, GEOCLEDIAN, presented its global Near-Realtime Field Monitoring service "Ag|knowledge" and how to use it. It was presented what kind of data and analytics are offered and how to access them and the usage of the API was explained. Also, available tools were presented such as GEOCLEDIAN's EO web analytics tool "Analyst's dashboard", QGIS plugin and available web visualization components. Ag|knowledge is part of the project's Big Data ecosystem and is used in the project to retrieve satellite data analytics for vineyards in several European countries. These data sets are connected in the project with all kinds of other data sources from the project partners, like yield, grape quality, or wine taste data. Prediction models and Precision Farming Practices were developed based on these data sets.

The other two (2) videos uploaded in our channel, came from a webinar and a special tech panel organized by Agroknow and by Agroknow and KU Leuven respectively. The main topics in these two webinars were:

- The provision of insights into the business challenges for the food industry as well as the scientific challenges for UX researchers when talking about predictive analytics, and how to overcome them; and
- The usage of predictive analytics for the food supply chain as well as the most effective way of applying them in business terms.

Videos with educational content

This category (playlist) was created in order to provide the practical perspective of the BigDataGrapes project. On 2019, a specific educational video has been uploaded in our channel, from our partner AUA at Kontogiannis Estate, showing the way that we collected some of our needed data for the “Table and Wine Grapes” Pilot. On the last year two (2) more videos were published for the needs of the “Food Protection” Pilot and their content was targeting on the importance of the Predictive Analytics in the food supply chain. Further to these videos, we foresee that a variety of videos will continue to be produced after the completion of the project, providing content of high-practical methods in data mining and collecting.

Figure 8: The BigDataGrapes YouTube channel

The total views on our videos on YouTube were **510**. It is important to mention that in the first two years of the project, the BigDataGrapes YouTube channel had only **26 views**.

3.2.3 SLIDESHARE

The BigDataGrapes SlideShare account (<https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes>) was created in June 2018, delivering and making available presentations used for scientific and public appearances. It was intended to give the viewer a deeper insight into the project and individual aspects of it. At this media channel, stakeholders will have the chance to check all the presentations of BigDataGrapes partners that have been presented in Conferences, Workshops, Meetups, Networking sessions and Trade Fairs. Until the end of the project the SlideShare account included **11 presentations**, which have received **3,105 views** and they have been downloaded **42 times** in total.

Below on the Table 10, we present all of the 11 generated presentations of our project, during the 3-year period. On this table, the title of the presentation, the year of release and the links that are available can be found.

Figure 9: The BigDataGrapes SlideShare

#	Title	Date	Available at
1	Big Data Grapes BDV Meetup Sofia	25 May 2018	https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/big-data-grapes-bdv-meetup-sofia
2	The BigDataGrapes Project - Changing the Grape Industry through Climate Change	5 March 2019	https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/the-bigdatagrapes-project-changing-the-grape-industry-through-climate-change
3	The BigDataGrapes vision enabling global disruption of the grapevine-powered industries	14 March 2019	https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/the-bigdatagrapes-vision-enabling-global-disruption-of-the-grapevinepowered-industries
4	BigDataGrapes_Table and Wine Grapes Pilot	14 March 2019	https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/bigdatagrapestable-and-wine-grapes-pilot
5	BigDataGrapes_Natural Cosmetics Pilot	14 March 2019	https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/bigdatagrapesnatural-cosmetics-pilot
6	GeoSpatial Aided Applications: farmer usage and administration data control, the Artea case	14 March 2019	https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/geospatial-aided-applications-farmer-usage-and-administration-data-control-the-arteacase
7	NetBeat: The first irrigation system with a brain	14 March 2019	https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/netbeat-the-first-irrigation-system-with-a-brain

8	Precision Viticulture at the Department of Agriculture Food and Environment	19 March 2019	https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/precision-viticulture-at-the-department-of-agriculture-food-and-environment
9	BigDataGrapes_Farm Management Pilot	19 March 2019	https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/bigdatagrapesfarm-management-pilot
10	BigDataGrapes_Wine Making Pilot	2 April 2019	https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/bigdatagrapeswine-making-pilot
11	Prediction algorithms for food data analytics and intelligence: towards a big data experimentation platform	26 March 2020	https://www.slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/big-data-grapespresentation-for-data-science-in-actionisess-2020-230920921

Table 10: BigDataGrapes SlideShare’s Presentations [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

In 2020, BigDataGrapes SlideShare got the most of the attention as it received **1.605 views** from the **3.105 in total** (51.69% of the view came last year based on the Figure 11). With this view it can be easily seen that **51.69%** of the views came the last year, and further on this, on Figure 10, we can see the traffic sources that are represented as follows: **90.35% referral** (redirection from other digital sources), **5.32% SlideShare**, **3.49 search** (coming from the Google search) and **0.83 direct**.

Figure 10: The BigDataGrapes traffic sources on SlideShare

Figure 11: BigDataGrapes SlideShare’s total views during the last year

BigDataGrapes’ partners, in their try to identify the strong footholds on the SlideShare platform, analyzed the highest and most trending presentations in order to keep up with the demand of the stakeholders. The top-3 presentations are listed in the following table:

#	Title	2020 views
1	Prediction algorithms for food data analytics and intelligence: towards a big data experimentation platform	301
2	NetBeat: The first irrigation system with a brain	287
3	Big Data Grapes BDV Meetup Sofia	1193

Table 11: BigDataGrapes’ Top-3 most viewed presentation on SlideShare

3.2.4 LINKEDIN

LinkedIn is a Professional Network through which BigDataGrapes Project addressed very specific target groups. Through it, we mainly targeted to create a sustainable network, by posting status of the project but also sharing project’s outcomes. For this reason, we created the BigDataGrapes LinkedIn account, during the first steps of our project, in January 2018 (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13574473/>).

Figure 12: The BigDataGrapes LinkedIn

BigDataGrapes during its lifetime addressed very specific messages, in total **35 posts**, to targeted groups, engaging a network of **173 followers**, creating a sustainable network in which the status of the project but also project outcomes could be shared. The posts were of high-content, collecting **314 Likes** and reached in June of 2020 (as it can be seen in the Figure 13) to magnetise the interest of almost **2.000 users** based on the LinkedIn Statistics.

BigDataGrapes' LinkedIn in numbers (Source: LinkedIn Statistics)	Reporting Period 01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020
Posts	35
Followers	173
Likes	314

Table 12: BigDataGrapes LinkedIn statistics [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

Figure 13: BigDataGrapes LinkedIn’s total views during the last year

3.2.5 DIGITAL CAMPAIGNS

Following the proposed methods of DoA for disseminating our project to other stakeholders and decision makers in the field of the project, we organized digital campaigns. The main aim of these campaigns was to put effort in order to drive engagement, conversions and traffic to our project. The majority of digital campaigns were about writing and sending email/ newsletters (we used the online tools Mailchimp, Hunter and SendGrid) but we also used LinkedIn by setting up promo posts for generating leads and we acquired premium LinkedIn accounts for selected project team members, which were used for exploring potential leads from selected BDG personas.

The newsletter approach was chosen since the database that we have is a very big one and the use of newsletters was the only economically feasible way to share our outcomes and activities with our relevant stakeholders all around the world in regular way. Moreover, the project exploited an electronic newsletter published by Big Data Value eCcosystem Project (BDVe, <https://www.big-data-value.eu/>). More precisely, on Big Data Value eCcosystem project newsletter (issued on September 2018), a BigDataGrapes announcement was released under the title “BigDataGrapes – Big Data To Enable Global Disruption Of The Grapevine-Powered Industries”.

In the following table are illustrated the project’s digital campaigns that have been implemented:

#	Type	URL	Partner
1	BigDataValue Newsletter	https://www.big-data-value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/PDF_Newsletter_February_2019_compressed.pdf	Agroknow
2	Agroknow Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/agroknow/foodsafetyintelligence1122020-7168273	Agroknow
3	Agroknow Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/agroknow/foodsafetyintelligence04122020-7156029	Agroknow
4	Agroknow Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/agroknow/foodsafetyintelligence27112020-7139817	Agroknow

5	Agroknow Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/agroknow/foodsafetyintelligence20112020	Agroknow
6	Agroknow Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/agroknow/foodsafetyintelligence12112020-7093049	Agroknow
7	Agroknow Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/agroknow/foodsafetyintelligence30102020-7032721	Agroknow
8	Agroknow Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/agroknow/foodsafetyintelligence22102020-5179993	Agroknow
9	Agroknow Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/agroknow/foodsafetyintelligence09102020-5172957	Agroknow
10	Agroknow Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/agroknow/foodsafetyintelligence09102020-5166313	Agroknow
11	Agroknow Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/agroknow/foodsafetyintelligence14082020-5158357	Agroknow

Table 13: Newsletter campaigns that have been implemented [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

Moreover, during the last year of the project (2020) we exploit LinkedIn’s ads (a total of 27 campaigns) in order to capitalize the work been done during the events and efficiently promote the BigDataGrapes results. Except from the general campaigns we run, we also plan and created targeted actions to capitalize on the GFSI event.

After the GFSI event, in which Agroknow participated, we run 4 dedicated campaigns targeting a total of 3.800 individuals (audience size). The targeting method we chose was by Participating Companies & Job Titles and the scope was to create new leads on the BigDataGrapes platform, emphasizing to the prediction component, but also promote the custom white papers developed after the event. Those campaigns resulted to 19 new leads and 97 website visits to the customized landing pages we developed for the white papers (for more details see Section 4.4).

The screenshot shows the targeting configuration for a LinkedIn ad campaign. The campaign is titled "GFSI-2020 Choco-FST-post" and is currently "Paused".

Job Titles (Current): Head Of Regulatory Affairs, Quality Control Lead, Director Of Quality Assurance, Assurance Specialist, Quality Assurance Lead, Head Of Quality Control, Quality Control Assistant, Quality Assurance Tester, Quality Management Specialist, Senior Quality Assurance Analyst, Quality Assurance Quality Control Inspector, Senior Quality Engineer, Quality Assurance Specialist, Supplier Quality Engineer, Vice President Of Quality, Quality Assurance Supervisor, Quality Consultant, Quality Assurance Manager, Senior Quality Assurance Specialist, Quality System Manager, Quality Assurance Engineer, Quality Assurance Team Lead, Quality Control Supervisor, Quality Control Engineer, Quality Specialist, Senior Quality Assurance Manager, Quality Assurance Analyst, Quality Assurance Officer, Vice President Quality Assurance, Director Quality Management, Quality Control Inspector, Lead Quality Assurance Analyst, Test Manager, Head Of Quality Assurance, Quality Control Chemist, Quality Assurance Quality Control Engineer, Assistant Quality Assurance Manager, Director Of Quality, Director Quality Engineering, Quality Analyst, Quality Control Coordinator, Director Of Manufacturing Operations, Quality Control Officer, Senior Quality Assurance Engineer

AND also have ANY of the following attributes:

Years of Experience: 6 years - 12+ years

AND also have ANY of the following attributes:

Company (Current Jobs): Mondelez International, Mars, The Hershey Company, Ferrero

Forecasted Results:

- Target audience size: 830+
- Segment breakdown:
 - Quality Assurance: 95%
 - Operations: 28%
 - Research: 20%
 - Information Technology: 9%
 - Sales: 8%
- 30-day spend: €170.00 - €820.00
- 30-day impressions: 2,900 - 14,000
- CTR: [unclear]

Figure 14: LinkedIn GFSI campaign example

Furthermore, we also run a total of 23 different, general, campaigns with an approximate 40.000 targeted audience per campaign. The targeting method we chose was by Company, Job Titles and Geographic location whereas the scope was to create new leads on the BigDataGrapes platform, promoting the official lunch of the prediction component. Those campaigns resulted to 707 new leads.

Predictions October 2020
Predictions Launch 14Oct2020 [↗](#) Paused Actions ▾

Step 1 **NEW**
Select Campaign Group

Step 2
Set up Campaign

- Objective selection
- Audience**
- Ad format
- Placement
- Budget & Schedule
- Conversion Tracking

Step 3
Set up Ads

- Conversation Ad

Step 4
Review & Launch

[Back to account](#)

Locations (Recent or Permanent) [↗](#)

Europe, Canada, United States

Exclude Locations (Recent or Permanent) [↗](#)

Pakistan, Bangladesh, Iraq

Your audience has their Profile Language set to English [↗](#)

Your audience size will vary depending on the language selected here. English may be selected as the default language, even in areas where a local language is available, to reach all users in the region.

Who is your target audience?

Include people who have **ANY** of the following attributes: [↗](#)

Company (Current Jobs)

Costco Wholesale UK, Dean Foods, AriZona Beverage Co., Woolworths Supermarkets, Puratos, pladis Global, Lion, Ahold Delhaize, Target Australia, Keurig Dr Pepper Inc., Lactalis Group, Unilever, TreeHouse Foods, Morrisons, Coca Cola Andina Brasil, BRAND'S Suntory, 蒙牛, Nestlé, Nestlé Waters, Lidl GB, Olam, PepsiCo, Alpura, Mondelēz International, Target, Mars, Walmart Canada, Chiquita, Whole Foods Market, Asahi Europe & International, Britannia Industries Limited, Bunge, Coca-Cola Amatil, Coca-Cola FEMSA, Costco Wholesale, H-E-B, The Kraft Heinz Company, Intermarché, JBS, Lidl in Germany, McCormick & Company, Ingredion Incorporated, Premier Foods, Red Bull, The Hershey Company, Tyson Foods, US Foods, Wegmans Food Markets, Coca-Cola Bottlers Japan Inc., Unilever Food Solutions, Dr. Oetker, pladis Global, Save-On-Foods, MONDELEZ UK LIMITED, Dairy Farmers of America, JACOBS DOUWE EGBERTS, Danone, KFC UK & Ireland, FrieslandCampina, Starbucks, JBS Australia Pty Limited, Carrefour

Forecasted Results [⊙](#) [⚙️](#)

Target audience size
40,000+

Segment breakdown [⊙](#)

Function ▾

Operations	63%
Quality Assurance	38%
Information Technology	5%
Research	5%
Support	4%

[Hide segments](#)

1-day 7-day **30-day**

30-day spend
€240.00 - €890.00

30-day message sends **1,200 - 4,400** [Key Result](#)

Forecasted results are directional estimates and do not guarantee performance. Note that some products are not yet incorporated in the results. [Learn more](#)

Is this information helpful? Yes No

Predictions October 2020
Predictions Launch 14Oct2020 [↗](#) Paused Actions ▾

Step 1 **NEW**
Select Campaign Group

Step 2
Set up Campaign

- Objective selection
- Audience**
- Ad format
- Placement
- Budget & Schedule
- Conversion Tracking

Step 3
Set up Ads

- Conversation Ad

Step 4
Review & Launch

[Back to account](#)

AND also have ANY of the following attributes: [↗](#)

Job Titles (Current)

Quality Control Lead, Quality Compliance Manager, Director Of Quality Assurance, Supplier Quality Assurance, Senior Director Quality, Director Quality Compliance, Quality Assurance Lead, Quality Assurance Engineering Manager, Head Of Quality Control, Director Global Quality, Director Of Manufacturing, Director Corporate Quality, Food Safety Manager, Supply Chain Supervisor, Senior Quality Assurance Associate, Quality Management Specialist, Senior Director Quality Assurance, Senior Quality Assurance Engineer Lead, Associate Director Quality Assurance, Supply Chain Management, Vice President Manufacturing Operations, Senior Quality Assurance Analyst, Quality Assurance Quality Control Inspector, Supply Manager, Vice President Operations Quality, Quality Assurance Compliance Manager, Quality Management Coordinator, Senior Quality Control Analyst, Quality Assurance Operations Manager, Lead Quality Assurance Tester, Supplier Manager, Director Quality Assurance Regulatory Affairs, Corporate Quality Assurance Manager, Senior Quality Assurance Auditor, Quality Management Representative, Senior Supply Chain Specialist, Director Quality Assurance Quality Control, Quality Assurance Regulatory Affairs Manager, Senior Executive Quality Assurance, Quality System Auditor, Quality Control Team Lead, Senior Quality Associate, Quality Assurance Specialist, Senior Quality Assurance Technician, Deputy Manager Quality Assurance, Quality Assurance Quality Control Coordinator, Quality Assurance Quality Control Supervisor, Quality Assurance Compliance Specialist, Group Quality Assurance Manager, Quality Assurance Supervisor, Senior Quality Assurance Officer, Regional Quality Assurance Manager, Quality Assurance Group Lead, Senior Quality Control Associate, Senior Quality Assurance Quality Control Engineer, Quality Assurance Manager, Food Safety Officer, Food Safety Specialist, Food Safety Supervisor, Senior Quality Assurance Specialist, Food Safety Auditor, Quality Control Analyst, Quality System Manager, Quality Assurance Engineer, Quality Assurance Team Lead, Supply Chain Planner, Quality Control Supervisor, Quality Specialist, Senior Quality Assurance Manager, Quality Control Technician, Quality Assurance Analyst, Manager

Forecasted Results [⊙](#) [⚙️](#)

Target audience size
40,000+

Segment breakdown [⊙](#)

Function ▾

Operations	63%
Quality Assurance	38%
Information Technology	5%
Research	5%
Support	4%

[Hide segments](#)

1-day 7-day **30-day**

30-day spend
€240.00 - €890.00

30-day message sends **1,200 - 4,400** [Key Result](#)

Forecasted results are directional estimates and do not guarantee performance. Note that some products are not yet incorporated in the results. [Learn more](#)

Is this information helpful? Yes No

Figure 15: LinkedIn general campaign example

3.3 CONTENT GENERATED

As mentioned before in “3.1 Project Website” section, along to the main online dissemination channel, was launched the project’s news blog (<http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/news>). The main purpose of this blog is to:

- inform the stakeholders about the latest news (e.g., new developments, project materials, announcements about events organized and impressions from past events, etc.)
- provide notes on scientific outcomes of the project, implementation results; as well as
- publish particularities of technical realizations.

In the following table, are demonstrated all the **67 articles/blog posts** that have been published in the project's news blog by the end of the project.

Blog Posts			
#	Date	Title	Link
1	17 May 2018	Presentation of the BigDataGrapes project at the Software approaches for managing Big Data workshop	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/64
2	22 June 2018	Presentation of BigDataGrapes at the Global Forum for Innovations in Agriculture 2018	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/79
3	8 Oct 2018	Presentation of the BigDataGrapes project at 12th ACM Conference on Recommender Systems	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/80
4	26 Oct 2018	From Cultivating Nature to Cultivating Data: Semantic Technology and Viticulture	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/55
5	5 Nov 2018	Presentation of the BigDataGrapes project at the 15th Conference of Agricultural Economy of Greece	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/58
6	15 Nov 2018	Presentation of the BigDataGrapes project at the 2nd Athens Innovation Festival (AIF) 2018	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/56
7	22 Nov 2018	Presentation of BigDataGrapes at the 11th Data Science Leuven Meetup	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/81
8	3 Dec 2018	Presentation of BigDataGrapes project at CNR-DIITET Department Conference - 'Informatica' Strategic Area	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/78
9	19 Dec 2018	Presentation of BigDataGrapes at the 12th Recommender Systems Netherlands (RecSysNL) meetup	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/82
10	20 Dec 2018	BigDataGrapes project successfully released its first Annual Report	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/59

11	24 Dec 2018	Publication of a portion of the technology used at the BigDataGrapes project	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/60
12	10 Jan 2019	Presentation of BigDataGrapes at the User-Centred Social Media (UCSM) series	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/83
13	15 Jan 2019	Presentation of the BigDataGrapes project at the SFARM workshop	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/61
14	4 Feb 2019	Presentation of the BigDataGrapes project at Kathimerini newspaper	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/66
15	12 Feb 2019	Presentation of BigDataGrapes project at Medium online publishing platform	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/85
16	15 Feb 2019	Presentation of the BigDataGrapes project at Connecting lives: The Digital Single Market – achievements and challenges event	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/67
17	19 Feb 2019	Organization of the BigDataGrapes workshop on “Big Data for the Grapevine Industries”	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/68
18	22 Feb 2019	Presentation of BigDataGrapes project in an article entitled "How big data helps winemakers to produce better wine".	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/86
19	2 May 2019	Presentation of the BigDataGrapes project at Seeds & Chips event 2019	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/71
20	10 May 2019	Geocledian participation at Seeds & Chips event 2019	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/73
21	13 May 2019	Presentation of BigDataGrapes at TUTTOFOOD 2019	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/84
22	13 May 2019	Presentation of the BigDataGrapes project at ESA Living Planet Symposium 2019	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/72
23	20 May 2019	Presentation of the BigDataGrapes poster at ESA Living Planet Symposium 2019	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/74
24	28 May 2019	BigDataGrapes Project Webinar on Field Monitoring	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/75
25	31 May 2019	Webinar on Field Monitoring with Geocledian’s Ag knowledge API & Tools in the context of BigDataGrapes project	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/76

26	31 May 2019	AUA 2019 data collection	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/77
27	27 June 2019	AUA 2019 drones data collection	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/87
28	11 Oct 2019	Presentation of the BigDataGrapes project at European Big Data Value Forum 2019	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/99
29	17 Oct 2019	Agroknow participation at European Big Data Value Forum 2019	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/100
30	25 Oct 2019	Presentation of the BigDataGrapes project at the China International Food Safety & Quality (CIFSQ) Conference	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/101
31	1 Nov 2019	Food Protection Pilot presentation at 13th China International Food Safety & Quality (CIFSQ) Conference	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/102
32	10 Nov 2019	Visually driven decision support tools for viticulture	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/104
33	12 Nov 2019	Table and wine grape: Vineyard assessment to vineyard management	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/103
34	20 Dec 2019	Counting grapevine leaves in the BigDataGrapes project	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/105
35	14 Jan 2020	Data-empowering the Food Safety Sector	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/121
36	16 Feb 2020	The art and science of food safety predictions	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/122
37	8 Mar 2020	Beyond data collection: how data orchestration is vital to ensure food safety	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/123
38	11 Apr 2020	Moving from reaction to prediction through emerging data technologies	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/124
39	15 May 2020	Can we predict which vineyard will supply the best quality leaves for natural cosmetics production?	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/106
40	22 May 2020	AI applications for wine and vine	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/107
41	24 May 2020	Getting a glimpse of the candy industry's food safety future	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/125

42	1 Jun 2020	Finding answers to critical business questions through ABACO Farmer	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/109
43	10 Jun 2020	Big Data Platform series: Setting up the BigDataGrapes platform	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/110
44	12 Jun 2020	Table and Wine Grapes Pilot: Grapevine Responses to Terroir	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/111
45	16 Jun 2020	Can we see from space if a vineyard needs water?	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/112
46	26 Jun 2020	What's new in FOODAKAI?	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/126
47	30 Jun 2020	Connecting data in an intelligent way: a semantic data model developed in BigDataGrapes project	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/113
48	11 Sep 2020	A journey from vine to wine in pictures	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/114
49	5 Oct 2020	2020 Future of Food 10X10 CEO Interview Series: Challenges and opportunities of the food industry	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/150
50	14 Oct 2020	Can we really prevent food fraud and safety incidents from happening?	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/115
51	20 Oct 2020	What's new in FOODAKAI: Predictions Dashboard Beta Version	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/127
52	9 Nov 2020	BigDataGrapes 6th Project Meeting (4-5 November 2020)	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/116
53	8 Dec 2020	A series of videos explaining food safety predictions for Busy People - Intro	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/119
54	22 Dec 2020	Episode 1: The food risk prevention question to drive effective predictive analytics	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/120
55	5 Jan 2021	Virtual Panel on "Predictive Analytics for the Food Supply Chain"	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/136
56	8 Jan 2021	Episode 2: How to select the right data for effective predictive analytics	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/137
57	21 Jan 2021	Episode 3: How to select the right food risk prediction algorithm?	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/138

58	21 Jan 2021	Conclusions from the virtual panel discussion on "Predictive Analytics"	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/140
59	21 Jan 2021	Webinar on "Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention"	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/141
60	27 Jan 2021	Episode 4: Focus on the right prediction metrics	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/142
61	28 Jan 2021	Episode 5: How to integrate predictions in your work flows	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/143
62	29 Jan 2021	Episode 6: How to apply lessons learned about a specific industry – the Chocolate Industry	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/144
63	29 Jan 2021	Online workshop on Prediction Analytics	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/145
64	29 Jan 2021	Webinar on "Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention"	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/146
65	31 Jan 2021	Episode 7 - How can we predict a food recall before it happens?	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/147
66	31 Jan 2021	Artificial Intelligence & Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention: A discussion paper	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/148
67	31 Jan 2021	Food Fraud: A Global Threat With Public Health and Economic Consequences	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/149

Table 14: The 67 articles/blog posts that have been published [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

In the last year of the project, in **33 posts** total were published in the BigDataGrapes website, which was the record of posts during the project's lifetime. On the pie chart, we can see better the increasing pace of the annual posts, where **49,25%** of the entire number of them happened during the last and most crucial period of our project. As we aforesaid, dissemination should be effective and envisioned to reach close and distinct stakeholder groups. Align with this, the 3rd and last year was the highlight-year of the website, where articles of broad spectrum were uploaded, creating an uninterrupted and continuous contact with the key-stakeholders of the project, ensuring the active participation and information in regard to BigDataGrapes overall and take-away outcomes.

Figure 16: BigDataGrapes Annual Posts (%)

3.4 CONTACT LISTS CREATED

Our goal was to select and record all top contacts, within the targeted stakeholders' segments, that will help us increase the number of visitors to the project's social media. These contacts include existing but also potential researchers of interest, including agri-food scientists and technology partners who influence each stakeholder segment, decision makers or other policy makers, etc.

The first step we took is to record and filter all the contacts we have in the 5 major stakeholders segments we are currently looking at: (1) European funding & projects in our area, (2) agribusiness, seed & fertilizer companies, (3) the International agricultural scientific community, (4) the people involved in International food safety networks, and (5) the people involved in agri-food sector in North American stakeholders. The next step was to filter and select from these lists the top people with whom we need to build a perfect relationship.

In the first list, namely European funding & projects in our area, we had by M36 138 listed stakeholders. In this list are included coordinators of important projects (see Annex B) & their key partners, EU community employees & partners at the Units of interest, participants in our EU events (eg eROSA stakeholder workshops), politicians & government officials in the EU, etc.

In the second list, agribusiness, seed & fertilizer companies, we managed to include 58 registered stakeholders. This list consists of the contacts that will impact those who have budgets within agribusiness companies to become BigDataGrapes subscribers and collaborate with us in future proposals. Particularly includes, the existing contacts & partners within agrochemical companies, new potential contacts that can allocate money in

digital science in the agrochemical companies, senior decision makers who can influence them, their critical suppliers, analysts, science forums & expert groups discussing related issues, etc.

The third list, the International agricultural scientific community consists of 19 registries. This list is consisted by existing contacts within projects like CGIAR, new potential contacts that can allocate money for digital and open science in CRPs, centers etc, senior decision makers in CRPs & centers that can influence them, their critical suppliers, communications & marketing people at CGIAR, communities of practice & expert groups discussing related issues, etc. We aim these contacts to impact those within international agricultural research companies to become BigDataGrapes subscribers and economically support and participate in future proposals.

The fourth list, people involved in International food safety networks, consists of **792 registries** from the GFSI & food safety networks. These stakeholders are the ones that will influence those who have budgets within food companies, scientists, and associations such as GMA to become aware of BigDataGrapes. These were contacts & partners within the GFSI networks, leading influential food safety scientists, critical technology partners, food safety news sites, communities of practice & expert groups discussing related issues, etc.

The last list, North American stakeholders, regards people in research institutes in USA that consists of 11 people. The list includes existing contacts & partners within Canada, new potential contacts that can allocate money for digital and open science in the country, critical technology partners, communications & marketing people, communities of practice & expert groups discussing related issues, etc.

In total, **1.018 stakeholders** have been included in project's dissemination list and got familiar with BigDataGrapes project objectives and outcomes.

*Based on the new EU regulation on personal data, BigDataGrapes project is committed that is in full compliance and processes stakeholders' personal data in accordance with all the EU General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation 2016/679) requirements.

3.5 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, there are several digital and social media platforms where we could promote BigDataGrapes results. As a consortium we choose the most effective and suitable platforms, in order to deliver our tailor, for the key-stakeholders, messages. To achieve our goal, we delivered high-quality posts, videos, blogs, webinars, presentations, etc. and influencing-centric documentation to our major stakeholders.

Through social media, we seek to build strong relationships with the key-stakeholders, engaging them to participate actively during the 3-years duration of our project. The maximum utilization of the digital channels was deemed necessary, after the sudden and unexpected outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, where tailored dissemination plans were the key to a timely and strategic response to these quickly changing developments. At the beginning of the project, we emphasized on the promotion of BigDataGrapes project and for this reason we had the highest activity on Twitter (in comparison with the other years), in which **48** well-crafted Tweets collected **441 Likes** and **116 Retweets**. On the second year, driven by the need to upgrade our dissemination activities, with the pressure from the COVID-19, we kept our dynamic exitance in Twitter but further to this, we

uploaded in form of presentation, generated knowledge from the pilots and we make it available for everybody through the SlideShare platform. Extra to this, we kept updating our official website with posts, ongoing and future webinars keeping it vivid the interest of our target groups.

Finally, the third and last year of the project, was the save active but with the highest number of dissemination material releases. During that period, we organized different-kind activities such as posts, webinars, series of videos and many others. As it can be seen in the figure below, **43.3%** of the completed website posts got uploaded spreading the BigDataGrapes results. Moreover, the third year accomplished the biggest volume of LinkedIn posts (**79%** of the total posts on LinkedIn), analyzing the results of the pilots and promoting solutions to relevant key-groups. Finally, by the end of the project, a miniseries of 8 videos was uploaded in YouTube, providing to companies all the needed-knowledge for applying artificial intelligence technologies and predictive analytics in the food sector, especially in terms of food safety challenges.

Figure 17: BigDataGrapes Digital Dissemination channels and activities [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

Therefore, the reporting will be based on the measurable numbers and the right conclusions will be drawn from those numbers.

4. EVENTS ORGANISED /ATTENDED

What was previously called as the “offline” dissemination activities of the BigDataGrapes project, include (a) the organisation of workshops in collaboration with international stakeholders and other EU-funded initiatives towards sharing best practices on aspects related to big data management, processing/analytics and visualization related to the BigDataGrapes pilots, (b) participation to small-scale events (e.g. workshops organized in partners’ premises) and large-scale events, like international conferences, workshop, policy events etc, and (c) publishing papers in conference proceedings, international journals and book chapters.

Due to the Covid-19 outbreak the majority of the events were cancelled or transformed to digital events. Hence, we are including all the events organised and attended, regardless if they were carried out with physical or virtual presence.

4.1 EVENTS ORGANIZED

During the project lifetime, BigDataGrapes consortium organised a series of events that truly influence, inspire, engage and connect with the intended target audience (whether they are live or online events) with main goals:

- The participation of all industries related to the project (Research, Food Industry, Policy Makers, etc.);
- The dissemination of information to organisations and companies active in two key industries powered by grapevines: the wine industry and the natural cosmetics one and to parties interested in the project activities and progress made;
- To engage members of an extended network related to agriculture and food, which are interested in activities and collaborations;
- To inform about the ways the big data is going to completely redefine industries, even the very traditional sectors like agriculture, food and beauty.

4.1.1 WORKSHOPS

During the lifespan of the BigDataGrapes project, the consortium members organized six (6) workshops, with scientific oriented content. To reach a broad but also specialised group of participants, the aim was to couple the workshops to existing and well-known big conferences, dealing with BigDataGrapes relevant issues (e.g., Living Planet Symposium). The workshops provided one (1) or two (2) days presentations and promoted the BigDataGrapes’ concept and results. Our goal through the organizations of this type of workshops was to reach a large community of interested stakeholders and to build awareness about the project, its benefits and outcomes.

Workshops took place in different countries and continents (i.e., Greece, Italy and Canada) in order to reach a wider range of participants and participants and depending on the capacity of the local hosts, we explored streaming these workshops online as well as recording parts of the workshops in video to upload in the BigDataGrapes YouTube channel to create additional outreach.

Moreover, to lure even more stakeholders, we invited targeted organisations which provided extra quality and hands-on expertise to the workshops. On the table below we provide more information about the workshops organised during the 3 years of the BigDataGrapes project.

#	Event Name	Event URL	Partners Participated	Location Dates	Audience	Participants
1	12th ACM Conference on Recommender Systems (RecSys)	https://intrs18.wordpress.com/invited-talk/	KULeuven	Canada 7/10/2018	Research	40
2	SFARM workshop	http://www.sfarm-project.eu/	AUA	Greece 14/1/2019	Research, Industry and Policy Makers	60
3	Workshop on “Big Data for the Grapevine Industries”	http://www.bigdatagrafes.eu/node/68	CNR, Agroknow, AUA, INRA, Abaco, SYMBEEOIS	Italy 8/4/2019	Research, Industry	50
4	OchraVineControl workshop	https://www2.aua.gr/el/news-events/ekdiloseis/imerida-me-titlo-integrated-and-innovative-precision-agriculture-strategies	AUA	Greece 16/9/2019	Research, Industry and Policy Makers	40
5	Living Planet Symposium 2019	https://lps19.esa.int/NikalaWebsitePortal/living-planet-symposium-2019/lps19	GEOCLEDIAN	Italy 17/8/2019	Research, Industry and Policy Makers	>3.000
6	Focused workshop with Syngenta Data Team on exploring synergies on using the BigDataGrapes predictions	On Syngenta Premises (Basel, Switzerland)	Agroknow	Switzerland 29/1/2020	Industry	15

Table 15: Organisation of special workshops in scientific conferences [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

One of the major workshops organized by the project was a one-day workshop on how ICT and big data science development can potentially provide innovative and more effective ways to support the grapevine industry dealing with extremely large and heterogeneous data flows. The workshop was organized by **the BigDataGrapes project consortium** in collaboration with the **Department of Agriculture, Food and Environment of the University of Pisa** on 8 March 2019 in Pisa, Italy. The aim of the workshop was to bring together different stakeholders from the grapevine industry, so as to present the project vision and enhance the dialogue regarding the challenges that are being faced within the value chain of these industry and how big data technologies can support them. The workshop was attended by 50 stakeholders and the agenda was built upon two sessions: 1) The BigDataGrapes Pilots, where the evolution of the pilots was presented and 2) Vine and Wine innovative Research and Teaching, where new technologies and the theoretical background were introduced to the participant researchers.

4.2 WEBINARS

An important part of our dissemination and marketing achievements, were the organization of six (6) (as they are depicted in the table below) highly targeted webinars within the 3 years of BigDataGrapes life, aligning them with its goals:

(i) to gain unique access to key stakeholders that form the BigDataGrapes ecosystem; and
(ii) to disseminate the project results to external stakeholders from the targeted project communities.
In these events, the project partners demonstrated the project outcomes to meet the needs and address barriers that multiple stakeholders face in achieving sustainability through the use of the big data that exist. Through these webinars we tried to build a deeper relationship with specialised target groups, and more with the research-oriented stakeholders, who participated, involved and engaged actively in the project evolution. The webinars were advertised through our channels, especially via the social media accounts of the project.

#	Event Name	Partners	Date(s)	Audience	Participants
1	Webinar on Field Monitoring in the context of BigDataGrapes project	Geocledian, SIRMA AI	29/5/2019	Research, Industry and Policy Makers, Software Engineers, Consulting	65
2	Data products – The scalable and reliable approach to data monetization	Agroknow	24/9/2020	Research, Agrologistics, AgriTech, Consultin, ICT	30
3	The BigDataGrapes Food Protection Pilot - Risk assessment and recall prediction	Agroknow, AUA, INRA, Abaco, SYMBEEOIS	09/10/2020	Research, Academic, Industry and Policy Makers	8
4	Big Data to empower the grapewines industries digital transformation	ABACO, CNR	18/12/2020	Research, Food Industry, Governmental Agencies	27
5	Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention: Towards visually appealing & highly interactive predictions	Agroknow, KU LEUVEN	22/1/2021	Education, AgriTech Governmental Agencies, Software Engineers, E-commerce	37
6	Big Data to empower the grapevine industries digital transformation	CNR, ABACO	14/1/2021	Research, Governmental Agencies, Industry, Food and Beverage Industry	27

Table 16: Organisation of webinars for scientists [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

Some of the most significant organized webinars of these 3 years are presented as follows:

Field Monitoring with Geocledian’s Ag|knowledge API & Tools

The 1st webinar was delivered on 29th of May 2019. Sixty-five (65) people registered and attended this webinar. The webinar was entitled “*Field Monitoring with Geocledian’s Ag|knowledge API & Tools*” and it was organized by **GEOCLEDIAN**. The attendants consist of researchers from different fields, policy makers, consultants and computer scientists. During the webinar GEOCLEDIAN, presented its global Near-Realtime Field Monitoring service “Ag|knowledge” (part of the project’s software stack and is used in the project to retrieve satellite data analytics for vineyards in several European countries) and how to use it. In particular, our partner presented what kind of data and analytics they offer and how to access them and explain the usage of our API.

Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention: Towards visually appealing & highly interactive predictions

The 5th webinar was organised on the 22nd of January of 2021. Thirty-seven (37) people registered and attended this webinar. The webinar was entitled “*Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention: Towards visually appealing & highly interactive predictions*” and it was co-organized by **KU Leuven and Agroknow**. The attendants came from different sectors such as education (universities and institutions), AgriTech, e-commerce, Consulting, Engineering and from governmental agencies. Also, large companies such as **Nestle, Unilever, DODONI** and many more were among the participants of this webinar validating the importance of the BigDataGrapes’ results to other relevant sectors. Main topics discussed during that day were: (i) From a business question to a risk

dashboard: the food safety intelligence equation; (ii) Designing an appealing, interactive & trustful prediction dashboard: visualization components & technologies; and (iii) A Food Risk Prediction Dashboard example and how it works. A total of 327 participants attended the webinars.

Big Data to empower the grapevine industries digital transformation (Original Title in Italian: Industria e Agricoltura 4.0. Transizione verso il digitale ed intelligenza artificiale)

On December 18th, ABACO and ISTI-CNR organized a webinar for presenting to Italian stakeholders some of the results achieved by the consortium of BigDataGrapes. The online meeting was attended by 27 people from both academia and wine making industries. After a short introduction about the project and its aims, CNR presented the challenges in agriculture for Machine Learning & Artificial Intelligence with an emphasis on the prediction tasks identified and addressed in BigDataGrapes. Then, ABACO introduced the BigDataGrapes farm management pilot and showcased the new developments introduced in the ABACO Farmer platform with the novel dashboards dedicated to the control of water stress in the field and to emergency irrigation.

The discussion after the technical presentations was stimulated by the participation of managers from the “Casato prime Donne” and “Il Palazzo” wineries who told about their positive experience with precision farming tools provided by ABACO and BigDataGrapes.

Figure 18: Banner for the event: “Big Data to empower the grapevine industries digital transformation”

Finally, in order to create additional outreach and increase the effectiveness of the dissemination actions some of the webinars were recorded and uploaded in the YouTube channel of the project, enhancing the online presence of the BigDataGrapes project.

4.3 OPEN DAYS

In addition to the previous mentioned workshops and webinars, we had in our plan to organise open days in the partners premises and invite anyone interested to find out about BigDataGrapes results and try produced tools/services. These activities were planned for the third year of the project’s implementation (as part of the

pilots evaluation activities) but due to the fact that we were not allowed to organise them physically (Covid-19) the majority of them (6/10) were virtual. Hence, we manage to attract 84 participants, with the majority of them being industrial actors. In the following table we present the full list of the open day events organised.

#	Event Name	Partners	Event Type	Date(s)	Audience	Participants
1	Experimental Farm on Viticulture for the "New Agriculture for a New Generation"	AUA	Workshop	5-6-7/2/2020	Research, Governmental Agencies, Industry	25
2	Workshop during the Evaluation Session of the wine making pilot	INRA	Workshop	8/7/2020	Research, Industry	6
3	Workshop during the Evaluation Session of the wine making pilot	INRA	Workshop	9/7/2020	Research, Industry	8
4	"New technologies for Sustainable Farming" for the "New Agriculture for a New Generation"	AUA	Workshop	8/8/2020	Research, Industry and Policy Makers	12
5	"New technologies for Sustainable Farming" for the "New Agriculture for a New Generation"	AUA	Workshop	9/8/2020	Research, Industry and Policy Makers	14
6	Workshop during the Evaluation Session of table and wine grapes pilot	AUA	Workshop	26/8/2020	Research, Industry and Policy Makers	3
7	Networking session presenting the prediction dashboard of the Food Protection Pilot	Agroknow	Networking session	4/9/020	Industry	5
8	Networking session presenting the prediction dashboard of the Food Protection Pilot	Agroknow	Networking session	10/9/020	Industry	3
9	Networking session presenting the prediction dashboard of the Food Protection Pilot	Agroknow	Networking session	25/9/2020	Industry	5
10	Networking session presenting the prediction dashboard of the Food Protection Pilot	Agroknow	Networking session	18/11/2020	Industry	3

Table 17: Organisation of open days [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

4.4 EVENTS ATTENDED

BigDataGrapes’ partners attended various dissemination events like trainings (i.e., summer schools and institutes), specialized forums, standardization and global conferences. Through these events, we reached a great number of stakeholders (based on partners’ estimations we calculate that we have reached more than 600.000 different people in the events we attended).

The BigDataGrapes project was promoted in **9 European countries** (i.e., Spain, Italy, Greece, Netherlands, United Kingdom, Bulgaria, Belgium, Finland and Germany) and in **3 non-EU countries** (i.e., USA, Canada and China)

targeting representatives from the relevant research communities and stakeholders from each country. In total, we participated in **18 events** in order to disseminate BigDataGrapes' outcomes, and especially to:

- **6** training events of young scientists (e.g., summer schools, summer institutes);
- **8** events targeted to special interest groups in specialised forums, standardisation groups, global networks;
- **4** events at AgriTech commercial exhibitions and trade fairs.

Training events of young scientists

One of the BigDataGrapes goals was to encourage wide adoption of the outcomes from the scientific and research communities, especially the young scientists who will be the future leaders of the IT (big data) and viticulture (wine) scientific sectors. Aligning with this aim, our consortium partners attended in different events (i.e., Master courses, Conferences, Training and Hackathons) with prior goal to inform, with the most effective way, the students. Brochures, presentations and other promotion material crafted, tailor-designed for the different circumstances of the several actions, influencing approximately 400 current and future researchers. As it can be seen in the Table 20, we participated in 6 events, in 5 different European countries.

The most significant events were:

- **“The 12th European Summer School in Information Retrieval”** – The ESSIR 2019 (European Summer School in Information Retrieval) was 5-day event (15-19 July, 2019) that offered a high-quality teaching on Information Retrieval (IR) and related research topics. A new edition of the Symposium on Future Directions in Information Access (FDIA) was also held at ESSIR 2019, providing a forum for early researchers to present their research in a friendly environment, whilst among senior researchers. There, CNR presented the modern research challenges and methods in information retrieval, stimulated the scientific research and cross-sectoral collaboration of agricultural fields with the field of ICT by showcasing primary results from the 5 pilots.
- **“CASA Doctoral Summer School for Advanced Spatial Modelling 2019”** – The purpose of SS-ASM19 was threefold: *firstly*, to warm participants up to key quantitative methods and introduce them to core spatial modelling methods; *secondly*, apply these methods in the context of National Industrial Strategy - and in doing so, think about new governmental geography products and what future cities could look like; *finally*, foster collaborations opportunities between PhD students from different institutions through the hackathon and subsequent conference attendance award. In this summer camp, KU Leuven participated showing techniques for building algorithms targeted in collecting the data needed for the geographical analysis.
- **“New technologies for Sustainable Farming for the New Agriculture for a New Generation”** – The training program offered training in greenhouse and hydroponics systems, controlled environment agriculture, precision farming, application of smart farming techniques and technologies to 360 young people. The training program was designed and implemented by the AUA, under the scientific guidance of a host of experienced university professors.
- The objective of the program is to give young generation (including farmers) the opportunity to acquire or improve/update already available knowledge and skills in new smart farming technologies that can be applied in the primary agricultural production and lead to a more sustainable use of external inputs, thus leading to a smart crop production with reduced environmental footprint using hi-tech and smart technologies. There, AUA implemented also the new scientific and practical knowledge that was

extracted by the BigDataGrapes pilots, showcasing the possibilities that was provided by the usage of the big data and drones.

Events with special interest groups

In our effort to create engagement around the project’s outcomes and validate them, our participation in events with special interest groups (e.g., Big Data, Food Safety, etc.) deemed necessary. The purpose through this type of events is to:

- Exchange knowledge and know-how;
- Reach a large number of potential users;
- Present the results of our activities.

To enhance our effort, BigDataGrapes consortium attended eight (8) events (as they are listed on the Table 20) organized in several countries and different continents (e.g., Helsinki-Finland, Beijing-China, Seattle-USA, etc.) These events were equal distributed during the three-year duration of the project, so we could provide and showcase its evolution. The most characteristic events of this category were:

“The European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF)”

From 14th until 16th of October 2019, Agroknow presented BigDataGrapes project at European Big Data Value Forum 2019 (EBDVF2019 in Helsinki, Finland) - The main event of the European Big Data and Data-Driven Artificial Intelligence (AI) Research and Innovation community. The organising committee of this event included, in addition to BDVA, the EC and VTT, multiple Finnish industrial, Innovation and research players, as well as international companies. During all three days, Agroknow representatives had a booth and answered to all requested questions regarding the project and distributed special brochures on BigDataGrapes project scope.

Figure 19: Pictures from the European Big Data Value Forum

Prior to this event, the European Big Data Value community has been gathered on the 16th of May in Sofia, Bulgaria. SAI represented BigDataGrapes project on the event organised by the Big Data Value PPP, aiming to strength the collaborations among community members and increase the visibility and awareness about Big Data in East Europe, and Bulgaria in particular.

“Chinese Food Quality and Safety Conference”

From 30th to 31st of October 2019, Agroknow (Food Protection Pilot Leader) presented BigDataGrapes project at **13th China International Food Safety & Quality Conference (CIFSQ2019)** in Beijing, China) - The largest event of its kind in the Asia Pacific region addressing the key issues for strengthening food protection. From testing to tracing to inspection and certification. Our project's fifth pilot, Food Protection, was presented during the two days event by Agroknow's representatives.

Figure 20: Presentation sample from the Chinese Food Quality and Safety Conference

In the event we also had a booth, answering questions related to BigDataGrapes project. We have to mention also that the conference leadership was consisted of organization and policy bodies such as European Commission, U.S. FDA, WHO, FAO, etc.

Figure 21: Our Booth at the Chinese Food Quality and Safety Conference

Figure 22: Presenting the Prediction Dashboard at the Chinese Food Quality and Safety Conference

“Global Food Safety Initiative (GFSI)”

From 25th to 28th of February 2020, Agroknow presented BigDataGrapes project at Global Food Safety Initiative – **GFSI 2020 Conference (Seattle, USA)**. Agroknow’s presentation, to the attendees of the GFSI Conference 2020 (1.015 final participants), focused on the ways which Big Data and Artificial Intelligence can be used to achieve greater visibility across the supply chain and can predict food risks. Moreover, the Agroknow booth that was set up (as it is depicted on the Figure 24) magnetised 22 representatives from several companies.

Based on the principals of inbound sales methodology we classify our “visitors” into two categories, the MQL and SQL. A **Marketing Qualified Lead (MQL)** is a prospect that we deem more likely to eventually turn into a sale than other leads, but isn’t quite ready to buy yet. These leads require additional marketing assistance before they’re ready to receive a sales call. From the other side, a **Sales Qualified Lead (SQL)** is a prospective customer that has progressed past the engagement stage, has been thoroughly analyzed by both marketing and sales, and has been deemed ready for the next stage in the sales process - a direct sales push. These leads have displayed intent to buy, and have met lead qualification criteria determining that they’re a right fit for the BigDataGrapes platform and related services.

Figure 23: The inbound sales methodology

More information for the companies that reached our booth as well as their classification is presented in the table below:

Nr	Companies	Classification
1	BRF SA	MQL
2	COSTCO CANADA	MQL
3	DAYMON	MQL
4	CHAMPION PETFOOD	MQL
5	LOBLAW COMP.	MQL
6	DANONE	MQL
7	DANONE	MQL
8	ARLA FOODS AMBA	MQL
9	PEPSICO	MQL
10	SIGMA ALIMENTOS	MQL
11	WALMART	SQL
12	NESTLE	SQL

13	FRIESLAND	SQL
14	MARS INCORPORATED	SQL
15	ALPURA	SQL
16	RETAIL BUSINESS SERVICES / Ahold	SQL
17	WHOLEFOODS	SQL
18	MCCAIN	SQL
19	DANONE	SQL
20	SIGMA ALIMENTOS	SQL
21	MONDELEZ	SQL
22	BIMBO BAKERY	SQL

Table 18: Companies visited Agroknow’s Booth in GFSI 2020 and their classification

Figure 24: Agroknow’s representation in the GFSI 2020

Figure 25: Presentation sample for the GFSI 2020 Conference (Seattle,USA)

For the companies that we successfully attracted them to Agroknow’s Booth, we created a number of custom white papers with prediction data, in order to increase their interest and achieve even bigger impact of our project. In this conference, we managed to spread the benefits of our project to a wide range of food sectors, by the implementation of our innovative culture-targeted to bring sustainable outcomes through the usage of big data in the food supply chain. Stepping on this point of view, we developed **16** custom white paper for **leading multinational companies** in their fields which namely are:

Sectors	Companies	Number of prepared custom white papers
Beverage	CocaCola	4
	PepsiCo	2
	General	2
Choco	Ferrero	2
	Hershey	2
	Mondelez	2
	General	2

Table 19: Prepared custom white papers per sector and companies

Given the great results captured from the participation to the GFSI 2020 conference, the BigDataGrapes outcomes will be also presented in another **GFSI event that is planned for the first quarter of 2021**. Especially, a **GFSI Roundtable on Predictive Analytics: Promise & Perils** has been planned and Agroknow is an invited participant, in order to present the Prediction Dashboard, developed in the Food Protection Pilot of the project.

This predictive analytics-oriented panel consists of representatives from multinational companies and organizations, such as:

- Carletta Ooton (VP Amazon)
- Zoltan Syposs (VP The Coca-Cola Company)
- Prof. Chris Elliott (Queens University Belfast)
- Don Prater (US FDA)

AgriTech commercial exhibitions and trade fairs

BigDataGrapes was represented at multiple conferences, workshops, policy events and emphasis was given to the participation in AgriTech commercial exhibitions and trade fairs. In order to show the commercial exploitation of the project, it was considered expedient to participate in exhibitions and trade fairs where we had the opportunity to interact with other stakeholders (e.g., pioneer companies in the key-fields) and get feedback. This feedback helped us understand and validate the users' needs.

In total, we attended four (4) Trade Fairs, in different European countries (Netherlands, Italy and Germany) during the first two (2) years of the project. The presentation of project's findings (commercial and non-commercial) in trade fairs was an important dissemination activity, providing an opportunity to present BigDataGrapes results and engage with various industry stakeholders. As it is depicted in the Table 20, GEOCLIDIAN was the main partner of our consortium who participated in these events, promoting and disseminating the initial outcomes through the usage of booths, flyers or distributing brochures to the participants which approximately were **545.100**, in all of the 4 Trade Fairs. The two (2) most- important trade fairs were:

- **“TUTTOWine”**: is part of the TUTTOFOOD, a B2B exhibition for the entire agri-food ecosystem. TUTTOFOOD is a barometer which measures trends and a hub for information and knowledge. As an international hub, TUTTOFOOD continuously monitors all supply chains and consumer styles to identify the latest hot topics, best practices and international scenarios and help companies make the right decisions, thanks to periodic insights offering a global picture of the food&beverage world. On 10th of May, 2019, GEOCLIDIAN's representatives (Farm Management Pilot Leader with ABACO) attended the TUTTOFOOD 2020 in Milano, Italy, informing the 82.000 participants about the BigDataGrapes initiative.
- **“Agrotechnica”**: All leading companies in the AgriTech sector presented their new products and innovations at the world's leading trade fair for agricultural machinery. AGRITECHNICA is the meeting place for decision-makers and the leading business marketplace. It is a showcase for the global agricultural engineering industry and a forum for the future of crop production. From the 10th until 16th of November, 2019, GEOCLIDIAN's representatives attended the Agrotechnica 2020 in Hannover, Germany, informing the 450.000 participants about the BigDataGrapes project.

#	Event Name	Partners	Event Type	Nature	Location (City)	Date(s)	Number of participants
Training events of young scientists							
1	Geospatial sciences - Digital geospatial data (GIS)	AUA	Master course	Brochure distribution	Athens, Greece	9/5/2018	20
2	Big Data techniques and applications in the agri-food system	AUA	Master course	Brochure distribution	Saragoza, Spain	17-21/6/2019	80
3	The 12th European Summer School in Information Retrieval	CNR	Conference	Presentation	Milan, Italy	15-19/7/2019	100
4	CASA Doctoral Summer School for Advanced Spatial Modelling 2019	KULeuven	Training/Hackathon	Brochure distribution	London, United Kingdom	21-23/8/2019	40
5	"New technologies for Sustainable Farming" for the "New Agriculture for a New Generation"	AUA	Training	Presentation	Marathonas (online May'20), Kyparissia (Aug'20), Chania (online Oct'20), Greece	Marathonas (May'20), Kyparissia (Aug'20), Chania (Oct'20)	90
6	BigDataGrapes Project introduction in the Master course "Teilflächenspezifischer Pflanzenbau" (Variable rate crop farming)	GEOCLEDIAN	Master course	Presentation	Freising, Germany	27/4/20	17
Events with special interest groups							
1	Big Data Value Meetup Sofia	SAI	Meetup	Panel	Sofia, Bulgaria	16/5/2018	-
2	Joint Workshop on Interfaces and Human Decision Making for Recommender Systems	KU LEUVEN	Workshop	Panel	Vancouver, Canada	2-7/8/2018	-

3	Presentation of BigDataGrapes projects outcome in BigDataValues Forum	Agroknow	Conference	Booth / Brochure distribution	Helsinki, Finland	14-16/10/2019	-
4	Presentation of BigDataGrapes projects outcomes to specific food-related SMEs participating in the EU-funded project Data Pitch	Agroknow	Workshop	Panel	London, United Kingdom	17/10/2019	-
5	Chinese Food Quality and Safety Conference 2019	Agroknow	Conference	Panel	Beijing, China	28/10-1/11/2019	-
6	Global Food Safety Initiative (GFSI)	Agroknow	Conference	Panel	Seattle, USA	25-28/2/2020	-
7	Digital Transformation in Times of Crisis” hosted by GreSI (Group for Research on Systems & Information)	Agroknow	Workshop	Panel	Toronto, Canada	9/11/2020	-
8	13th International Symposium on Environmental Software Systems	Agroknow	Conference	Panel	Wageningen, Netherlands	04-07/02/2020	-
AgriTech commercial exhibitions and trade fairs							
1	Global forum for Innovations in Agriculture	GEOCLEDIAN	Trade Fair	Booth	Utrecht, Netherlands	20-21/06/2018	500
2	Seeds & Chips	GEOCLEDIAN	Trade Fair	Booth	Milan, Italy	6.-9/5/2019	12600
3	TuttoWine (part of TuttoFood)	GEOCLEDIAN	Trade Fair	Brochure distribution	Milan, Italy	10/5/2019	82000
4	Agritechnica	GEOCLEDIAN	Trade Fair	Booth	Hannover, Germany	10-16/11/2019	450000

Table 20: BigDataGrapes participation in events [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

5. ENGAGEMENT WITH SMEs

5.1 PORTFOLIO OF SMEs WE WORK WITH

In order to achieve the highest possible impact to the industrial actors we build strong relationships with startups and SMEs. The implemented activities have contributed to stakeholders (including innovators and SMEs) awareness about the project's results. The results can have a positive impact on SMEs (in the wine and natural cosmetics industries but to other food-related sectors), through facilitating them to access e-infrastructures and resources (i.e. datasets, models, analytics workflows, services) as part of their R&D activities. At the same time, the project can facilitate SMEs to become suppliers of novel methods and resources for the wine and natural cosmetics industries i.e. to act as added-value suppliers of e-infrastructures and relevant resources. In order to substantiate these impacts, the partners have addressed and been engaged effectively with SMEs during the whole project lifetime.

The goal was to establish a link by exploiting the BigDataGrapes Platform API to a non-necessarily-agricultural sector, which presents thematic overlaps with research communities already engaged in the scope of BigDataGrapes' activities.

Using the Big Data Grapes software stack, Agroknow developed a Data API for sharing global food safety data with third party systems such as the ABACO Farmer application. The data exposes the enriched version of the different types of the food safety data that is collected and processed by the Big Data Platform. The Data API was shared with startups and companies from the food industry to collect feedback about the coverage and the methods that are provided by the API. This section focuses on the exploitation of the Big Data Platform' Data API that was developed in the context of the BigDataGrapes project. The Data API was used by 5 start-ups and the use cases for each company are analysed in this section.

5.1.1 THE CASE OF ISMOOD

Intro about the company

isMOOD (<https://www.ismood.com/>) is providing an online platform for social media mining focusing on specific geographical regions. It provides the services to companies from several sectors such as financial, food, health, retailers and insurance. It monitors the brand of the companies and provides analytics and sentiment analysis based on the data that is collecting from social networks and media sites.

Contact point

Taniou Pinelopi, Account manager.

The use case

The main objective of the use case was to study the impact in the brand of a food company due to food recalls.

isMOOD is working with large food brands such as Nestle and Coca Cola. To provide an integrated service to food companies for brand monitoring, isMOOD needed access to data about food recalls. More specifically, the goal was to study the impact of food product recalls to a company's brand. isMOOD used the Big Data Platform Data API, to get the information of product recalls and border rejections for all the food companies that it serves.

BigDataGrapes technical partners helped isMOOD Data engineers to create a bridge that uses the Data API to pull information from the BigDataPlatform and link this information with the social data for a specific company.

5.1.2 THE CASE OF CREMEGLOBAL

Intro about the company

Creme Global (<https://www.cremeglobal.com/>) is a data modelling, visual analytics and computing company working to enable better decision making in a complex world. Creme Global is working with many of the biggest companies in the world. They help organisations to understand the context of their data and provide unequalled services in scientific modelling, data analytics and new model development utilising advanced cloud computing technology and curated data sets. They are working with large brands from the food sector such as Cargill, Unilever and Kerry. They have developed a data platform, namely Data Foundry, that was used by the Food Industry Intelligence Network to collect food fraud and authenticity data from the laboratory tests that food companies are conducting.

Contact point

Brendan Ring, Commercial Director

The use case

The collaboration with Creme Global focused on two aspects:

- a) On how data from the BigDataPlatform about food safety and fraud incidents can be integrated into their Data Platform
- b) How the risk assessment models that they are building for assessing the exposure to chemicals can utilize the data from the BigDataPlatform that was setup in the context of the BigDataGrapes project.

The **objective** of the use case was to manage concerns related to perceived increase in risk to consumers due to a particular pesticide residue alert.

Example scenario: One of the many global regulatory authorities detect a pesticide residue on a produce (e.g., a fruit like grapes, vegetable, dairy etc.) at above the Maximum allowable Residue Level (MRL). The regulatory authority issues an alert on their publicly available website. This alert causes anxiety with some consumers / lobby groups. Even though it was the agri producer or processor that used incorrect quantity of pesticide, it triggers a negative reaction to the pesticide manufacturer. The pesticide manufacturing company(s) must provide clear communication based on solid science to mitigate the concerns and de-escalate the issue.

The means by which to provide this communication can be achieved by:

1. Calculating the typical exposure a population would have to a particular pesticide residue.
2. Determining what the change in exposure would be due to the increased concentration as referenced in the alert.
3. Compare the two charts and show the impact related to the alert

5.1.3 THE CASE OF PROVISION ANALYTICS

Intro about the company

Provision Analytics (<https://www.provisionanalytics.io/>) has developed a data platform that captures and interprets all the food data in one place. Using their platform, they have built a food safety compliance and traceability solution, to help food businesses to go 100% paperless.

Contact point

Michael Gibbons, VP Product

The use case

The main objective of the use case was to empower the Provision Analytics' data platform with global food safety data of the Big Data Platform.

More specifically, Provision Analytics' Engineers used the Data API of the Big Data Platform to pull information about food safety incidents linked to the products and suppliers of their customers. The use case focused on developing the integration of the global food safety data for specific supply chains in North America such as the ones for seafood and protein. The dashboards the Provision Analytics provides to their customers were enhanced with the information of food recalls and border rejections providing improved evaluation reports for ingredients and suppliers. As the platform of Provision Analytics focus very much on traceability, we used the information of UPC and LOT number to interconnect the data from the two platforms.

5.1.4 THE CASE OF MESH INTELLIGENCE

Intro about the company

Mesh Intelligence (<https://www.meshintel.com/>) provides services for predicting food safety and food supply chain risks. They work with the world's leading organizations and help them to predict, plan for, manage and avoid costly food safety and supply chain disruption.

Contact point

Shub Debgupta, CEO

The use case

The main objective of this use case was to use the global food safety incidents to predict risks in the supply chain. More specifically, Mesh Intelligence is focusing on developing risk prediction models that are based both on the company's internal data and external data for the global supply chain. Its engineers were seeking for more datasets in order to build more accurate prediction models. This is how they approached Agroknow and asked if we could provide the global food safety data in the form of Data API. The use case focused on the dairy sector and specifically on milk and milk products. They used the food safety incidents that the Big Data Platform is collecting and exposing through the Data API in order to develop models that may predict biological hazards. The outcomes of developing prediction models for the case of dairy sector were presented to one of the largest dairy companies on the world.

5.1.5 THE CASE OF BRITESCAN

Intro about the company.

BriteScan (<https://britescan.com/>) team started in 2010 as one of the most successful natural product DNA testing labs in the United States. That lab conducted testing and method development for some of the world’s largest retailers, dietary supplement manufacturers, herb & spice and food companies in the world including federal government agencies like the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA), US Department of Agriculture (USDA), National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), US Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS), and National Center for Complementary and Integrative Health (NCCIH) and the National Institutes of Health (NIH). In 2015 they sold that lab to an international standard setting organization. In 2018, BriteScan team discovered the power, speed and affordability of Artificial Intelligence and they launched the BriteScan portable testing device.

Today BriteScan’s platform provides fast, affordable testing to government bodies, third party testing labs, manufacturers, food & beverage companies, cannabis growers and oil producers on a global basis.

Contact point

Danica Reynaud, CEO

The use case

BriteScan is currently looking for ways to enhance the detection capability of their device. To that direction they need access to more data about fraud and adulteration cases identified in the ingredients that are tested for authenticity using their device. The data of fraud and adulteration cases can be used to train the artificial intelligence models that are used to classify the samples to authentic or not. More specifically, they wanted to focus on the herbs and spices as well as olive oil. To get the critical mass of fraud and adulteration data that are needed to train the algorithms, they have used the Data API of the Big Data Platform that was developed in the context of the BigDataGrapes. The results of integrating more data in the BriteScan for the case of herbs and spices was evaluated and presented to a very large manufacturer.

5.2 TRAINING MEETUPS WITH FOOD COMPANIES

A series of training meetup sessions (29) were organised during the last three months of the pilot implementation, in order to introduce the Prediction Dashboard to food companies and validate it. These training sessions were planned and executed in order to create a buzz around the BigDataGrapes innovations in the agrifood ecosystem.

Company Name	Number of training sessions	HQ Location
Unilever	2	United Kingdom
PepsiCo	1	United States
Conagra Brands, Inc.	2	United States
Schreiber Foods	7	United States
Haribo	2	Germany
Yili	1	China
Coca-Cola European Partners	2	United Kingdom
Danone	1	France

Perfetti	1	Italy
Hershey	1	United States
Mars	1	United States
AB InBev	1	Belgium
ABP	2	United Kingdom
Buhler AG	1	Switzerland
WorldAware, Inc.	1	United States
Zaragoza Logistics Center	1	Spain
Creme Global	1	Ireland
André Simonazzi	1	Switzerland
Total training sessions on predictions	29	

Table 21: Prediction Dashboard training sessions

During the training session we presented to the participants how they can use the predictions dashboard to:

- 1) identify the hazards that they need to include in their testing plan by knowing the increasing risk trends for all their ingredients;
- 2) identify products that will be affected by the emerging and increasing risks;
- 3) identify the sourcing countries with the highest predicted risk for their ingredients.

Moreover, a **dedicated online workshop** was also carried out on the 8th of December, 2020 with 13 members of the Conagra company. Conagra Brands, Inc. (founded in 1919) is an American packaged foods company headquartered in Chicago, Illinois. It is an approximately \$8 billion company that combines a rich heritage of making great food with a sharpened focus and entrepreneurial spirit. Conagra makes and sells products under various brand names that are available in supermarkets, restaurants, and food service establishments.

Throughout the workshop we presented live and in real time the Prediction Dashboard we implement for the Food Protection Pilot and we had the chance to ask specific questions to the participants about all the above functionalities. The next figures present the summary of the answers we received.

Figure 26: Prediction Dashboard suppliers coverage

Figure 27: Prediction Dashboard sources coverage

Figure 28: Prediction Dashboard timesaving

Finally, to better understand our audience and have some critical insights about the pains that the prediction dashboard is going to relieve, we asked the participants about the value proposition they see from the adoption of a tool like this. It is clear that the majority of the participants have already identified the need to move to a

more a proactive approach and use the right tools which will give them the ability to predict risks before they occur. The full set of the results are depicted in the following figure.

Figure 29: Prediction Dashboard relevancy

5.3 SOCIAL DATA INTEGRATION

In order to integrate the consumer's view about food safety and fraud issues, we expanded the Big Data Platform with components that can be used to collect data from social media. With this integration the Big Data Platform is collecting posts and comments in Greek from social media such as Facebook and Twitter. Sentiment analysis is performed for each text to identify positive, negative and neutral views of the consumers. This is a high velocity data source that was integrated in the Big Data Platform.

We run a specific use case about the recall of a honey product by a retailer in Greece. The historical food safety and fraud data were used to predict the hazards or fraud issues that can lead to a honey product recall. The social data were used to study the impact of the recall to the brand reputation. The case was presented to the retailer.

Figure 30 Example of social data report for an impact of a honey product recall

5.4 OPEN DATA COUNTRY RISK INSIGHTS AND INTEGRATION OF THE COVID-19 RELATED DATA SOURCES SAFETY DATA

The COVID-19 situation has disrupted the global supply chain in several ways (<https://agroknow.com/fsqa-digital-transformation/fears-of-global-food-shortages-on-the-major-food-production-countries-around-the-world/>). As a response to the COVID-19 situation, Agroknow developed a live and open country risk dashboard (<https://open.agroknow.com/>) combining the data from the global supply chain with the data about the pandemic status in each country. To develop the risk dashboard, we integrated into the Big Data Platform that was developed using BigDataGrapes software stack, daily open data about COVID-19 cases that are published by European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. This COVID-19 data was linked with the food safety profile data of each country.

The main goal was to inform and help the food safety experts working in food companies, national authorities, research centers and universities to have the most updated view of each country and to be able to explore the correlation of the pandemic with the food safety profile of the country. The risk dashboard provides open access to the data collected and processed in the context of the BigDataGrapes projects and analytics about COVID-19 status in the country and the status of the food safety incidents for the products that are produced in the country (figure).

Figure 31: The COVID-19 live and open risk dashboard for the food industry

5.5 INDUSTRY INNOVATION GROUP ON PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS FOR FOOD INTEGRITY

In our effort to explore the applicability and value of predictive analytics in food integrity scenarios, validate the outcomes of the BigDataGrapes project and explore all the exploitable assets of the project, an informal industry innovation group was set up, inviting people that would be interested to follow the relevant developments, participate in shaping requirements, and try how predictive analytics work for ingredients and raw materials of high importance to their work.

This group is entitled **“Industry Innovation Group on Predictive Analytics for Food Integrity”** and is an ongoing project with the collaboration of Prof. Chris Elliott from Queen’s University of Belfast, the food authenticity testing startup Bia Analytical Ltd., and the scientific modelling & data analytics leader Creme Global.

As of today, they come from over 20 companies of different types and sizes. We asked this group a very simple, but an important question: **“What is your experience with predictive analytics?”**

Their response was extremely interesting: **Almost 45% said that they have heard and read a lot about predictive analytics, but they haven’t tried it yet.**

Through the BigDataGrapes results (mainly from the piloting activities and evaluation assessment) we saw tremendous value in enhancing the predictive capabilities of food risk assessment and prevention. We also believe that there is an untapped potential in the way that AI-powered prediction machines can help us anticipate and mitigate food risks.

On the other hand, training, deploying and operating a reliable predictive analytics solution for food safety is not as simple as it may initially seem. What we hear from the industry is that companies want to give this technology a serious chance. They are already devoting significant budget to it as they know it will lead to better decision making and a competitive advantage.

On the other hand, the participants also report that:

- They do not have time to experiment with immature, incomplete solutions that have no clear objectives.
- They need reliable, consistent, well thought out tools and services will support people in existing tasks and decision making.
- They are looking for tools that will help them save time, prevent risks, and manage resources effectively.
- They are keen to use solutions that can work next to the human experts, providing recommendations that will support food safety professionals in their decision-making process.

Simply put: the results of this group showed us that the food industry is looking for reliable predictive analytics solutions that can be applied in real-life business settings, to help solve every day food safety challenges.

5.6 INDUSTRY INNOVATION GROUP ON PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS FOR FOOD INTEGRITY

Dr. Nikos Manouselis (Coordinator of the BigDataGrapes Project) was invited by John Keogh from Shantalla Inc., to share his perspective on the challenges and opportunities of the food industry, as part of the 2020 Future of Food – 10X10 CEO Interview Series.

This series comprises 10 interviews with 10 companies/experts on advanced technologies including AI, ML, Big Data etc. This was an amazing opportunity to discuss some of the first findings of the BigDataGrapes project, ranging from the importance of using trusted data sources for critical food safety decisions to whether AI algorithms can go wrong.

Figure 32: The 2020 future of food 10x10 series

In the interview Dr. Manouselis highlighted the urgent need to take advantage of all the data that is out there, for traceability, provenance or prevention purposes. This need becomes more urgent these days because, due to the Covid-19 outbreak, it is difficult for people working at the food industry to actually go out and perform an inspection – of an establishment, a procedure or other. So, we have to take action based on the information available at hand. But how can we combine this information? How can we connect this information?

As part of the work already done, Dr. Manouselis mentioned that we already know how to gather all this information, create the links, and develop the necessary decision support and analytics on top of all the data. Right now, this is what is needed, but at a very large scale.

The key points of the interview can be found in the [BigDataGrapes website](#).

The series of interviews are already planned to recure on 2021 and Dr. Manouselis is again invited and will participate aiming to give his perspective based on the final results of the BigDataGrapes project. The 2021 series

is entitled “The 2021 future of food 10x10 series: Predictive analytics in the food chain” and is planned to be realised in the first quarter of the year.

Coming in January-February

The 2021 Future of Food 10x10 Series #1: Predictive Analytics in the Food Chain

This series comprises 10 interviews with 10 companies/experts on advanced technologies including AI, ML, Big Data etc. that contribute to the predictive nature of key aspects in the food chain from food safety, food fraud, food loss/waste, supply-demand balancing and more. After the 10 interviews, the series will conclude with an academic panel to discuss the content and identify key gaps in knowledge and research.

Figure 33: The 2021 future of food 10x10 series: Predictive analytics in the food chain

6. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS AND OUTLETS

6.1 PRESS PUBLICATIONS

Besides its main dissemination channels, the project partners prepared a number of online press publications and communicated the project objectives and vision via online dissemination media. For example, a blogpost was published by ONTOTEXT to its blog, entitled “From Cultivating Nature to Cultivating Data: Semantic Technology and Viticulture” (<https://bit.ly/2l4CMG5>). Additionally, on February 2019 an online article was published at Kathimerini, one of the biggest Greek newspapers, entitled "Agricultural production with satellites and robots" (<https://bit.ly/2ZitvQO>). During M14 of the project, another online article was published in the Derstandard newspaper, concerning the project, entitled “How big data helps winemakers to produce better wine” (<https://bit.ly/2WxrHBK>). One more online article was published at Agroknow’s medium concerning how the project can help the Grape Industry survive through Climate Change, entitled “Sensors, Internet of Things and Vineyards” (<https://bit.ly/2KFQG3g>).

#	Publication Title	Venue	URL	Type	Partner
1st Year					
1	From Cultivating Nature to Cultivating Data: Semantic Technology and Viticulture	ONTOTEXT	https://www.ontotext.com/from-cultivating-nature-to-cultivating-data-semantic-technology-and-viticulture/	Blogpost	ONTOTEXT
2nd Year					
2	Agricultural production with satellites and robotics	Kathimerini	http://www.kathimerini.gr/1008009/gallery/epikairothta/perivallon/agrotikh-paragwgh-medyforoy-kai-rompot	Online article	Agroknow, AUA
3	Sensors, Internet of Things and Vineyards.	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/sensors-internet-of-things-and-vineyards-28b560a7c6d9?sk=bob283d15a7a71579578381c8fa6f93c	Online article	Agroknow
3rd Year					
4	The hidden risks of hazelnuts in the chocolate supply chain	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/the-hidden-risks-of-hazelnuts-in-the-chocolate-supply-chain-69c0bdc73d3b	Online article	Agroknow
5	The power of data behind keeping food safe	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/the-power-of-data-behind-keeping-food-safe-1535e0e5986c	Online article	Agroknow
6	“We are taking people on a journey into data”	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/we-are-taking-people-on-a-journey-into-data-e4190d7fffb1	Online article	Agroknow

7	What does the future hold for chocolate?	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/what-does-the-future-hold-for-chocolate-507d05d6bb2e	Online article	Agroknow
8	Data-empowering the Food Safety Sector	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/data-empowering-the-food-safety-sector-9acfa81c46a	Online article	Agroknow
9	Resilient food systems: how does data sharing help?	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/resilient-food-systems-how-can-sharing-data-help-29288ea38580	Online article	Agroknow
10	The art and science of food safety predictions	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/the-art-and-science-of-food-safety-predictions-f45a39208838	Online article	Agroknow
11	Empowering Food Safety Professionals with timely, accurate and customized insights	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/empowering-quality-assurance-and-food-safety-professionals-with-timely-accurate-and-tailor-made-a6f40d96dd15	Online article	Agroknow
12	The power of data behind keeping food safe	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/the-power-of-data-behind-keeping-food-safe-1535e0e5986c	Online article	Agroknow
13	“We are taking people on a journey into data”	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/we-are-taking-people-on-a-journey-into-data-e4190d7fffb1	Online article	Agroknow
14	Food safety innovation in the making: do you want to be part of it?	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/food-safety-innovation-in-the-making-do-you-want-to-be-part-of-it-178a7af593e3	Online article	Agroknow
15	Food safety AI has come to stay — but not without adult supervision	Medium	https://medium.com/@AgroKnow/food-safety-ai-has-come-to-stay-but-not-without-adult-supervision-8e3c45efc110	Online article	Agroknow

Table 22: The BigDataGrapes 15 Press publications [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

6.2 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS IN JOURNALS AND CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

As a research and innovation action (RIA) project, the BigDataGrapes project seeks to have a significant impact on international research in the areas of ICT in agriculture and food, as well as in the area of Big Data. During the lifetime of the project, BigDataGrapes published or accepted for publication **twenty-five (25) papers in scientific Journals and twenty-four (22) papers at International Conferences.**

#	Authors	Paper Title	Publication Type	Publication Venue	Publisher	Status	Publication Date	Lead Partner
1	Nicola Tonello, Craig Macdonald, Iadh Ounis	Efficient Query Processing for Scalable Web Search	Journal paper	Foundations and Trends in Information Retrieval	NOW	Published	2018	CNR
2	Francesco Lettich, Claudio Lucchese, Franco Maria Nardini, Salvatore Orlando, Raffaele Perego, Nicola Tonello, Rossano Venturini	Parallel traversal of large ensembles of decision trees	Journal paper	IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems	IEEE	Published	2018	CNR
3	Manlio Bacco, Matteo Catena, Tomaso de Cola, Alberto Gotta, Nicola Tonello	Performance Analysis of WebRTC-based Video Streaming over Power Constrained Platforms	Conference paper	Proceedings of the 2018 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM 2018)	IEEE	Published	2018	CNR
4	Claudio Lucchese, Franco Maria Nardini, Salvatore Orlando, Raffaele Perego, Fabrizio Silvestri, Salvatore Trani	X-CLEAVER: Learning Ranking Ensembles by Growing and Pruning Trees	Journal paper	ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology	ACM	Published	2018	CNR
5	Claudio Lucchese, Franco Maria Nardini, Raffaele Perego, Roberto Trani, Rossano Venturini	Efficient and Effective Query Expansion for Web Search	Conference paper	Proceedings of the 27th ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management (2018)	ACM	Published	2018	CNR
6	Claudio Lucchese, Franco Maria Nardini, Salvatore Orlando, Raffaele Perego, Salvatore Trani	Selective Gradient Boosting for Effective Learning to Rank	Conference paper	The 41st International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research & Development in Information Retrieval	ACM	Published	2018	CNR

7	Nicola Tonello, Matteo Catena, Ophir Frieder	Efficient energy management in distributed web search	Conference paper	Proceedings of the 27th ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management (2018)	ACM	Published	2018	CNR
8	Giulio Ermanno Pibiri and Rossano Venturini	Handling Massive N-Gram Datasets Efficiently	Journal paper	ACM Transactions on Information Systems (TOIS)	ACM	Accepted	-	CNR
9	Francisco Gutiérrez, Katrien Verbert, Nyi Nyi Htun	PHARA: an augmented reality grocery store assistant	Conference paper	ACM Conference on Human-Computer Interaction with Mobile Devices and Services Adjunct (MobileHCI)	ACM	Published	2018	KULeuven
10	Francisco Gutiérrez, Nyi Nyi Htun, Florian Schlenz, Aikaterini Kasimati, Katrien Verbert	A Review of Visualisations in Agricultural Decision Support Systems: an HCI Perspective	Journal paper	Computers and Electronics in Agriculture	ELSEVIER	Published	2019	KULeuven
11	Karsten Seipp, Francisco Gutiérrez, Xavier Ochoa, Katrien Verbert	Towards a visual guide for communicating uncertainty in Visual Analytics	Journal paper	Journal of Computer Languages	ELSEVIER	Published	2019	KULeuven
12	Franco Maria Nardini, Roberto Trani, Rossano Venturini	Fast Approximate Filtering of Search Results Sorted by Attribute	Conference paper	The 42st International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research & Development in Information Retrieval	ACM	Published	2019	CNR
13	Matteo Catena, Ophir Frieder, Cristina Ioana Muntean, Franco Maria Nardini, Raffaele Perego, Nicola Tonello	Enhanced News Retrieval: Passages Lead the Way!	Conference paper	The 42st International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research & Development in Information Retrieval	ACM	Published	2019	CNR

14	Francisco Gutiérrez, Xavier Ochoa, Karsten Seipp, Tom Broos, Katrien Verbert	Benefits and Trade-offs of Different Model Representations in Decision Support Systems for Non-expert Users	Conference paper	In IFIP Conference on Human-Computer Interaction (INTERACT)	Springer	Published	2019	KULeuven
15	Francesco Lettich, Claudio Lucchese, Franco Maria Nardini, Salvatore Orlando, Raffaele Perego, Nicola Tonello, and Rossano Venturini	Parallel Traversal of Large Ensembles of Decision Trees	Journal paper	IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON PARALLEL AND DISTRIBUTED SYSTEMS	IEEE	Published	2019	CNR
16	Regis Pires Magalhaes, Francesco Lettich, Jose Antonio Macedo, Franco Maria Nardini, Raffaele Perego, Chiara Renso, Roberto Trani	Speed prediction in large and dynamic traffic sensor networks	Journal paper	Information Systems	Springer	Published	2019	CNR
17	Nicola Ferro, Claudio Lucchese, Maria Maistro, Raffaele Perego	Boosting learning to rank with user dynamics and continuation methods	Journal paper	Information Retrieval Journal	Springer	Published	2019	CNR
18	Lorenzo Beretta, Franco Maria Nardini, Roberto Trani, Rossano Venturini.	An Optimal Algorithm to Find Champions of Tournament Graphs.	Conference paper	SPIRE	Springer	Published	2019	CNR
19	Leopoldo Melo Junior, Franco Maria Nardini, Chiara Renso, Jose Antonio Macedo	KNORA-IU: Improving the Dynamic Selection Prediction in Imbalanced Credit Scoring Problems	Conference paper	IEEE ICTAI	IEEE	Published	2019	CNR
20	Leopoldo Melo, Franco Maria Nardini, Chiara Renso, José Antônio Fernandes de Macêdo	An Empirical Comparison of Classification Algorithms for Imbalanced Credit Scoring Datasets	Conference paper	IEEE ICMLA	IEEE	Published	2019	CNR
21	Matteo Catena, Nicola Tonello	Multiple Query Processing via Logic Function Factoring	Conference paper	The 42st International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research & Development in Information Retrieval	ACM	Published	2019	CNR

22	Giulio Ermanno Pibiri and Rossano Venturini	On Optimally Partitioning Variable-Byte Codes	Journal paper	IEEE TKDE	IEEE	Published	2019	CNR
23	Diego Rojo Garcia, Nyi Nyi Htun, Katrien Verbert	A knowledge-based visual support system for selecting machine learning models	Journal paper	Computers and Electronics in Agriculture	ELSEVIER	Published	2020	KULeuven
24	I. Polychronou, P. Katsivelis, M. Papakonstantinou, J. Stoitsis and N. Manouselis	Machine Learning Algorithms for Food Intelligence: Towards a Method for More Accurate Predictions	Conference paper	ISSES2020 13th International Symposium on Environmental Software Systems	Springer	Published	2020	Agroknow
25	Diego Rojo Garcia, Nyi Nyi Htun, Katrien Verbert	GaCoVi: a Correlation Visualization to Support Interpretability-Aware Feature Selection for Regression Models.	Conference paper	EuroVis 2020	Eurographics	Published	2020	KULeuven
26	Giulio Ermanno Pibiri, Raffaele Perego, Rossano Venturini	Compressed Indexes for Fast Search of Semantic Data	Journal paper	IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering	IEEE	Published	2020	CNR
27	Claudio Lucchese, Franco Maria Nardini, Salvatore Orlando, Raffaele Perego, Salvatore Trani	Query-level Early Exit for Additive Learning-to-Rank Ensembles	Conference paper	ACM SIGIR	ACM	Accepted	2020	CNR
28	Sean MacAvaney, Franco Maria Nardini, Raffaele Perego, Nicola Tonello, Nazli Goharian, Ophir Frieder	Training Curricula for Open Domain Answer Re-Ranking	Conference paper	ACM SIGIR	ACM	Accepted	2020	CNR
29	Sean MacAvaney, Franco Maria Nardini, Raffaele Perego, Nicola Tonello, Nazli Goharian, Ophir Frieder	Efficient Document Re-Ranking for Transformers by Precomputing Term Representations	Conference paper	ACM SIGIR	ACM	Accepted	2020	CNR
30	Sean MacAvaney, Franco Maria Nardini, Raffaele Perego, Nicola Tonello, Nazli Goharian, Ophir Frieder	Expansion via Prediction of Importance with Contextualization	Conference paper	ACM SIGIR	ACM	Accepted	2020	CNR

31	Ida Mele, Cristina Ioana Muntean, Franco Maria Nardini, Raffaele Perego, Nicola Tonello, Ophir Frieder	Topic Propagation in Conversational Search	Conference paper	ACM SIGIR	ACM	Accepted	2020	CNR
32	Leopoldo Melo Junior, Franco Maria Nardini, Chiara Renso, Roberto Trani, Jose Antonio Macedo	A novel approach to define the local region of dynamic selection techniques in imbalanced credit scoring problems	Journal paper	Elsevier Expert with Systems Applications	Elsevier	Published	2020	CNR
33	Simon Gog, Giulio Ermanno Pibiri, Rossano Venturini	Efficient and Effective Query Auto-Completion	Conference paper	ACM SIGIR	ACM	Published	2020	CNR
34	Giulio Ermanno Pibiri, Rossano Venturini	Techniques for Inverted Index Compression	Journal paper	ACM CSUR	ACM	Accepted	2020	CNR
35	Cristina Ioana Muntean, Franco Maria Nardini, Raffaele Perego, Nicola Tonello, Ophir Frieder	Weighting Passages Enhances Accuracy	Journal paper	ACM TOIS	ACM	Published	2020	CNR
36	Claudio Lucchese, Cristina Ioana Muntean, Franco Maria Nardini, Raffaele Perego, Salvatore Trani	RankEval: Evaluation and Investigation of Ranking Models	Journal paper	Elsevier SoftwareX	Elsevier	Published	2020	CNR
37	Leopoldo Melo Junior, Franco Maria Nardini, Chiara Renso, Roberto Trani, Jose Antonio Macedo	A Novel Approach to Define the Local Region of Dynamic Selection Techniques in Imbalanced Credit Scoring Problems	Journal paper	Elsevier Expert with Systems Applications	Elsevier	Published	2020	CNR
38	Nicola Tonello, Alberto Gotta, Franco Maria Nardini, Daniele Gadler, Fabrizio Silvestri	Neural Network Quantization in Federated Learning at the Edge	Journal paper	Elsevier Information Sciences	Elsevier	Submitted	2020	CNR
39	Lorenzo Valerio, Franco Maria Nardini, Andrea Passarella, Raffaele Perego	Dynamic Hard Pruning of Neural Networks at the Edge of the Internet	Journal paper	Elsevier Information Sciences	Elsevier	Submitted	2020	CNR
40	Franco Maria Nardini, Roberto Trani, Rossano Venturini	Fast Filtering of Search Results Sorted by Attribute	Journal paper	TOIS	ACM	Submitted	2020	CNR

41	Franco Maria Nardini, Roberto Trani, Rossano Venturini	Learning Bivariate Scoring Functions for Ranking	Conference paper	ACM SIGIR	ACM	Submitted	2020	CNR
42	Ida Mele, Cristina Ioana Muntean, Franco Maria Nardini, Raffaele Perego, Nicola Tonello, Ophir Frieder	Adaptive Utterance Rewriting for Conversational Search	Journal paper	TOIS	ACM	Submitted	2020	CNR
43	Giulio Ermanno Pibiri and Rossano Venturini	Practical Trade-Offs for the Prefix- Sum Problem	Journal paper	Software: Practice and Experience	Wiley	Published	2020	CNR
44	Ioanna Polychronou, Giannis Stoitsis, Mihalis Papakonstantinou, Nikos Manouselis	Stress-testing big data to extract smart and interoperable food safety analytics	Journal paper	International Journal of Signal and Imaging Systems Engineering	InterScience	Submitted	2020	Agroknow
45	A. Kasimati , A. Kalogrias , V. Psiroukis , K. Grivakis , J.A. Taylor and S. Fountas	Are all NDVI maps created equal? - Comparing vineyard NDVI data from Proximal and Remote Sensing	Conference paper	ECPA 2021	ECPA	Submitted	2020	AUA
46	Diego Rojo Garcia, Nyi Nyi Htun, Denis Parra, Robin De Croon, Katrien Verbert	AHMoSe: A Knowledge-Based Visual Support System for Selecting Regression Machine Learning Models	Journal paper	Computers and Electronics in Agriculture	Elsevier	Submitted	2020	KULeuven
47	Nyi Nyi Htun, Diego Rojo Garcia, Jeroen Ooge, Robin De Croon, Aikaterini Kasimati, Katrien Verbert	Developing Visual-assisted Decision Support Systems across Diverse Precision Agriculture Use Cases	Journal paper	Computers and Electronics in Agriculture	Elsevier	Forthcoming	2020	KULeuven / AUA

Table 23: Scientific Journals and papers at International Conferences [01.01.2018 - 31.12.2020]

6.3 DISSEMINATION MATERIALS

To support the promotion activities of the project, a total number of 5 dissemination materials have been prepared, in order to be distributed by the project partners in the scope of conferences, workshops, fairs and other events:

- **BigDataGrapes project poster roll-up** presents the main project motto, as well as the project consortium and links to the project social media and web-site.
- **BigDataGrapes project general brochure** (2 editions) presents an overview of the BigDataGrapes project, its main objectives, as well as the project consortium and links to the project social media and web-site.
- **BigDataGrapes project flyer** (2 editions) presents an overview of the BigDataGrapes project, the vision, the pilots as well as the project consortium.

#	Material Title	URL	Lead Partner
1	Roll Up Banner	http://www.bigdatagrappes.eu/sites/default/files/Rollup.pdf	Agroknow
2	Flyer	http://www.bigdatagrappes.eu/sites/default/files/Flyer.pdf	Agroknow
3	e-Brochure	http://www.bigdatagrappes.eu/sites/default/files/e-Brochure.pdf	Agroknow
4	e-Brochure (2020 update)	http://www.bigdatagrappes.eu/sites/default/files/e-Brochure_2020.pdf	Agroknow
5	Flyer (2020 update)	http://www.bigdatagrappes.eu/sites/default/files/Flyer_2020.pdf	Agroknow

Table 24: Dissemination material

Some samples of the dissemination material are presented in the following figures:

Figure 34: BigDataGrapes Rollup sample

The flyer is divided into several sections:

- BIG DATA GRAPES** (Logo)
- SUPPORTING THE EUROPEAN GRAPEVINE-POWERED INDUSTRY**
 - Big Data Grapes is an ICT project that aims to enhance the wine and natural cosmetics industries.
 - We improve the competitive positioning of companies in the European IT sector that are serving companies and organisations with software applications, such as:
 - Farm management and precision agriculture systems for vineyards
 - Food risk assessment monitoring and prediction systems for companies in the food sector.
 - Quality control and compliance software for companies in the beauty and cosmetics sector.
- THE BIGGER VISION**
 - Big Data Grapes aims to help European companies in the wine and natural cosmetics industries become more competitive in the international markets.
 - Targeting technology challenges of the grapevine-powered data economy as its business problems and decisions requires processing analysis and visualisation of data with rapidly increasing volume, velocity and variety; satellite and weather data, environmental and geological data, phenotypic and genetic plant data, food supply chain data, economic and financial data and more.
 - It therefore makes a perfectly suitable cross-sector and cross-country combination of industries that are of high European significance and value.
- TARGET GROUPS**
 - WINE PRODUCERS, BOTTLERS & DISTRIBUTORS
 - PRODUCERS & PACKAGERS OF FOOD & WINE PRODUCTS
 - NATURAL COSMETIC COMPANIES
 - QA & FS AND R&D EXPERTS IN FOOD & WINE SECTOR
- PILOTS & LEADERS**
 - 01 TABLE & WINE GRAPES PILOT**: Leader: AJA. Improve the quality of table & wine grapes.
 - 02 WINE MAKING PILOT**: Leader: INRA. Improve the quality of wine and support the efficient management of the vineyard.
 - 03 FARM MANAGEMENT PILOT**: Leader: ABACO. Improve the ability to take quick and informed decisions through farm management systems.
 - 04 NATURAL COSMETICS PILOT**: Leader: SYMBEOSIS. Correlate different quality biomarkers for producing better grape extracts used for natural cosmetics.
 - 05 FOOD PROTECTION PILOT**: Leader: AGROKNOW. Enhance the current digital solution with new modules that will address further needs of the grape and wine supply chain.

Figure 35: BigDataGrapes Flyer

Figure 36: BigDataGrapes Brochure sample

6.4 WHITE AND DISCUSSION PAPERS

6.4.1 WHITE AND DISCUSSION PAPERS CONTENT

In order to outreach policy & decision makers and inform them about project activities, outcomes, successes and societal impact we develop, except of the scientific papers, three extra papers (i.e. two white papers and one discussion paper). These papers offer insights to some of the major problems faced on the food supply chain such as the access to global food safety data, fraud data, predictions for food risks and exploit the results of the BigDataGrapes project in order to provide critical information for other food sectors.

White Paper 1: Lessons learned from global food safety and fraud data and the guidance it can provide to the food industry

The chocolate industry, according to a recent study by the International Cocoa Organization, is the top performing sector of the confectionery industries. Cocoa and chocolate products rely on high-quality ingredients and raw materials, strict supplier partnership schemes and conformity to clearly defined quality and safety standards.

Over the course of the past 10 years there have been a significant number of food safety incidents associated with chocolate products. The presence of Salmonella enterica, Listeria monocytogenes, allergens and foreign

materials in cocoa/chocolate products have been reported on a global scale. Today, information on food safety incidents and potential risks is quickly and widely available by way of the internet.

However, **because the pertinent data is frequently siloed**, food safety professionals are unable to take full advantage of it. The combination of contemporary consumer concerns and awareness, the global distribution of cocoa/chocolate products, the complexity of multi-continental food supply chains, and the highly diverse product lines within food industries, creates an environment where food safety challenges and threats to the integrity of brands are continuously increasing.

The full document can be found here in pdf format:

http://bigdatagrapes.eu/sites/default/files/BigDataGrapes_White_Paper.pdf

Figure 37: Cover page of the White Paper 1: Lessons learned from global food safety and fraud data and the guidance it can provide to the food industry

White Paper 2: What we can learn for non-alcoholic beverages from global food safety and fraud data

The non-alcoholic beverage sector plays a key role in the global economy, as it is among the top performing F&B industries. According to the American Beverage Association, the direct impact of the industry accounts for 182.6 billion dollars. Among others, soft drinks, juices and functional drink products rely on high-quality ingredients

and raw materials, strict supplier partnership schemes and conformity to a wide range of quality and safety standards.

When it comes to food safety, there have been **several recall incidents over the last few years** associated with non-alcoholic beverages. Especially during the last decade, incidents relating to chemical hazards are the top concern in the non-alcoholic beverage sector, with food additives and flavourings being among the main associated ingredients that have been reported on a global scale.

Non-alcoholic beverages constitute a diverse group of products. There are several ways in which they are classified, e.g. on the basis of their sugar and fruit juice content, flavoring, carbonation level, main non-water ingredients, and functionality.

The main categories of non-alcoholic beverages that this industry report covers are: Soft Drinks; Juice Drinks; Juices; Energy Drinks; Water; Functional Drinks.

The full document can be found here in pdf format:

http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/sites/default/files/BigDataGrapes_White_Paper_Non-Alcoholic_Beverages.pdf

Figure 38: Cover page of the White Paper 2: What we can learn for non-alcoholic beverages from global food safety and fraud data

Discussion Paper: Artificial Intelligence & Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention

Access to food safety insights enables businesses and professionals alike, to identify, monitor and prevent any increasing risks or incidents that need global attention across the complete supply chain. Technology alone is not enough. In order to truly enrich data to create actionable intelligence – for example reactive and predictive insights on the global supply chain – we must integrate human skills and expertise as well. Using scientific or hands-on human expertise can help interpret (and even sense-check) the results thrown out by sophisticated AI algorithms.

Frequently, for example, big data analytics and machine learning are very effective at identifying that something has happened but are less effective at explaining why. That's where you need the human approach to enrich data insights and create tailormade intelligence to achieve greater visibility across the global food supply chain.

As part of our two EU-funded data related initiatives: "**Big Data Grapes**" as well as "**Cybele**" we are investigating ways in which big data and AI can support decision scenarios of high risk and uncertainty. We wanted to understand better which changes we should expect in the near future regarding **AI and Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention**. We therefore reached out to the community, asking distinguished colleagues from a variety of supply chain stakeholders about their opinion on what impact predictive analytics are having on the food supply chain and what are the critical food risk assessment and prevention questions that we would expect AI to help answer.

The full document can be found here in pdf format:

http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/sites/default/files/Agroknow-BigDataGrapes-Discussion_Paper.pdf

Figure 39: Cover page of the Discussion Paper: Artificial Intelligence & Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention

6.4.2 WHITE AND DISCUSSION PAPERS CAMPAIGNS

For the efficient promoting of the papers presented in the previous section we created digital campaigns, with the majority of them funnelled by Agroknow’s LinkedIn page. A series of posts were posted and promoted and dedicated landing pages were designed for each case in order to maximize the impact from the papers. In the following pictures we present the case of the white paper “Lessons learned from global food safety and fraud data and the guidance it can provide to the food industry”.

Figure 40: Landing Page sample for promoting White Paper: Lessons learned from global food safety and fraud data and the guidance it can provide to the food industry

Figure 41: Thank you mail after downloading the White Paper: Lessons learned from global food safety and fraud data and the guidance it can provide to the food industry

Agroknow
1,575 followers
1yr

The number of safety incidents for cocoa has been doubled between 2009-2010. Get the latest trends for food protection in the free report.

Number of **safety** incidents

Year	Incidents
2002	1
2003	2
2004	3
2005	4
2006	6
2007	12
2008	10
2009	18
2010	15
2011	10

Food Safety Insights
reports.foodakai.com

Figure 42: Example post from LinkedIn

12 ads		-	€177.72	-	-	15,371		
<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>Food Safety Hazards Chemical hazards constitute the major hazard category for cocoa products. See a detailed raw material vulnerability analysis in our free report.</p> <p><small>Creative name: image ad 4 d Campaign: UK Image Ads - Member Skills Creative ID: 90049693 - Sponsored Content - Single Image</small></p>		...	Paused ▼	€116.84	25 Website Visits	€4.67	7,459
<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>Food Safety Assesment Cocoa from South America has been associated with 45 food safety incidents the past 3 years. Find out about regional food fraud risk analysis in our free</p> <p><small>Creative name: image ad 3 d Campaign: UK Image Ads - Member Skills Creative ID: 90049703 - Sponsored Content - Single Image</small></p>		...	Paused ▼	€8.53	2 Website Visits	€4.27	2,456
Food Safety Hazards								

Figure 43: Screenshot from the LinkedIn ad manager

Agroknow
1,575 followers
1yr • Edited

Cocoa from South America has been associated with 45 food safety incidents the past 3 years. Find out about regional food fraud risk analysis in our free report.

Food Safety Hazards
forestvieweu.go2cloud.org

Figure 44: Example post from LinkedIn (2)

Agroknow
1,575 followers
1yr

Chemical hazards constitute the major hazard category for cocoa products. See a detailed raw material vulnerability analysis in our free report.

Food Safety Hazards
forestvieweu.go2cloud.org

Figure 45: Example post from LinkedIn (3)

7. COLLABORATION WITH OTHER INITIATIVES

Collaboration is essential to thriving in an ever-changing environment. It has been a big issue the past several years, as organizations realize that effective collaboration is key to innovation. New methods have emerged to extend the meaning of collaboration from the simple act of working together to a more complex function of inter-relating diverse teams to achieve new ideas, innovative practices and to yield superior results. These methods include practices and tools that promote communication, idea sharing and transparency for local and distributed teams. The activities, in terms of communication, are listed in the following table and a detailed table with all the engaged projects with which we had indirect cooperation by presenting BigDataGrapes objectives and outcomes in events we participated in is presented in Annex B.

#	Title	Info URL	Partner	Project	Type	Country	Date(s)
1	Sustainable Farming	http://www.sfarm-project.eu/	AUA	SFARM	Workshop	Greece	14/1/2019
2	Big Data	https://plus.aginfra.eu/	Agroknow	agINFRA+	Meetup	Digital	10/3/2019
3	Predictions for food safety	https://foodsafetymarket.eu/	Agroknow	TheFSM	Meetup	Digital	1/9/2019
4	DSS tools in vines	https://www.ochravine.eu/	AUA	OchraVine Control	Meetup	Digital	29/01/2020
5	Crop management DSS tools	https://www.plantteams.eu/	Agroknow	Diversify	Meetup	Digital	20/02/2020
6	Decision making	https://www.iof2020.eu/	AUA	IOF2020	Meetup	Digital	15/3/2020
7	Data management, Open Science, e-Infrastructure	https://www.smartcow.eu/	INRAE/ Agroknow	SmartCow	Presentation	Digital	13/10/2020
8	Artificial Intelligence & Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/node/148	Agroknow	CYBELE	Discussion Paper	Digital	28/1/2021

Table 25: Collaboration activities with other projects

Moreover, during the project’s lifetime, we have communicated and incorporated the developed project’s tools and data to several EU and international projects. For the collaboration we used a standardized methodology for uploading data to the BigDataGrapes platform.

Process for continuous data Integration

Step 1: Use the data integration tool to upload the dataset or the end point. The dataset or end point will be added to the registry of the data platform

1. **Data Source Selection:** The user chooses the source of data to be uploaded (file or API endpoint);

2. **Data Type Selection:** The user chooses the type of data to be uploaded (based on the data types obtained from the Agroknow Data Integration API);
3. **Data Upload:** The user uploads the file;
4. **Data Mapping:** The user maps their file columns to the expected schema elements, according to the Data Integration API specification;
5. **Data Editor:** The user proceeds to fill-in missing or erroneous values in an online spreadsheet-like interface;
6. **Metadata:** The user inputs some metadata that accompany the file that they want to publish and optionally, select the data asset that they want to associate the file with;

Step 2: The new dataset is reviewed by the Big Data Platform expert

Step 3: The new dataset appears in the Big Data Platform Dashboard in the Registry

Step 4: The new dataset is processed by the data platform

Step 5: The new dataset is available through the Data Platform API end point

7.1 LIAISON WITH CYBELE

Use Case

CYBELE it's a EU funded project (<https://www.cybele-project.eu/>) that provides access to high performance computing resources in order to address challenges of the agri-food sector. It focuses on several use cases of the agri-food sector and one of them is the food safety use case. It aims at enhancing the SMEs that are providing innovative services to the stakeholders of the food sector.

The project has used the big data components developed in the context of BigDataGrapes, to perform data enrichment and to generate predictive analytics that will enable the prediction of food safety and fraud risks at a large scale.

Software stack components shared

The software components that were used by CYBELE are the following

- Knowledge classification component
- Trend analytics component
- Food risk estimation component
- Prediction component
- Correlation component

Data shared

Dataset 1	Global Food Recalls
Metadata/Description	The food recalls data that are collected by from 35 National Authorities all around the world. The data are processed and enriched using the BigDataGrapes software stack.
Provider	Agroknow
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 1.2 GB of data
Velocity	The provided dataset is accessed through a REST service and shows the desired velocity since it is generated and ingested in real-time
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data

Dataset 2		Border rejections
Metadata/Description	The food border rejections data that are collected and processed by 9 National Authorities all around the world.	
Provider	Agroknow	
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 1.4 GB of data	
Velocity	The provided dataset is accessed through a REST service and shows the desired velocity since it is generated and ingested in real-time	
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data	

Dataset 3		Laboratory testing data
Metadata/Description	The results of the chemicals monitoring programs collected from 33 countries. The laboratory testing data are processed and enriched using the BigDataGrapes software stack.	
Provider	Agroknow	
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 117 GB of data.	
Velocity	The provided dataset is accessed through a REST service and shows the desired velocity since it is generated and ingested in real-time	
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data	

Dataset 4		Price data
Metadata/Description	Price data for agricultural products collected from the European Commission's prices monitoring service.	
Provider	Agroknow	
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 2.68 GB of data	
Velocity	The provided dataset is accessed through a REST service and shows the desired velocity since it is generated and ingested in real-time	
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data	

Dataset 5		Fraud cases data
Metadata/Description	Data for fraud cases including the economical motivation adulteration and food authenticity issues that are reported by the National Authorities and food safety professional websites.	
Provider	Agroknow	
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 0.28 GB of data	
Velocity	The provided dataset is accessed through a REST service and shows the desired velocity since it is generated and ingested in real-time	
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data	

Dataset 6		Production data
Metadata/Description	Data from FAOSTAT about the production of agriculture products and livestock.	

Provider	FAOSTAT
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 0.8 MB of data
Velocity	The dataset was provided in the form of a data dump (csv).
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data

Dataset 7	Trade data
Metadata/Description	Data from FAOSTAT about the trade of agriculture products and livestock.
Provider	FAOSTAT
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 0.7 MB of data
Velocity	The dataset was provided in the form of a data dump (csv).
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data

Results

The results of the collaboration between the CYBELE and BigDataGrapes project focused on developing a holistic and tailor-made prediction model for the food companies by combining different data types such as food recalls, border rejections, laboratory data and price data. The software components were ported on the CYBELE computing infrastructure and the risk prediction was performed for all the possible hazards – ingredient pair. Taking into account that we have more than 4.000 ingredients and more that 1.300 hazards, and that we used more than 100 million of records, the prediction of risk for each hazard and ingredient pair results in a computational intensive problem.

7.2 LIAISON WITH THEFSM

Use Case

H2020 TheFSM project (<https://foodsafetymarket.eu/>) is focusing on the digitalization of the certification process and the development of a food safety data marketplace that will facilitate the secure exchange of the data throughout the supply chain. The project aims at setting up a platform that will provide the secure data exchange services for the global food safety data. For the development of the data exchange platform, it will adopt several components for big data processing that were developed in the context of BigDataGrapes project as well as food protection datasets.

Software stack components shared

TheFSM adopted software components for the data collection from diverse data source, components for the enrichment of the food safety data with hazards and product terms, components for risk estimation and components for the generation of predictive analytics. In addition to this, it will use and further evolve the components for the data marketplace.

More specifically, the software components that were used by TheFSM project are the following:

- Knowledge classification component
- Web scraping component
- Trend analytics component
- Food risk estimation component
- Prediction component

In terms of data, TheFSM will have access to the recalls, border rejections and laboratory data that were developed in the context of the BigDataGrapes project. The details of the datasets that were shared with TheFSM are presented in the following tables.

Data shared

Dataset 1 Global Food Recalls	
Metadata/Description	The food recalls data that are collected by from 35 National Authorities all around the world. The data are processed and enriched using the BigDataGrapes software stack.
Provider	Agroknow
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 1.2 GB of data
Velocity	The provided dataset is accessed through a REST service and shows the desired velocity since it is generated and ingested in real-time
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data

Dataset 2 Border rejections	
Metadata/Description	The food border rejections data that are collected and processed by 9 National Authorities all around the world.
Provider	Agroknow
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 1.4 GB of data
Velocity	The provided dataset is accessed through a REST service and shows the desired velocity since it is generated and ingested in real-time
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data

Dataset 3 Laboratory testing data	
Metadata/Description	The results of the chemicals monitoring programs collected from 33 countries. The laboratory testing data are processed and enriched using the BigDataGrapes software stack.
Provider	Agroknow
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 117 GB of data.
Velocity	The provided dataset is accessed through a REST service and shows the desired velocity since it is generated and ingested in real-time
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data

Dataset 4 Food businesses data	
Metadata/Description	The dataset includes the information for 400.000 food businesses. It provides information about the location, alternative names, products and subsidiaries.
Provider	Agroknow
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 5 GB of data.
Velocity	The provided dataset is accessed through a REST service and shows the desired velocity since it is generated and ingested in real-time
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data

Dataset 5 Inspection data	
Metadata/Description	The dataset includes the results of 227.500 inspections that are conducted by the National Authorities to food businesses. The dataset provides information about the facility that was inspected, the findings, products, date and location.
Provider	Agroknow
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 2.4 GB of data.
Velocity	The provided dataset is accessed through a REST service and shows the desired velocity since it is generated and ingested in real-time
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data

Results

The big data software components were used in TheFSM to collect and process data types such as food companies’ information, inspections information, certification information, trade information and production information. The datasets (see tables above) produced in the context of the BigDataGrapes project were used in TheFSM to create an evaluation dashboard for suppliers and to estimate risk for each supplier. In addition to this, the prediction components will be used to estimate the risk of each supplier using different data types such as recalls, border rejections, lab data, inspections, certificate, trade and production information.

7.3 LIAISON WITH IOF2020

Use Case

The liaison goal was to help better decision making by interacting with a dedicate use case of the IOF project (<https://www.iof2020.eu/>). The goal of the IOF2020 fruit trial was the effective use of IoT technologies at a big scale. The fruit trial focused on how IoT technology can improve each step in the production process by collecting different data types such as sensor data (from weather stations, multispectral/thermal cameras, stem water potential, light micro-climate measures, fruitful indexes), monitoring data and data from early warning systems that are used to control pests/diseases (e.g. variable rate spraying, selective harvesting). To address the challenge of collecting, processing and linking this highly heterogenous data, the project used software components that were developed in the context of BigDataGrapes. Such components were already used in the BigDataGrapes project for collecting data from the vineyards and processing stages of the grape supply chain and identifying correlations.

Software stack components shared

The software components that were used by IOF2020 are the following

- Knowledge classification component
- Time Series data component
- Big data indexing component based on Elasticsearch
- Correlation component

Data shared

Dataset 1 Soil electrical conductivity data	
Metadata/Description	Soil electrical conductivity data at 0.5 and 1.0 m depth (ms/m) for 3 fields in Greece.
Provider	Agriculture University of Athens

Volume	1 MB
Velocity	A dump of the dataset was provided for a specific period.
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data

Dataset 2	Reflectance information
Metadata/Description	Reflectance information from plant canopies and classic spectral vegetative index data for 3 fields in Greece.
Provider	Agriculture University of Athens
Volume	2.5 MB
Velocity	A dump of the dataset was provided for a specific period.
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data

Results

The liaison specifically focused on the production of the table grapes, exploring how all the data collected in the different stages and by different systems can be interconnected (linked) and processed in order to identified correlations which can help in improving the quality and the yield.

7.4 LIAISON WITH AGINFRA+

Use Case

agINFRA+ developed a research data e-infrastructure that facilitates the development of innovative data- and computing-intensive applications for different research communities of the agri-food sector. One of the communities that agINFRA+ supports with its services is the community that focuses on the development of the predictive models for food safety. The goal of the use case was to exchange data but also software components with the agINFRA+ project in order to help the development of innovative services for the food safety research community.

Software stack components shared

The software components that were used by agINFRA+ are the following

- Web scraping component for the collection of research publications from different research repositories
- Knowledge classification component for the enrichment of the collected data with hazards and products terms of semantic vocabularies
- Big data indexing Elasticsearch component for indexing of millions of research publications

Data shared

Dataset 1	Food recalls due to biological hazards in foods
Metadata/Description	A dataset that includes food recalls due to the biological hazards that were reported by the National Authorities all around the worlds from 1981 until 2019. The dataset includes also the numerical results of the identified hazard.
Provider	Agroknow
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 0.4 GB of data.
Velocity	The provided dataset is accessed through a REST service and shows the desired velocity since it is generated and ingested in real-time
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data

Dataset 2		Border rejections due to biological hazards in foods
Metadata/Description	A dataset that includes food border rejections due to the biological hazards that were reported by the National Authorities all around the worlds from 1981 until 2019. The dataset includes also the numerical results of the identified biological hazard.	
Provider	Agroknow	
Volume	In terms of volume this dataset has a total size of 0.4 GB of data.	
Velocity	The provided dataset is accessed through a REST service and shows the desired velocity since it is generated and ingested in real-time	
Variety	In terms of variety the provided dataset shows one type of data	

Results

The software components for the data collection, data enrichment and data indexing were used by the agINFRA+ project to collect millions of research publications about food safety risks. The two (2) datasets of the biological hazards were used by the food safety research community for the development of the predictive microbial computational models.

ANNEX A: DISSEMINATION MATERIAL

Figure 46: BigDataGrapes Project Poster Roll-up

Figure 47: BigDataGrapes Brochure for demonstrating the BigDataGrapes vision towards supporting the European grapevine-powered industry [1st page]

SUPPORTING THE EUROPEAN GRAPEVINE-POWERED INDUSTRY

Big Data Grapes is an ICT project that aims to enhance the wine and natural cosmetics industries.

We improve the competitive positioning of companies in the European IT sector that are serving companies and organisations with software applications, such as:

Farm management and precision agriculture systems for vineyards

Food risk assessment monitoring and prediction systems for companies in the food sector.

Quality control and compliance software for companies in the beauty and cosmetics sector.

Figure 48: BigDataGrapes Brochure for demonstrating the BigDataGrapes vision towards supporting the European grapevine-powered industry [2nd page]

THE BIGGER VISION

Big Data Grapes aims to help European companies in the wine and natural cosmetics industries become more competitive in the international markets.

Targeting technology challenges of the grapevine-powered data economy as its business problems and decisions **requires processing, analysis and visualisation of data with rapidly increasing volume, velocity and variety: satellite and weather data, environmental and geological data, phenotypic and genetic plant data, food supply chain data, economic and financial data and more.**

It therefore makes a **perfectly suitable cross-sector and cross-country combination of industries** that are of **high European significance and value.**

TARGET GROUPS

WINE PRODUCERS, BOTTLERS & DISTRIBUTORS

PRODUCERS & PACKAGERS OF FOOD & WINE PRODUCTS

NATURAL COSMETIC COMPANIES

QA & FS AND R&D EXPERTS IN FOOD & WINE SECTOR

Figure 49: BigDataGrapes Brochure for demonstrating the BigDataGrapes vision towards supporting the European grapevine-powered industry [3rd page]

PILOTS & LEADERS

<p style="font-size: 2em; color: #008000; font-weight: bold;">01</p> </p> <p>Improve the quality of table & wine grapes</p>	
<p style="font-size: 2em; color: #008000; font-weight: bold;">02</p> </p> <p>Improve the quality of wine and support the efficient management of the vineyard</p>	
<p style="font-size: 2em; color: #008000; font-weight: bold;">03</p> </p> <p>Improve the ability to take quick and informed decisions through farm management systems</p>	
<p style="font-size: 2em; color: #008000; font-weight: bold;">04</p> </p> <p>Correlate different quality biomarkers for producing better grape extracts used for natural cosmetics</p>	
<p style="font-size: 2em; color: #008000; font-weight: bold;">05</p> </p> <p>Enhance the current digital solution with new modules that will address further needs of the grape and wine supply chain</p>	

Figure 50: BigDataGrapes Brochure for demonstrating the BigDataGrapes vision towards supporting the European grapevine-powered industry [4rd page]

PROJECT PARTNERS

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SYMBEOSIS

GEOCLEDIAN

Figure 51: BigDataGrapes Brochure for demonstrating the BigDataGrapes vision towards supporting the European grapevine-powered industry [5th page]

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 780751

Figure 52: BigDataGrapes Brochure for demonstrating the BigDataGrapes vision towards supporting the European grapevine-powered industry [6th page]

ANNEX B: LIST OF ENGAGED PROJECTS

In this list are presented all the projects that we had indirect cooperation by presenting BigDataGrapes objectives and outcomes in events we participated in.

Number	Framework/ Programme	Title	Call
1	H2020	Healthy crop, Healthy environment, Healthy finances ... through Optimization	H2020-SMEINST-2-2014
2	H2020	Ecosystem Approach to making Space for Aquaculture	H2020-SFS-2014-2
3	H2020	Advanced Tools and Research Strategies for Parasite Control in European farmed fish	H2020-SFS-2014-2
4	H2020	Eco-efficient high-yield production of antioxidant compounds from microalgae	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
5	H2020	Drone-based integrated monitoring system for early detection of crop pathology and pest control in high tech greenhouse agriculture.	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
6	H2020	Development and demonstration of an innovative FT-NIR-based system for food content analysis	H2020-SMEINST-2-2015
7	H2020	Real time and online monitoring of the debittering stage in the table olive processing	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
8	H2020	Vegetable ozone therapy for the defense of greenhouse crops	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
9	H2020	Functional ingredient from fermented vegetable waste streams to diminish the use of antibiotics in pig husbandry	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
10	H2020	Bio-pesticide from a strain of Bacillus licheniformis for the control of major pests in different cultures	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
11	H2020	Development and market launch of novel technology for production of nutritionally complete plant proteins called FIDOs - “Functional (Protein) Isolates Derived from Oilseeds”.	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
12	H2020	Actiwhey based microencapsulation solution for sustainable food manufacturing	H2020-SMEINST-2-2015
13	H2020	BLUE HEALTH	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015

14	H2020	Genetic markers assisted selection for improvement of swine breeding productivity.	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
15	H2020	RLTProFood - Remote Lighting Technology for processing and production of food	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
16	H2020	An integrated high throughput robot and a new multi-rootstock grafting technology to improve plant/crop yield	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
17	H2020	Food treatment process based on high voltage nanopulsed electric discharges in liquid phase	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
18	H2020	A Sustainable Soil Solution: Scaling up Novihum, an innovation to convert bad soil into better, make brown coal clean and barren land green, and profitably advance food security in Europe and beyond	H2020-SMEINST-2-2015
19	H2020	Sustainable agricultural eco-system: business and technological solution for eco-conscious vegetable cultivation using on-site produced algae fertilizer	H2020-SMEINST-2-2014
20	H2020	Design of an agricultural greenhouse for intensive growing of microalgae in fresh / sea water with a syngas production plant and organic farming of chickens and pigs outdoors.	H2020-SMEINST-2-2015
21	H2020	Validation and market uptake of a natural disinfection whey-based formula for whole and fresh-cut fruits and vegetables	H2020-SMEINST-2-2014
22	H2020	Antiseptic kaolin-silver complex for substituting the use of sulfites in winemaking	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
23	H2020	Natural Food formulation for the prevention and treatment the Obesity and Metabolic syndrome obtained with herbal extracts	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
24	H2020	Proposal for innovative and sustainable polyculture greenhouse system Polydome	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
25	H2020	Solar Energy for Food Industry	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
26	H2020	Environmental friendly fungicide based on new endophytic Biological Control Agent Trichoderma asperellum strain T18	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
27	H2020	Rapid on-site detection of Mycotoxin in wheat	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
28	H2020	Sales and production acceleration of EU saffron	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015

		through an innovative cultivation and crop system that allows European producers to increase eco-efficiency, production and processing	
29	H2020	Innovative active-uptake foliar nutrition technology capable of significantly reducing pesticide rates	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
30	H2020	DEMOstrators of micro waves efficiency for agrifood industry	H2020-SMEINST-2-2014
31	H2020	Innovative highly concentrated Omega 3 food supplement	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
32	H2020	Food Retail Industry Supply Chain Optimization (FRISCO): Food Discount Intelligence to Reduce Food Waste through the implementation of the FoodLoop Platform	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
33	H2020	Jellyfish Barge - A floating greenhouse	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
34	H2020	BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE SERVICE FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF CROPS BASED ON CLOUD AND BIG DATA	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
35	H2020	Low-energy leak-proof double seat control valve based on a water hydraulic actuator system	H2020-SMEINST-2-2014
36	H2020	Fodder for for HEALTHier animals and improved liveSTOCK production	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
37	H2020	ECO-INNOVATE-AQUACULTURE-SYSTEM	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
38	H2020	UltraCLEAN thermoforming equipment for ultraclean PACKaging of foods, and in-situ production of aseptic trays.	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
39	H2020	UV cleaning for beverage tanks eliminating the need for water and chemicals	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
40	H2020	HISPOB- High Speed Potato Breeding: securing healthy food for the future	H2020-SMEINST-2-2014
41	H2020	Novel Ozone and Thermal Shock Conservation Process for Vegetables	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
42	H2020	SUstainabLe Tunnel Agriculture with light cascade techNology	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
43	H2020	Strawberry Processing Machine	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
44	H2020	A novel vision based orchard system to maximize fruit	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014

		tree yields and Class 1 quality by 20% while reducing waste by 50%	
45	H2020	Non-thermal treatment to delay the onset of honey crystallization	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
46	H2020	AUTOMATIC VERTICAL SCANNER FOR DETERMING LEAN DISTRIBUTION IN ANIMAL CARCASSES (AVSCAN)	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
47	H2020	Eco-innovative housing solution for efficient production of slaughterpigs with limited environmental impact.	H2020-SMEINST-2-2014
48	H2020	Demonstration of a cloud-based precision farming management system for a sustainable and intensive agriculture to secure long-term food supply in Europe	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
49	H2020	NEW GENERATION OF HIGH VALUE-ADDED ANTIOXIDANT FOOD INGREDIENTS FOR THE GOURMET CUISINE	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
50	H2020	MicroLAB lab-on-a-cartridge, a disruptive concept. Towards an innovative solution for food safety	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
51	H2020	Subsustainable and efficient food processing and cooking system	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
52	H2020	Transitioning to microalgae as a sustainable, high-quality large-scale food source through launching the first daily drink containing spirulina	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
53	H2020	FOOD SAFETY CONTROLS FOR ALL	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
54	H2020	Camelina Oil for Sustainable Salmon Aquafeed	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
55	H2020	A truly-rapid, one-minute test system for the dairy industry to assess raw milk quality, detect sub-clinical mastitis and monitor udder health, reducing antibiotic usage and environmental impact	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
56	H2020	An innovative fruit ripeness checker, to offer non-destructive testing in order to ensure resource efficient fruit processing - Ripesense	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
57	H2020	PlotLab - Plot combines with integrated lab equipment for lean breeding	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
58	H2020	Fermentation processes for functional foods from RAPeseed, Sunflower and Other EU matrices Devoted	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014

		to Young animals.Zero-miles model boosting safety and competitiveness of livestock sector	
59	H2020	Antibiotics reduction with early mastitis pathogens detection for @ point of animal care usages	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
60	H2020	Colour-code labelling for continuous monitoring of quality and safety of packed chicken meat	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
61	H2020	BeadCAP-DNA: 30-minute on-site DNA test kit	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
62	H2020	NATURHEALTH FOOD: NEW GENERATION OF NATURAL BIOPRESERVATIVE SUBSTITUTE OF CURRENT E-NUMBERS IN FOOD PRODUCTS	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
63	H2020	Improved machine vision for guidance of optical system for cost-effective and environmentally safe in-situ removal of ectoparasites from farmed fish	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
64	H2020	Towards a long-term Africa-EU partnership to raise sustainable food and nutrition security in Africa	H2020-SFS-2014-1
65	H2020	High Pressure Processing (HPP) equipment for large beverage productions	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
66	H2020	Increasing grain quality through advanced oxidation treatment during storage	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
67	H2020	Electrochemical Oxidation in the Recirculating Aquaculture Systems Industry	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
68	H2020	Biopolus Aero Green - Feasibility Study	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
69	H2020	New eco-efficient and healthy professional espresso coffee machine	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
70	H2020	Monitoring Meat Texture To Optimize Slicing Yield And Reduce Wasted Meat In High-Speed Slicing Lines	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
71	H2020	EU-CHINA Lever for IPM Demonstration	H2020-SFS-2014-2
72	H2020	Faster Upcoming Technology Uptake Relevant for the Environment in FOODs Drying	H2020-SFS-2014-2
73	H2020	Traditional tomato varieties and cultural practices: a case for agricultural diversification with impact on food security and health of European population	H2020-SFS-2014-2
74	H2020	Effective Management of Pests and Harmful Alien Species - Integrated Solutions	H2020-SFS-2014-2

75	H2020	Novel biocontrol agents for insect pests from neuroendocrinology	H2020-SFS-2014-2
76	H2020	Interactive Soil Quality Assessment in Europe and China for Agricultural Productivity and Environmental Resilience	H2020-SFS-2014-2
77	H2020	Process integration for rapid implementation of sustainable innovative food processing	H2020-SFS-2014-2
78	H2020	Sustainable finance for sustainable agriculture and fisheries	H2020-SFS-2014-2
79	H2020	Development of high quality food protein through sustainable production and processing	H2020-SFS-2014-2
90	H2020	Deployment of high pressure and temperature food processing for sustainable, safe and nutritious foods with fresh-like quality	H2020-SFS-2014-2
91	H2020	Integration of PEF in food processing for improving food quality, safety and competitiveness	H2020-SFS-2014-2
92	H2020	DIVERSITY OF LOCAL PIG BREEDS AND PRODUCTION SYSTEMS FOR HIGH QUALITY TRADITIONAL PRODUCTS AND SUSTAINABLE PORK CHAINS	H2020-SFS-2014-2
99	H2020	PARAGONE: vaccines for animal parasites	H2020-SFS-2014-2
94	H2020	Waste reduction and quality improvement of fruits and vegetables via an innovative and energy-efficient humidification/disinfection technology	H2020-SFS-2014-2
95	H2020	LAND Management: Assessment, Research, Knowledge base	H2020-SFS-2014-2
96	H2020	Science, Technology, and Society Initiative to minimize Unwanted Catches in European Fisheries	H2020-SFS-2014-2
97	H2020	Ecofriendly PROcessing System for the full exploitation of the OLIVE health potential in products of added value	H2020-SFS-2014-2
98	H2020	Metrics, Models and Foresight for European Sustainable Food and Nutrition Security	H2020-SFS-2014-2
100	H2020	Embedding crop diversity and networking for local high quality food systems	H2020-SFS-2014-2
101	H2020	Farming Tools for external nutrient Inputs and water	H2020-SFS-2014-2

		Management	
102	H2020	Adapting the feed, the animal and the feeding techniques to improve the efficiency and sustainability of monogastric livestock production systems	H2020-SFS-2014-2
103	H2020	Strengthening Animal Production and Health through the Immune Response	H2020-SFS-2014-2
104	H2020	DiscardLess – Strategies for the gradual elimination of discards in European fisheries	H2020-SFS-2014-2
105	H2020	EuroMix	H2020-SFS-2014-2
106	H2020	Creating links to speed-up innovation in the bio economy	H2020-ISIB-2014-1
107	H2020	PROViding smart DELivery of public goods by EU agriculture and forestry	H2020-ISIB-2014-2
108	H2020	FACCE-Evolve - Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change Coordination and Support Action 2	H2020-ISIB-2014-1
109	H2020	Professional support to the uptake of bioeconomy RD results towards market, further research and policy for a more competitive European bioeconomy	H2020-ISIB-2014-1
110	H2020	Network for the exchange and transfer of innovative knowledge between European wine-growing regions to increase the productivity and sustainability of the sector	H2020-ISIB-2014-1
111	H2020	Sustainable and Resilient agriculture for food and non-food systems	H2020-ISIB-2014-1
112	H2020	Platform of bioeconomy ERA-NET Actions	H2020-ISIB-2014-1
113	H2020	Practice-led innovation supported by science and market-driven actors in the laying hen and other livestock sectors	H2020-ISIB-2014-1
114	H2020	CommBeBiz - Communicating and Bridging BioEconomy Research to Business	H2020-ISIB-2014-1
115	H2020	Forum for Bio-Based Innovation in Public Procurement	H2020-ISIB-2014-1
116	H2020	Space for Agricultural Innovation	H2020-ISIB-2014-1
117	H2020	Cooperation between NCPs for Horizon 2020 Societal Challenge 2 on “Food security, Sustainable Agriculture, Marine and Maritime Research and the Bioeconomy”	H2020-ISIB-2014-1

		and the Key Enabling Technology (
118	H2020	Promoting stakeholder engagement and public awareness for a participative governance of the European bioeconomy	H2020-ISIB-2014-1
119	H2020	Organic Knowledge Network Arable	H2020-ISIB-2014-1
120	H2020	Camelina & crambe Oil crops as Sources for Medium-chain Oils for Specialty oleochemicals	H2020-ISIB-2014-2
121	H2020	Public Ecosystem Goods And Services from land management - Unlocking the Synergies	H2020-ISIB-2014-2
122	H2020	Distributed, integrated and harmonised forest information for bioeconomy outlooks	H2020-ISIB-2014-2
123	H2020	Sea Change	H2020-BG-2014-1
124	H2020	Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance Support Action	H2020-BG-2014-1
125	H2020	Sustainable oceans : our collective responsibility, our common interest. Building on real-life knowledge knowledge systems for developing interactive and mutual learning media	H2020-BG-2014-1
126	H2020	Optimizing and Enhancing the Integrated Atlantic Ocean Observing System	H2020-BG-2014-2
127	H2020	Industrial Applications of Marine Enzymes: Innovative screening and expression platforms to discover and use the functional protein diversity from the sea	H2020-BG-2014-2
128	H2020	Nematodes as the world first pathogen free, ready-to-use and sustainable live feed for larval aquaculture industry	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
129	H2020	Open Ocean Fish farms	H2020-SMEINST-2-2015
130	H2020	Continual Acoustic Based Multifunctional Cage Mounted Fish estimator Deigned To Reduce Feed Waste, Fish Mortality, and Predator and Fish Escape Control	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
131	H2020	Reference standards for a specific, reliable and early detection of the marine toxins that causes ciguatera disease	H2020-SMEINST-1-2015
132	H2020	A replacement of the sub-optimal live feeds used at hatcheries today with a new cryopreserved live diet for	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014

		the improved and efficient production of juveniles in marine aquaculture	
133	H2020	Connecting Science with Society	H2020-BG-2014-1
134	H2020	Development of a Novel, Intelligent Down the Hole Disconnect Tool	H2020-SMEINST-2-2014
135	H2020	Slimming Microalgae Extract : Development of a new highly effective microalgae-based slimming ingredient for nutraceutical applications	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
136	H2020	Developing a multispectral volume scattering meter for measuring the optical properties of sea and ocean water	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
137	H2020	Remote Controllable Devices	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
138	H2020	Boost BLUE economy through market uptake an innovative seaweed bioextract for IODINE fortification	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
139	H2020	Sonar Integrated Advanced Navigation	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
140	H2020	Designing waves for the people	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
141	H2020	Coastal and shallow-water monitoring through innovative low-cost technologies for blue growth in the Mediterranean	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
142	H2020	The untapped potential of omega-3; from fish oil to healthy bowels	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
143	H2020	Marine Investment for the Blue Economy	H2020-BG-2014-1
144	H2020	Sea-More-Yield: A Blue Biotechnology Solution for the Reduction of Pod Shatter in Bio-Oil Producing Crops	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
145	H2020	COLUMBUS - Monitoring, Managing and Transferring Marine and Maritime Knowledge for Sustainable Blue Growth	H2020-BG-2014-1
146	H2020	Floating Offshore Photovoltaic systems	H2020-SMEINST-1-2014
147	H2020	Strategic Use of Competitiveness towards Consolidating the Economic Sustainability of the European Seafood sector	H2020-BG-2014-2
148	H2020	Bringing together Research and Industry for the Development of Glider Environmental Services	H2020-BG-2014-2
149	H2020	NOVEL, SUSTAINABLE MARINE BIO-SURFACTANT /	H2020-BG-2014-2

		BIO-EMULSIFIERS FOR COMMERCIAL EXPLOITATION	
150	H2020	Novel marine biomolecules against biofilm. Application to medical devices.	H2020-BG-2014-2
151	H2020	Tools And Strategies to access to original bioactive compounds from Cultivation of MARine invertebrates and associated symbionts	H2020-BG-2014-2
152	H2020	Sensors for Large scale Hydrodynamic Imaging of ocean floor	H2020-BG-2014-2
153	H2020	Dexterous ROV: effective dexterous ROV operations in presence of communication latencies.	H2020-BG-2014-2
154	H2020	Developing Innovative Market Orientated Prediction Toolbox to Strengthen the Economic Sustainability and Competitiveness of European Seafood on Local and Global markets	H2020-BG-2014-2
155	H2020	Underwater Time Of Flight Image Acquisition system	H2020-BG-2014-2
156	H2020	Processing Underutilised Low value sugarbeet Pulp into VALUE added products (PULP2VALUE)	H2020-BBI-PPP-2014-1
157	H2020	ValChem - Value added Chemical building blocks and lignin from wood	H2020-BBI-PPP-2014-1
158	H2020	Combined Ultrasonic and Enzyme treatment of Lignocellulosic Feedstock as Substrate for Sugar Based Biotechnological Applications	H2020-BBI-PPP-2014-1
160	H2020	Flagship demonstration of an integrated biorefinery for dry crops sustainable exploitation towards biobased materials production	H2020-BBI-PPP-2014-1
161	H2020	PROcesses for Value added fibres by Innovative Deep Eutectic Solvents	H2020-BBI-PPP-2014-1
162	H2020	Protein Mining of Cereal side-streams Exploring Novel Technological Concepts	H2020-BBI-PPP-2014-1
163	H2020	Smart Technologies for the Conversion of Industrial Lignins into Sustainable Materials	H2020-BBI-PPP-2014-1
164	H2020	Nutrient recovery from biobased Waste for Fertilizer production	H2020-BBI-PPP-2014-1
165	H2020	Cost effective lignin-based carbon fibres for innovative light-weight applications	H2020-BBI-PPP-2014-1

ANNEX C: ANALYSIS OF DISSEMINATION ACTIONS IN DIGITAL CHANNELS

In the following tables we are analyzing all the completed activities for high-dissemination through: LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube respectively. For every digital channel, specifically targeted to stakeholders, actions took place, increasing the awareness and creating successfully ongoing buzz around both our offering and our brand promise.

Publish Date	Post message / text	Post URL
2019		
3/6/2019	"Our partner AUA keeps on the data collection. In this case, AUA tool pictures during the drone data collection and some more when using their quad bike for canopy sensing. Two drones equipped with a multispectral and a thermal camera were used to collect aerial imagery data. #IoT #BigDataGrapes #viticulture #bigdata #drones	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_iot-bigdatagrapes-viticulture-activity-6596065468174344194-EdiB/
5/7/2019	BigDataGrapes 4th Project Meeting in Athens Pilot leaders have presented how their collected data can be collaborated with the developed software tools. #OpenData #BigData	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_big-data-grapes-on-twitter-activity-6596066277935198208-k9sf/
12/8/2019	AUA is collecting data again! Soil sampling collection and vines scanning to record vegetation indexes... #bigdatagrapes #h2020 #agriculture #bigdata	https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/bigdat agrapeseu/
8/11/2019	AGRITECHNICA: The world's largest Agriculture & Technology trade fair is taking place in Hannover Germany this week, November 10-16 and our project partner Geocledian GmbH has a stand (D51 in hall P11) to present their products & the aims of our project. Visit us if you would like to learn about remote sensing for agriculture & the BigDataGrapes project. It would be great to meet you there! #opendata #bigdata #satellite #remotesensing #technology #visitus	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_opendata-bigdata-satellite-activity-6600278909567160320-5NWC/
14/8/2019	During the previous week, Florian Schlenz, our partner from Geocledian GmbH participated at #agritechnica2019 & had the opportunity to communicate the outcomes of BigDataGrapes to many companies that are dealing with grapevine data from Greece, France & Italy. #OpenData #BigData #satellite #remotesensing #DataAnalytics	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_agritechnica2019-opendata-bigdata-activity-6602099904653463552-kazj/
29/11/2019	Only one week left for applying to the Data Science challenge! Which SME is going to win the €10,000 prize? Secure your	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_call-to-european-data-

	participation and apply now here: https://bit.ly/33BWFw5 #bigdata #OpenData #agriculture	science-startups-who-activity-6606188269862551552-F4zt/
2020		
27/2/2020	This week we're in #Seattle to present how #BigData technologies can foster #foodsafety across the supply chain and ensure that consumers have access to safe food. #gfsi2020	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_seattle-bigdata-foodsafety-activity-6638919315686989824-Z2tb/
5/3/2020	Why do our partners from INRAE count grapevine leaves? Learn how #machinelearning and #deeplearning techniques contribute to moving one step closer to precision viticulture through #BigDataGrapes EU Science, Research and Innovation https://lnkd.in/dzZJdz	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_machinelearning-deeplearning-bigdatagrapes-activity-6641267942396841984-TnJx/
19/3/2020	Throwback to February 2020 and #ISESS2020 organized by Wageningen Environmental Research WDCC where Ioanna Polychronou from Agroknow showcased the capabilities of the project's #bigdata experimentation platform. Full presentation available here: https://lnkd.in/dm49AqR	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_issess2020-bigdata-activity-6649003513735073793-SW-j/
8/5/2020	Digitalization in French vineyards is a reality - and especially during the times of social distancing. Farm robots can act as a major data collection source during the main phenological stages of the vine.	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_un-nouvel-arrivant-au-domaine-des-vallettes-activity-6662966403617824768-wyxO/
20/5/2020	Celebrating #WorldBeeDay today, and we dig into our natural cosmetics pilot of Symbeeosis S.A., where bee and grapevine products blend giving an excellent raw material for cosmetics and pharma industries. Read more on how we are assessing the biological efficacy of grapevine by-products using #bigdata and how we are going to predict which area would supply grape leaves of the best quality for natural cosmetics production. https://lnkd.in/dVDmWsQ	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_worldbeeday-bigdata-activity-6668801211531051008-gebZ/
26/5/2020	How does #artificialintelligence support a multitude of applications for wine and vine? Our colleagues Pascal Neveu and Coraline Damasio from INRAE, France describe the way that the BigDataGrapes project aims to provide answers on the influence of climatic effects or the winemaking process on the aromatic composition of wine. Read more> https://lnkd.in/dFSnHb8	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_artificialintelligence-activity-6670948032265105408-g5bU/

29/5/2020	<p>This week our colleague Diego Rojo Garcia from KU Leuven presented at the virtual session of #EuroVis2020 their approach to designing a novel system for correlation visualization, GaCoVi. GaCoVi is designed to put domain experts in the loop of feature selection for #regressionmodels in scenarios where transparency of the #machinelearning systems are crucial. Learn more on how it helps viticulture and vinification domain experts: https://lnkd.in/eKctGhM #datascience #datavisualization</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_ev-short-papers-3-representation-perception-activity-6672050320748666880-oLIs/</p>
1/6/2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to increase productivity and grape quality? • How to reduce the use of emergency irrigation? • How to detect the moment where the stress level is critical for the plant? • Which part of the vineyard does really need irrigation? <p>Four critical business questions that we answer in real-life business cases of the BigDataGrapes project. Read more on the case of ABACO Farmer https://lnkd.in/dEPKD2Q</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_how-to-increase-productivity-and-grape-activity-6673144676230418432-oKjC/</p>
9/6/2020	<p>The first dataset of the forthcoming 2020 harvest is ready! The team of Smart Farming Technology Group - Agricultural University of Athens did the first flights over the slopes of Korinthia, Greece and fueled the #bigdataplatform with fresh data! More on the video below!</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_h2020-bigdatagrapes-project-activity-6676374354739113985-Hb_r/</p>
15/6/2020	<p>Demystifying “terroir” Maritina Stavrakaki from the Agricultural University of Athens explains the critical questions that the researchers and data scientists of BigDataGrapes project will answer in the Table and Wine Grapes Pilot.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Can we predict grape yield & correlate it with grape quality? ▪ Are different parts of our vineyard characterized by different grape quality? ▪ How does zoning contribute to efficient vineyard management? <p>Read more on: http://bigdatagrapes.eu/node/111</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_table-and-wine-grapes-pilot-grapevine-responses-activity-6678208786156527616-1e1z/</p>
25/6/2020	<p>This is how vintage 2020 looks in Champagne vines - all phenological stages at once. Soon we will be able to see the data behind them!</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_la-naissance-du-mill%C3%A9sime-2020-la-magie-activity-6679649880476016640-O5xv/</p>

26/6/2020	<p>Can we see from space if a vineyard needs water? Florian Schlenz from Geocledian GmbH presents how the #farmmanagement pilot provides answers to fundamental farming questions with #bigdata and water balance modeling. Thanks to #copernicus earth observation datasets we get useful insights on vegetation status and the vegetation water content in the vineyard. Read more on https://lnkd.in/dsV8NfN</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_can-we-see-from-space-if-a-vineyard-needs-activity-6682184956438966272-7_Ac/</p>
30/6/2020	<p>What is #semantic data linking, and how are we leveraging domain-specific ontologies for advancing viticultural research and producing top quality wines? Coraline Damasio and Arnaud CHARLEROY from INRAE explain how we deal with multidimensional data representation ranging from viticulture to winemaking https://lnkd.in/dt6GzKJ</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_connecting-data-in-an-intelligent-way-a-activity-6683754993343840256-Rwft/</p>
15/7/2020	<p>At BigDataGrapes we are passionate about working with end-users to determine their pain points and create a solution that fits their real needs. Have a look at some snippets from our hands-on evaluation session, kindly hosted by INRA French National Institute for Agricultural Research. http://bigdatagrapes.eu</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_at-bigdatagrapes-we-are-passionate-about-activity-6689084134561783808-NJRz/</p>
11/9/2020	<p>A journey from #vine to #wine in pictures. Coraline Damasio and Arnaud CHARLEROY from INRAE, visited The “Cave Coopérative Les Trois Grappes” to understand better the viticulture part and the “Vignerons de la Vicomté” for #bottling and #winetasting.</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_a-journey-from-vine-to-wine-in-pictures-activity-6711169259034173440-6H3l/</p>
14/10/2020	<p>Agroknow, coordinator of the BigDataGrapes project, asked food industry experts “What is your experience with predictive analytics?” Almost 45% said that they have heard and read a lot about predictive analytics, but they haven’t tried it yet. So, can we really prevent food fraud and safety incidents from happening? Just give it a try! #artificialintelligence #ai #predictiveanalytics #foodindustry #foodsafety #bigdata</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_can-we-really-prevent-food-fraud-and-safety-activity-6722168607893262336-OLUb/</p>
9/11/2020	<p>The 6th (and final) Project Meeting of the BigDataGrapes project has been successfully completed, with the participation of 9 partners from 6 European countries. The consortium is working systematically in order to present to the global market the innovative results for the Grapevine-powered industries.</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_bigdatagrapes-6th-project-meeting-4-5-november-activity-6731598465299734528-nPQF/</p>

29/11/2020	A beautiful photo from BigDataGrapes' pilot site for #winemaking production. Thank you Aikaterini Kasimati.	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_h2020-bigdatagrapes-project-activity-6747131966929293312-wG6A/
22/12/2020	<p>Are you curious about how food safety predictive analytics should work to ensure that they deliver reliable predictions to support business-critical decisions?</p> <p>We are delighted to present you, our first (intro) video from a short video series addressing the critical questions on this topic. #foodsafety #predictiveanalytics</p> <p>Read more on: https://lnkd.in/ex_UDbR</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_a-series-of-videos-explaining-food-safety-activity-6747133837144330241-pUCb/
23/12/2020	<p>Are you interested in how you can solve the Food Safety intelligence equation for more effective predictive analytics?</p> <p>BigDataGrapes' Episode 1: "The food risk prevention question to drive effective predictive analytics", is released now, providing you all the must-information for a better-handling of predictive analytics. #foodsafety #predictiveanalytics</p> <p>Check it out!</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_episode-1-the-food-risk-prevention-question-activity-6747548634138648576-BDiZ/
2021		
5/1/2021	<p>Promise and Perils of Artificial Intelligence and Predictive Analytics in the food supply chain. Friday, January 15th, 2021, 6:00 – 7:30pm (EET) / 11.00 – 12.30 (EST).</p> <p>As an initiative of the BigDataGrapes project (http://bigdatagrapes.eu), Agroknow is organizing a virtual panel discussion on “Predictive Analytics for the Food Supply Chain” to be moderated by Dr. Wietske Van Osch.</p> <p>Five speakers representing five leading Food Safety Technology Companies will provide insights and constructive knowledge about the Promise and Perils of AI and Predictive Analytics in the food supply chain.</p> <p>You will learn about: What is Predictive Analytics and which problems can this technology help solve? What do customers require in terms of predictions? Which are the critical business questions they bring forward? What is the current offering of tech companies in terms of predictions? What is still missing?</p> <p>Panelists: James Flynn, Andrew Harrison, Michael Gibbons, Brendan Ring, Giannis (John) Stoitsis</p> <p>#predictiveanalytics #bigdata #ai</p> <p>BOOK YOUR SEAT HERE:</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/dSxpKhh</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_predictive-analytics-for-the-food-supply-activity-6752947764314828800-YmeM/

<p>8/1/2021</p>	<p>Fascinated with predictive analytics? Wonder how to select the right data? Is it possible to predict with high confidence, how many food safety incidents we are going to have for each ingredient category in 2020?</p> <p>Then don't miss out the new short video series' episode by BigDataGrapes project, where Giannis (John) Stoitsis, CTO, and partner at Agroknow (Coordinator partner of the BigDataGrapes project), addresses the previous and even more of your questiones!</p> <p>#foodsafety #predictiveanalytics</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_episode-2-how-to-select-the-right-data-activity-6753283682385092608-CemY/</p>
<p>21/1/2021</p>	<p>Confused about choosing the right food risk prediction algorithm to make the most of a predictive analytics solution? In this episode of our mini video series, Giannis (John) Stoitsis, CTO, and partner at Agroknow (Coordinator partner of the BigDataGrapes project), explains how we can find and parameterize the algorithm that will work appropriately for a specific problem and data combination. #foodsafety #predictiveanalytics</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_episode-3-how-to-select-the-right-food-activity-6757953213409898496-Alyt/</p>
<p>21/1/2021</p>	<p>Fascinated by the applications of AI technology in the food sector? Here is a chance you can't miss!</p> <p>As an initiative of the BigDataGrapes project (http://bigdatagrapes.eu), KU Leuven and Agroknow are organizing a webinar on: "Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention: Towards visually appealing & highly interactive predictions".</p> <p>The webinar will provide Insights and constructive knowledge of the business challenges for the food industry as well as the scientific challenges for UX researchers when talking about predictive analytics, and how to overcome them.</p> <p>The main topics we are going to discuss are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · From a business question to a risk dashboard: the food safety intelligence equation · Designing an appealing, interactive & trustful prediction dashboard: visualization components & technologies · A Food Risk Prediction Dashboard example and how it works <p>The webinar will be held on Friday, January 22nd, 2021, 4:00 – 5:30pm (CET) / 10.00 – 11.30am (EST) via Zoom (you will receive the link once you fill in the registration form below).</p> <p>Register here to receive the broadcast link via email.</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdatagrapeseu_webinar-on-predictive-analytics-for-food-activity-6757968313021714432-nPCm/</p>

<p>27/1/2021</p>	<p>Are you searching for the right prediction metrics to measure if your prediction algorithm is working properly? This and more answers you can find them on 4th episode of the BigDataGrapes short video series, where Giannis (John) Stoitsis, CTO and partner at Agroknow (Coordinator partner of the BigDataGrapes project), presents the right prediction metrics that we are calling to choose when we want to check if our prediction algorithm is working properly. #foodsafety #predictiveanalytics</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_episode-4-focus-on-the-right-prediction-activity-6760153110779359232-b_bz/</p>
<p>28/1/2021</p>	<p>Do you want to harness the untapped potential of AI-powered prediction machines and lead to an important change in your company, anticipating and mitigating food risks? In this episode, Giannis (John) Stoitsis, CTO, and partner at Agroknow (Coordinator of the BigDataGrapes project), presents the way to integrate predictions into an operation mode, so AI can lead to an important change in your company. In addition, this video focuses on how we can update and automate predictions, ensuring continuous integration with systems and external data for more accurate decision making. #foodsafety #predictiveanalytics</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_episode-5-how-to-integrate-predictions-activity-6760488368041181184-oDL4/</p>
<p>29/1/2021</p>	<p>Are you interested on how you can use the predictions methodology in the food sector? In this episode, Giannis (John) Stoitsis , CTO and partner at Agroknow (Coordinator partner of the BigDataGrapes project), presents the right way of applying the lessons learned from these BigDataGrapes' project short video series in the Chocolate Industry. During the previous videos of the BigDataGrapes series we explained all the theoretical background on how to use Predictions in the food sector. Now, it is time to focus on how we can implement all this gained-knowledge and methodology (that combines big data processing technologies with artificial intelligence technologies), in the chocolate products and their ingredients.</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_episode-6-how-to-apply-lessons-learned-activity-6760962893086294017-F9P8</p>
<p>29/1/2021</p>	<p>Did you miss the webinar that KU Leuven and Agroknow organized on "Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention: Towards visually appealing & highly interactive predictions"? Then you can watch it here, in the link that exists down on this post! The webinar provided insights into the business challenges for the food industry as well as the scientific challenges for UX</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/bigdat agrapeseu_predictive-analytics-for-food-risk-prevention-activity-6760972151471304704-SufV</p>

	<p>researchers when talking about predictive analytics, and how to overcome them.</p> <p>Main topics that discussed were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From a business question to a risk dashboard: the food safety intelligence equation; - Designing an appealing, interactive & trustful prediction dashboard: visualization components & technologies; - A Food Risk Prediction Dashboard example and how it works. 	
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Publish Date	Post message / text	Post URL
2018		
15/1/2018	@BigDataGrapes kicks off! Enter our http://bigdatagrapes.eu and join our linkedin group https://linkedin.com/groups/13574473/ #BigData #H2020 #grapes	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/952906516985675776
15/1/2018	The disruption of the grape-powered industry starts tomorrow in the Agricultural University of Athens. Follow discussions through @BigDataGrapes and #bigdatagrapes	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/952929065236910088
16/1/2018	Our first project meeting is officially on! Pythagoras from @AgroKnow shares fascinating details behind the project conception #BigData #H2020 #research #innovation	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/953179670542999552
17/1/2018	Day 2 of #BigDataGrapes kick off, and Spyros Fountas from the Agricultural University of Athens explains the activities around the #grape production pilot	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/953595703762345984
17/1/2018	Consortium family photo under the blue athenian sky! The 2nd day of the kick-off meeting is over and grape-powered Industry Application Pilots are set! #BigDataGrapes #H2020	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/953672109770895360
18/1/2018	Day 3 of #BigDataGrapes kick off is all about #BigData technologies. Nicola from @StampaCnr presents the analytics and processing WP #H2020	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/953915359471562752
1/2/2018	Reading in @qz "Can winemakers defeat the climate models that are predicting their demise?" https://qz.com/1189627 Looking fwd to see how #BigData will help grapes to overcome #ClimateChange	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/959022461642858497
27/3/2018	Connection established! First Day of #BigDataGrapes vineyard experiments has started. In-field data collection from the teams of Agricultural University of Athens.	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/978542100982661120

27/3/2018	That's the beginning of another excellent year. Bud burst in the vineyard marks the start of seasonal growth. The best moment to start collecting grape and vine growth #data !	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/978555977086599168
28/3/2018	Mapping and data collection is a process that needs both stamina and precision! Here the team of #AUA in an #organic vineyard with indigenous Greek grape varieties.	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/978934133148803072
29/3/2018	Wines from Far East are riding the #BigData wave! Read more on a case from Japan on how growers and wineries are discovering the scientific aspects of the japanese terroir using data: https://nippon.com/en/features/co4602/	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/979265848543272961
4/4/2018	Get a glimpse of the predecessor of #BigDataGrapes developed by @AgroKnow. A digital hub collecting the knowledge and practice of the Greek #vineyard - extracting value out of #bigdata @EU_H2020 #ResearchImpactEU #InvestEUresearch	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/981401982014455808
5/4/2018	From landfill to lipstick: A treasure is hidden in #grape pressing waste. Read more on @ScienceDaily: https://sciencedaily.com/releases/2018/03/180319090734.htm #ResearchImpactEU #InvestEUresearch	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/981830906473254912
5/5/2018	Next week our partner @ontotext will be at the @BDVA_PPP meetup in Sofia. Reach out to @YankovaMilena for more details on how we disrupt the grape-powered industry taking advantage of #BigData and cutting-edge technologies #BigDataGrapes	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/994590132123652097
10/5/2018	Here is our latest presentation from @YankovaMilena of @ontotext during the @BDVA_PPP #bdvmeetupsofia18 https://slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/big-data-grapes-bdv-meetup-sofia	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/999943879871909888
27/5/2018	Our Sunday afternoon read from @stephenburanyi / @gdnlongread: https://theguardian.com/news/2018/may/15/has-wine-gone-bad-organic-biodynamic-natural-wine As detoxification of the grape & wine industry is more than a trend, data science & tech can support elimination of chemicals in vinegrowing & winemaking, supported by the wealth of #BigData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1000738504412942337
1/6/2018	Touring the slopes of #Nemea, the largest wine-producing region in the Balkans. The team of AUA is collecting data related to canopy characteristics and vegetation indices.	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1002475086572646400
2/6/2018	Saturday vineyard visit for photosynthesis measurement in the	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes

	slopes of ancient Corinth. #datacollection never stops!	/status/1002861144770572288
4/7/2018	Good news!!! The #APIGEA team started collecting data from the vineyards of Athens natural cosmetics pilot is in action!!!!	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1014435890712731654
18/7/2018	Hosted by @Inra_France and @Supagro for the next two days the heart of @BigDataGrapes beats at #Montpellier #H2020 #BigData #Viticulture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1019503281738080256
18/7/2018	Panagiotis @pzervas from @AgroKnow welcomes the consortium of @BigDataGrapes and presents the main achievements of the project until today #BigData #viticulture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1019507505486073856
18/7/2018	The current progress of WP2 - Grapevine-powered Industries Big Data Challenges is presented by Pythagoras @pythk. Some of the main issues regarding the #DataManagement and the Overall #DataProcessing Architecture were discussed	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1019513397749182464
19/7/2018	Last night @Inra_France and @Supagro provided a special Social Dinner to @BigDataGrapes team members at #Montpellier. It was the perfect way to complete the first day of the meeting!!	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1019862575104831488
19/7/2018	The second day of @BigDataGrapes 2nd Meeting has started!!! Pythagoras @pythk from @AgroKnow presented the first session by describing the current progress and the next steps of the Integration & Deployment of the project	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1019866109569392640
19/7/2018	Franco Maria @fmmardini from @StampaCnr presented and Pythagoras @pythk from @AgroKnow gave some important inputs regarding the design and execution of the rigorous testing of the project's proposed technical solutions #viticulture #BigData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1019931814088073216
19/7/2018	Right now Francisco García Cirujano and Nyi Nyi Htun from @KU_Leuven present the current progress of the technologies for producing added value from large data collections #BigData #Montpellier @BigDataGrapes	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1019957623062450176
20/7/2018	Welcome to the only experimental & transfer structure dedicated to research in the fields of viticulture and oenology with an integrated point of view. Hello from INRA Pech Rouge Experimental Vineyard! @BigDataGrapes	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1020223837655453697
20/7/2018	INRA Pech Rouge Experimental Vineyard has installed a meteorological station that calculates the direction and speed of the wind, the temperature, the humidity and the rainfall @BigDataGrapes #viticulture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1020231930774806528
20/7/2018	What an educational experience!!! @BigDataGrapes 2nd	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes

	Meeting participants visited the wine production facilities at INRA Pech Rouge Experimental Vineyard @BigDataGrapes	/status/1020236971745177601
27/7/2018	As climate changes so will grape varieties!! Reading in @Harvard gazette and wondering how exploitation of #BigData will strengthen the adaptation to lesser-known grape varieties. http://bit.ly/2LFoE5Y #climatechange #viticulture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1022825565232017408
1/8/2018	Celebrating August. We loved this interesting and educational data story	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1024583159126679552
7/8/2018	This is sad news. Farmers of #Bordeaux vineyards expect to lose between 20 and 70 per cent of their crop to mildew that ravages France's largest wine-growing region. You can read more here http://bit.ly/2OiEK6d	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1026830786782261248
8/8/2018	Perfect for a summer night with a glass of wine. Chill it down slightly and flavours come into focus, alcohol becomes less apparent, structure tightens up and the wine is more refreshing to drink. For wine recommendations & more info read http://bit.ly/2OjYpCz #winetasting #bigdatagrapes	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1027222915950039040
9/8/2018	Still wondering how big data will change viticulture? We have all the answers. Read more here http://bit.ly/2no1EO6 #BigData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1027298404928352256
9/8/2018	Here is a great way to start enjoying Cretan wine and learn more about it.	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1027557706226388992
11/8/2018	Big data can help you pick better wine. With Big Data we can directly identify the wines most similar to wines we already know are favorites. For more information read here http://bit.ly/2nIVPRn #winetasting #BigDataGrapes	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1028314347821457408
30/8/2018	On 2018, the fine quality of the grapes on our partner vineyards, the @KontogiannisFam Estate remained the same, even though the amount of grapes harvested is less due to bad weather. @BigDataGrapes aims to understand and help the producer overcome problems like that!	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1035082801513676801
8/9/2018	Harvest time and in-field measurements once again in Nemea in the context of @BigDataGrapes project from @vitislab and PA Labs, Agricultural University of Athens	https://twitter.com/vitislab/status/1038339827639431168
20/9/2018	Finally consumers are at the center of the strategy. Finally we can base decisions on solid data and not feelings and wine marketers could enjoy a new era where the market needs are clearly identified and managed. @BigDataGrapes. Read more	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1042757341404377088

	here http://bit.ly/2pp5xDB	
15/10/2018	The harvest of grapes has been successfully completed at Fasoulis, Palivou and @KontogiannisFam estates. The whole process of selecting the right harvest time was based on the data provided by the recently installed weather station. @BigDataGrapes	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1051778571264581633
26/10/2018	Save the date! The next European #BigData Value Forum will take place on 12th - 14th November in Vienna.	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1055820543243497472
26/10/2018	The second of the #BDVE series of webinars related to Big Data technologies will be held on Tuesday, November 6, 2018! Register now!	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1055824020745175041
5/11/2018	When you work with such unquenchable partners. Our project colleague @ontotext wrote a very interesting post about our project by the name From Cultivating Nature to Cultivating Data: Semantic Technology and Viticulture. Read more here https://ontotext.com/from-cultivating-nature-to-cultivating-data-semantic-technology-and-viticulture/ #data	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1059422797401853953
12/11/2018	The European Big Data Value Forum, the key European event aiming to overcome all challenges and to exploit all opportunities of the European data economy and data-driven innovation in Europe has just started!! Stay tuned! #BigData #EBDVF2018	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1061904504264839168
14/11/2018	The Agricultural University of Athens participated through its Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Technology Transfer Office (#InnovInAgri) at the 2nd Athens Innovation Festival (#AIF2018), where the @BigDataGrapes project was presented with the use of brochures. Congratulations!	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1062695940065239045
30/11/2018	Today, at the Conferenza del Dipartimento #Cnr-Diitet - Area strategica '#Informatica', the @BigDataGrapes project was presented with the use of brochures and poster. #BigData #openscience #opendata	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1068514467581898752
20/12/2018	Great news! @BigDataGrapes project successfully released its first Annual Report. To learn more about its vision and the project's advancements achieved during the first year of its execution please check http://bigdatagrapes.eu/node/59	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1075760241038581760
2019		
16/1/2019	The Agricultural University of Athens presented the @BigDataGrapes project at the #SFARM workshop. Congratulations! #BigData #openscience #opendata	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1085465913820958720

4/2/2019	Thank you for mentioning us @kathimerini_gr! #OpenData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1092393550208217093
20/2/2019	The BigDataGrapes project consortium in collaboration with the Department of Agriculture, Food and Environment of the University of Pisa will organize a one-day workshop on 8 March 2019 in Pisa, Italy. The Agenda is available here https://tinyurl.com/y529dtgn Register now!	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1098157645087805440
22/2/2019	We are so pleased for mentioning us @derStandardat! #BigData #OpenData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1098925150064599041
1/3/2019	Good Month to everyone! Only a week has left until the workshop on “Big Data for the Grapevine Industries” on 8 March 2019 in Pisa, Italy. You can register here https://bit.ly/2Ta5JaU Register now #opendata #BigData #openscience	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1101391096444342272
6/3/2019	For the next two days, the heart of @BigDataGrapes beats at #Pisa. The 3rd PMB Meeting has started, hosted by @StampaCnr. #opendata #BigData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103227995332988936
6/3/2019	The current progress of WP8 - Grapevine-powered Industry Application Pilots is presented by Katerina Kassimati, representative of the Agricultural University of Athens - Laboratory of Farm Machinery #BigData #viticulture #vitislab	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103279655715524608
6/3/2019	Coraline Damasio from @Inra_France presented the current progress of the Wine Making Pilot and identified the next steps. #opendata #BigData #viticulture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103301513840132096
6/3/2019	Florian Schlenz from Geocledian and Simone Parisi from @Abaco_Group gave some important inputs regarding the Farm Management Pilot current progress and future plans. #viticulture #BigData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103316982869487617
7/3/2019	The second day of @BigDataGrapes 3rd Project Meeting has started. Milena Yankova from @ontotext presented the first session by describing the current progress and the next steps, for the following 6 months, of the WP3 - Data & Semantics Layer. #BigData #viticulture #OpenData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103599648751661057
7/3/2019	#Happeningnow @fmmardini from @StampaCnr presents the current status of the WP7 - Cross sector Rigorous Experimental Testing along with its concrete plans for the next 6 months @BigDataGrapes #BigData #opendata #viticulture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103617321610944512
7/3/2019	Last night, in Pisa - @StampaCnr hosted the perfect dinner for the	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103623122266345472

	@BigDataGrapes team. The perfect ending to our first day of the meeting!	
7/3/2019	Last day of the @BigDataGrapes Project Meeting - @pzervas from @AgroKnow has just presented the last deck about the current progress and the upcoming new steps on the WP6 - Integration & Deployment. #BigData #viticulture #OpenData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103656628983861249
8/3/2019	Thank you @LaSpinettaItaly & @offigari for the amazing wine tasting experience! Our 3rd Project Meeting couldn't have a better ending #BigData #viticulture #OpenData @BigDataGrapes	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103942335061282817
8/3/2019	The Workshop on “Big Data for the Grapevine Industries” has just began. @raffaele_perego from the National Research Council (Cnr) was the first to welcome the attendees. #BigData #viticulture #OpenData @BigDataGrapes	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103952295413338112
8/3/2019	A precious moment; Bringing together all the stakeholders from the grapevine industry. This is the @BigDataGrapes project. #opendata #BigData #viticulture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103959381765509120
8/3/2019	Katerina Kassimati from the Agricultural University of Athens - Laboratory of Farm Machinery gave interesting input regarding the current progress of the Table and Wine Grapes Pilot @vitislab #viticulture #BigData #opendata @BigDataGrapes	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103970639877160960
8/3/2019	All developments implemented in the Wine Making Pilot were described from Pascal Neveu from @inra_france #opendata #BigData #openscience @BigDataGrapes	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103978009793650690
8/3/2019	Eleni foufa from Symbeosis Long Live Life S.A. talked about the work that has been done until today regarding the Natural Cosmetics Pilot progress. #opendata #BigData #openscience @BigDataGrapes #viticulture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103979570896781312
8/3/2019	Well done Katerina! #opendata #BigData #viticulture @BigDataGrapes @vitislab	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103980743439601664
8/3/2019	#Happeningnow Giovanni Caruso from the University of Pisa presents the innovative research done on the precision viticulture at the Department of Agriculture Food and Environment #opendata #BigData #openscience @BigDataGrapes #viticulture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103990790383169536
8/3/2019	The current progress of the Farm Management Pilot was captured in the presentation of Florian Schlenz from	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1103991129052274690

	Geocledian and Simone Parisi from @Abaco_Group. #viticulture #BigData #OpenData @BigDataGrapes	
8/3/2019	Marco Panizza from @NetafimCorp described the function of the NetBeat: The first irrigation system with a brain. #viticulture #BigData #OpenData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1104000380202041344
8/3/2019	Saving the best for last - a discussion about the Challenges at the grapevine industries and how Big Data can address them. #viticulture #BigData #OpenData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1104020738485424128
13/5/2019	This week @geocledian will participate at #ESA Living Planet Symposium #LPS19 by presenting a poster on Ag knowledge Earth Observation data analytics platform and its role in the @BigDataGrapes project. Check more here https://bit.ly/2VuILYW #climatechange #EarthObservation	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1127906951864750080
27/5/2019	Save the day and register now! Webinar alert! Are you interested in improving the way you monitor your field? Then join the @BigDataGrapes webinar on May 29 here https://bit.ly/2W6RMfj #opendata #learningtogether #bigdata	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1132957124844294145
3/6/2019	Our partner AUA started again the data collection. The pictures demonstrate the soil sampling collection and the vines scanning to record vegetation indexes data @BigDataGrapes #BigData #opendata	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1135462812149592064
3/7/2019	@BigDataGrapes send eyes into the sky once more. AUA used two drones equipped with a multispectral and a thermal camera to collect aerial imagery data #OpenData #BigData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1146411894955237377
5/9/2019	The consortium gathered for an important milestone in Luxembourg today. It's the mid-term project review where we discuss on the progress made so far and we set the strategy ahead! #BigData #viticulture #H2020	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1169534385059704833
22/9/2019	The time has come! Our partner in Pech Rouge are gathering their grapes #BigData #OpenData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1175717202563162112
9/10/2019	The first day of BigDataGrapes 4th Project Meeting has started and pilot leaders have just presented how their collected data can be collaborated with the developed software tools. #OpenData #BigData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1181850310471553024
14/10/2019	The project @BigDataGrapes participates, ones more, at the @BDVA_PPP that is held this year in #helsinki. To learn more about the project, come and visit our booth (B2). We will be	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1183662732006035456

	glad to solve all your questions.	
14/10/2019	The interest of @BDVA_PPP participants on @BigDataGrapes project during the first day of the event was impressive! We are waiting for many more participants to visit us tomorrow. #bigdata #OpenData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1183733322112995328
15/10/2019	Thank you @AlexandraGaratz for your interest in @BigDataGrapes project! #BigData #OpenData #agriculture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1184095745009471488
15/10/2019	The second day of the @BDVA_PPP event was a very productive one! Many participants were impressed with @BigDataGrapes project. We will wait for many more of your questions at our booth (B2) tomorrow during the last day of the event #BigData #OpenData #agriculture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1184116722045018114
16/10/2019	Today was the last day of the @BDVA_PPP event and we successfully managed to disseminate the aims and outcomes of the project. #BigData #OpenData #agriculture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1184419635262902272
30/10/2019	The 13th China International Food Safety & Quality (CIFSQ) Conference will be held this year on October 30 – 31, 2019 in Beijing, P. R. China. Among the 700 regulators, industry executives, and academics that are expected to attend @AgroKnow will be there to showcase FOODAKAI	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1189447921919561728
1/11/2019	During his presentation in CIFSQ, @AgroKnow's Director of Technology @stoitsis had the chance to showcase the value that the FOODAKAI offers and the benefits that industry users can get. #FoodSafety #foodsafetynow #BigData #Food #foodsecurity	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1190162200641626112
8/11/2019	#Agritechnica: The world's largest Agriculture & Technology trade fair will be held in Hannover #Germany next week, November 10-16 and our project partner @geocledian will participate and demonstrate @BigDataGrapes. For more information stay tuned!! #OpenData #BigData #satellite	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1192810792342740993
12/11/2019	This week @geocledian will have a stand (D51 in hall P11) at #Agritechnica to present their products & the aims of our project. Visit us if you would like to learn about remote sensing for agriculture & the @BigDataGrapes project. It would be great to meet you there!#OpenData	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1194149363104256000
16/11/2019	Geocledian had a great week at #Agritechnica ! We had excellent meetings, interesting insights into current #agtech trends and a great time with our customers and partners. Explained a lot of people what #satellite #remotesensing and #DataAnalytics can offer for #agriculture .	https://twitter.com/geocledian/status/1195649349864349696

18/11/2019	During the previous week @geocledian participated at #Agritechnica & had the opportunity to communicate the outcomes of @BigDataGrapes to many companies that are dealing with grapevine data from Greece, France & Italy. #OpenData #BigData #satellite #remotesensing #DataAnalytics	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1196332698127745025
29/11/2019	Only one week left for applying to the Data Science challenge! Which SME is going to win the €10,000 prize? Secure your participation and apply now here: https://bit.ly/33BWFw5 #BigData #OpenData #agriculture	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1200422100873482240
2020		
27/2/2020	This week we're in #Seattle to present how #BigData technologies can foster #foodsafety across the supply chain and ensure that consumers have access to safe food.	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1233149396184915976
5/3/2020	Why do our partners from @INRAE_France count grapevine leaves? Learn how #machinelearning and #deeplearning techniques contribute to moving one step closer to precision viticulture through #BigDataGrapes @EU_H2020 http://bigdatagrapes.eu/node/105	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1235503163324731392
19/3/2020	#ThrowbackThursday to our last week's meeting at the great outdoors of @INRAE_France where we set the ground for the evaluation of the project's Software Demonstrators	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1240590261052411904
26/3/2020	Another #tbt to @DataWUR #ISESS2020 where Ioanna from @AgroKnow presented the capabilities of the project's #bigdata experimentation platform. You can reach out for the full presentation in our @SlideShare account: slideshare.net/BigDataGrapes/big-data-grapespresentation-for-data-science-in-actionisess-2020-230920921	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1243235747710341122
29/4/2020	Our 5th Project Meeting is on! Virtually this time, due to #COVID19, we are discussing the updates on progress and the latest developments in our 5 pilots	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1255475169113657344
29/4/2020	It might look like a piece of contemporary art - but this is a first visualization shared by @KU_Leuven on the effects of different parameters (from vine to vinification) that affect the quality and characteristics of the produced wine #linkeddata in action!	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1255487519615041539
4/5/2020	Last week all project partners met online for the 5th Project Management Board Meeting. Topics on the agenda? ▫ Pilots progress ▫ Data integration ▫ Tech Roadmap ▫ Key results	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1257184430390513664

	And of course #happyfaces	
4/5/2020	How do the grapevines respond to terroir? Here is one of the latest visualizations of the table and wine grapes pilot including yield mapping and earth observation data. Next step? The visualization of yield evolution through time across the vineyard parcels #BigData #wine	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1257235265405497350
4/5/2020	Last week's meeting in a nutshell. Which are the key priorities of all partners for the next 6 months?	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1257299438483066880
20/5/2020	Celebrating #WorldBeeDay today, and we explore our natural cosmetics pilot, where bee and grape products are key raw materials. Read more on how we use #BigData to predict which area would supply grape leaves of the best quality for natural cosmetics. http://bigdatagrapes.eu/node/106	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1263037294078033920
26/5/2020	Have you ever wondered how #artificialintelligence can help to analyze the influence of climatic effects or the winemaking process on the aromatic composition of wine? Thanks to our colleagues from @INRAE_France #MISTEA @UMR_LEPSE that have the answers! http://bigdatagrapes.eu/node/107	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1265184791307190272
29/5/2020	This week our colleague @Diego_Rojo_ from @AugmentHCI presented at the virtual session of #EuroVis2020 their approach to designing a novel system for correlation visualization, GaCoVi. Learn more on how it helps viticulture and vinification domain experts https://youtu.be/edIPfDIH1p0?t=4003	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1266306771100057602
1/6/2020	How to increase productivity and grape quality using #BigData This is one of the four critical business questions that we answer in real-life business cases of the BigDataGrapes project. Read more on the case of ABACO Farmer software: http://bigdatagrapes.eu/node/109	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1267414841196711937
11/6/2020	Last week the team of Agricultural University of Athens as part of the training on “New technologies for Sustainable Farming” under the #generationaggrece program, presented the “Application of Precision Agriculture in Vineyards” through @BigDataGrapes. #neageorgianeagenia	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1271028027271634944
15/6/2020	Demystifying “terroir” @maritina155 from @vitislab explains the critical questions that the researchers and data scientists of @BigDataGrapes will answer in the Table and Wine Grapes Pilot. Can we predict grape yield & correlate it with grape quality? http://bigdatagrapes.eu/node/111	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1272441632990822400
25/6/2020	What happens when image processing, #deeplearning and	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes

	data visualizations come together for grapevine growth? More to follow soon, from the labs of @AugmentHCI @UMR_LEPSE @INRAE_France @KU_Leuven	/status/1276083697050103809
26/6/2020	Can we see from space if a vineyard needs water? @geocledian presents how the #farmmanagement pilot answers fundamental farming questions with #bigdata and water balance modeling, thanks to @CopernicusEU Read more on http://bigdatagrapes.eu/node/112	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1276417233678479360
26/6/2020	How does #blockchain technology ensure the authenticity of wine? Read on @ITProPortal about the benefits of providence information sharing @everledgerio what if we bring #bigdata on the wine blockchain, ranging from vineyard to winery and the bottle?	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1276473531295911936
30/6/2020	Semantics: How are we leveraging domain-specific ontologies? @INRAE_Intl and @ontotext explain how we deal with multidimensional data representation ranging from viticulture to winemaking for advancing viticultural research and producing top quality wines http://bigdatagrapes.eu/node/113	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1277990695870124035
15/7/2020	At @BigDataGrapes, we are passionate about working with end-users to determine their pain points and create a solution that fits their real needs. Have a look at some snippets from our hands-on evaluation session, kindly hosted by @INRAE_Intl http://bigdatagrapes.eu	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1283315537691529216
11/9/2020	A journey from vine to wine in pictures. @INRAE_Intl, visited The “Cave Coopérative Les Trois Grappes” to understand better the viticulture part and the “Vignerons de la Vicomté” for bottling and #winetasting. Take the journey: http://bigdatagrapes.eu/node/114	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1304422127605514240
14/10/2020	Almost 45% of food industry experts have heard about predictive analytics but haven't tried it. Can we prevent food fraud and safety incidents from happening? Just give it a try! #artificialintelligence #ai #predictiveanalytics #foodindustry #foodsafety.	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1316400976442675202
9/11/2020	The 6th Project Meeting of the BDG has been successfully completed. The consortium is close to introducing to the global market the innovative and progressive results of the BigDataGrapes project for the wine and cosmetics industry. Stay tuned for more! bigdatagrapes.eu/node/116	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1325817564925194240

22/12/2020	Curious about how food safety predictive analytics should work to ensure that they deliver reliable predictions to support business-critical decisions? Our intro video from a short video series is here, addressing the critical questions on this topic. bigdatagrapes.eu/node/119	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1341365613684531200
23/12/2020	Interested in how you can solve the Food Safety intelligence equation for more effective predictive analytics? BigDataGrapes' new episode is released, providing you all the must-information for a better-handling of the predictive analytics. Check it out: http://bigdatagrapes.eu/node/120	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1341782799888609282
2021		
5/1/2021	We would like to invite you to a virtual panel discussion on "Predictive Analytics for the Food Supply Chain". The panel brings together 5 speakers representing 5 leading Food Safety Technology Companies. #BigData #PredictiveAnalytics More info: bigdatagrapes.eu/node/136	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1346503493767585796
8/1/2021	Fascinated with predictive analytics? Wonder how to select the right data? Then, don't miss out the new short video series' episode by BigDataGrapes project! Check it here!	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1347515109757890564
21/1/2021	Are you confused about choosing the right food risk prediction algorithm to make the most of a predictive analytics solution? Then, don't miss out the new short video series' episode by BigDataGrapes project! #BigData #PredictiveAnalytics Check it here: https://youtube.com/watch?v=YDqnIKOFXBI&t=3s	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1352185821965807616
21/1/2021	We would like to invite you to a webinar organized by @KU_Leuven and @Agroknow on "Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention: Towards visually appealing & highly interactive predictions". Don't miss it! #BigData #PredictiveAnalytics Register here!	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1352202023664558080
27/1/2021	Are you looking for the right prediction metrics to measure if your prediction algorithm is working properly? This and more answers you can find them on the 4th episode of the BigDataGrapes short video series. #BigData #PredictiveAnalytics	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1354385836360560641

	Check it here!	
28/1/2021	Do you want to harness the untapped potential of AI-powered prediction machines and lead to an important change in your company, anticipating and mitigating food risks? #BigData #PredictiveAnalytics Then, don't miss to check out our new episode!	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1354720725605765125
29/1/2021	Are you interested on how you can use the predictions methodology in the food sector? Then fasten your seatbelts for a "tasteful" trip on predictive analytics in the chocolate industry! #BigData #PredictiveAnalytics	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1355196197498191874
29/1/2021	Did you miss the webinar that @KU_Leuven and @Agroknow organized on "Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention: Towards visually appealing & highly interactive predictions"? Then you can watch it here, with all the topics that have been discussed!	https://twitter.com/BigDataGrapes/status/1355203875406544901

Publish Date	Post message / text	Post URL
2019		
3/6/2019	Webinar on Field Monitoring in the context of BigDataGrapes project	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TE3dEILLegU
2020		
10/6/2020	BigDataGrapes Data Collection at Kontogiannis Estate	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZVfgOHxiE4w
8/12/2020	A series of videos explaining food safety predictions for Busy People - Intro	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uas3XYjF9tk
22/12/2020	Episode 1 - The food risk prevention question to drive effective predictive analytics	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tww8f_o_ohk
2021		
8/1/2021	Episode 2 - How to select the right data	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BbY1JajaeG4
21/1/2021	Virtual Panel Discussion on Predictive Analytics in	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q3iC

	the context of BigDataGrapes project	gtNoiCI
21/1/2021	Episode 3 - How to select the right food risk prediction algorithm?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YDqnIKOFXBI
26/1/2021	Predictive Analytics for Food Risk Prevention Webinar in the context of BigDataGrapes project	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a8jXMfQNRBQ
27/1/2021	Episode 4 - Focus on the right prediction metrics	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t8KNvd-3Nuc
28/1/2021	Episode 5 - How to integrate predictions in your work flows	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yjCnmW6wa3I
29/1/2020	Episode 6 - How to apply lessons learned about a specific industry – the Chocolate Industry	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1bLa70s4dSU&t=1s
29/1/2020	Online workshop on Predictive Analytics	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ad9nxYBl2dw&t=303s
29/1/2020	GFSR interviews Nikos Manouselis on extracting data from the Supply Chain	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UbgUh1J_5bQ
31/1/2021	Episode 7 - How can we predict a food recall before it happens?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UbgUh1J_5bQ